

BAMBOO

D2.7: Definition of specifications and data requirements for electricity flexibility and energy market constraints

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0 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main purpose of this document is to provide an overview of energy and gas markets in the countries represented by the project partners, as regards generation and demand, the main structure of the power market as well as the legal and economic framework. The main trends and differences among countries have been highlighted.

This document is also meant to map the main requirement for energy flexibility strategies in the analysed countries, according to technological advances as well as to restrictions and specific regulations, especially what concerns the provision of ancillary services and implicit flexibility options.

The contents are based on the analyses performed by the involved partners through detailed questionnaires, in order to collect comparable data and achieve a common framework within the task.

Within Task 2.5, models to forecast the day-ahead price in the German market have been developed and will serve as a support for the decision making. Their description complements the information provided for the relative energy markets.

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The work documented in this deliverable has been carried out within the framework of Task 2.5 “*Analysis of requirements concerning electricity flexibility subject to energy market conditions*”, which will be concluded in month 16 with the submission of this report.

The task aims at gathering the characteristics of the power and natural gas markets in different countries to get an overview of the advances made towards flexible energy markets, including issues related to the provision of ancillary services and the integration of renewable energy sources.

Based on algorithms developed in previous work by N-SIDE for the Belgian energy market, forecasting models have been adapted to the German market and have been optimized for the requirements of the DSS-toolbox to be developed in WP6 by N-SIDE.

The political and technical framework of energy flexibility in the energy market in general and in particular in the industrial sector is provided and discussed in this document with the aim of mapping the main requirements for energy flexibility and assess the implementation potential of different strategies.

The document is structured as follows

- In chapter 3 the trends and main differences identified in energy markets are presented; detailed qualitative analysis of energy markets, main actors and legal and economic framework in different countries are provided in Annex II, III and IV.
- In chapter 4 the aforementioned forecasting models for power prices are described.
- Chapter 5 summarizes the requirements for energy flexibility in the countries analysed in chapter 3, highlighting key trends and opportunities; detailed descriptions of the technological, legal and economic framework, as well as the main strategies for the implementation of energy flexibility in each country are described in detail in Annex IV.
- Chapter 6 contains the main conclusion drawn in relation to the presented content and the identified issues related to energy flexibility.

2 METHODOLOGY

As the main aim was to gather relevant information and data related to the energy markets where the demo-sites are based, at a first instance Germany, Spain, Turkey and Greece have been the focus of the qualitative analysis. TUBS took over the analysis for Germany, IKL for Spain and Turkey, supported by RINA-C, and CERTH for Greece.

In order to provide a wider set of results at European level, the analysis was extended to other countries represented by the BAMBOO partners, i.e. Norway, France, Italy, Austria and Belgium. TUBS carried out the study for Norway and France, RINA-C for Italy, EI for Austria and N-SIDE for Belgium.

With the purpose of collecting the data in an organic way, TUBS prepared a questionnaire, with the support of N-SIDE, to be filled-up by all involved partners for each country. The consolidated version of the questionnaire can be found in the Annex I - Questionnaire for qualitative analysis of Energy markets and assessment of energy flexibility requirements.

The questionnaire consists of three main sections: energy and gas markets, energy flexibility and implementation of energy flexibility strategy.

In the first section a general overview of the energy market shall be provided, including generation and demand, the market structure as well as legal and economic frameworks. In the second section the technological framework of energy flexibility shall be assessed, with focus on the industrial sector. Details related to explicit flexibility, as ancillary services and reserve markets, as well as implicit flexibility, including the issues related to the fluctuation of energy prices shall be described. In the last section selected flexibility strategies can be assessed from an economic, technical and environmental perspective.

The questionnaire was filled-up by the involved partners, using as basis data from statistics, databases, energy companies, national operators, governmental and public institutions.

In parallel to this activity, N-SIDE has been working on the development of power prices forecasts and on the development of a forecasting platform to facilitate the visualization and export of forecasted values.

3 QUALITATIVE ANALYSES OF ENERGY MARKETS

Based on the developed questionnaires, relevant data related to the energy and gas markets were collected by the involved partners. In the following, a summary of the main characteristics of each country is provided, following the information gathered in the first section of the questionnaire. The main trends and differences for all countries have been identified.

In this chapter only main conclusions are introduced. Further data regarding national markets, the structure of the energy market and the main actors as well as the legal and economic framework can be found in ANNEX II - national energy market, ANNEX III - STRUCTURE OF ENERGY MARKETS AND MAIN ACTORS and ANNEX IV - LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK, respectively.

3.1 Identification of trends and main differences

Table 3.1 provides an overview of the final energy consumption by sectors and by energy carriers in the analysed countries. Germany is the biggest energy consumer within the analysed countries, followed by France and Italy.

In Germany the most energy-intensive sector is the transportation one, directly followed by households and industry. The most consumed energy carriers in the German industrial sector are natural gas and electricity.

In Spain the transportation sector has the highest share on the final consumption, followed by the industrial sector, with a high demand of gas and electricity.

In Turkey the industrial sector is the biggest energy consumer, with a high demand of gas, electricity and solid fossil fuels.

The energy consumption in Greece is dominated by the transport sector, followed by households and industry. The main consumed energy carriers in the industrial sectors are oil and electricity.

In Norway the industrial sector is responsible for the highest share of energy consumption, with a high demand of electricity and oil.

In France the transportation sector is the main consumer. The industrial sector is characterized by a high demand of electricity and natural gas.

The Italian energy consumption is dominated by the transport sector, directly followed by households. In the industrial sector the most used energy carriers are electricity and natural gas, followed by heat.

Austria and Belgium are smaller in size and population in comparison to the other countries and have therefore a lower energy consumption. In Austria the transport and industrial sector are dominant in term of consumption, while in Belgium the industrial sector is the most energy-intensive. In both countries the industrial sector is characterized by a high demand of electricity and natural gas.

Table 3.1: Final energy consumption in the analysed countries (2017) [1]

Energy Consumption (ktoe)										
Country	Type	Total	Solid Fossil Fuels	Manuf. gases	Oil & petroleum products	Natural gas	RES & bio-fuels	Waste	Heat	Electricity
Germany	Total	204.604,4	4.547,9	2.194,8	73.663,0	52.771,6	15.871,0	1.126,7	9.807,0	44.622,4
	Industry	56.272,6	4.029,2	2.194,8	2.075,1	20.360,7	2.763,4	1.126,7	4.110,4	19.612,3
	Transport	57.242,6	0,0	0,0	53.158,2	457,0	2.599,3	0,0	Z	1.028,1
	Commercial	34.451,7	18,3	0,0	6.996,6	10.355,7	2.856,8	0,0	1.265,5	12.958,8
	Households	56.552,3	500,4	0,0	11.347,9	21.598,2	7.651,4	0,0	4.431,1	11.023,2
	Agriculture & Forestry	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	Others	85,2	0,0	0,0	85,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Spain	Total	79.397,4	649,5	236,7	38.805,8	13.485,8	6.043,2	7,0	0,0	20.169,5
	Industry	18.973,8	531,7	236,7	2.878,0	6.884,6	1.611,3	0,0	0,0	6.831,5
	Transport	31.722,8	0,0	0,0	29.935,1	373,2	959,5	0,0	Z	454,9
	Commercial	10.413,0	0,0	0,0	1.290,6	2.404,6	471,0	7,0	0,0	6.239,8
	Households	15.435,2	79,3	0,0	2.674,4	3.747,5	2.914,3	0,0	0,0	6.019,7
	Agriculture & Forestry	2.404,2	0,0	0,0	1.754,8	75,6	76,9	0,0	0,0	496,8
	Others	448,5	38,5	0,0	272,9	0,3	10,1	0,0	0,0	126,7
Turkey	Total	100.457,1	11.793,9	311,9	36.218,3	24.745,2	5.210,6	0,0	1.034,2	21.143,1
	Industry	32.114,4	6.027,7	311,9	4.402,2	10.296,6	295,0	0,0	1.034,2	9.746,7
	Transport	28.305,5	0,0	0,0	27.613,0	435,9	145,6	0,0	Z	111,1
	Commercial	13.565,2	3.804,8	0,0	935,7	2.788,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	6.036,0
	Households	22.159,0	1.961,3	0,0	245,0	11.126,9	4.161,0	0,0	0,0	4.664,8
	Agriculture & Forestry	4.168,8	0,0	0,0	2.937,4	56,8	609,0	0,0	0,0	565,6
	Others	144,2	0,0	0,0	84,9	40,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	19,0
Greece	Total	16.054,2	195,7	0,0	8.329,2	1.180,1	1.657,7	0,0	51,1	4.640,5
	Industry	3.096,3	190,4	0,0	1.058,7	655,5	135,4	0,0	0,0	1.056,2
	Transport	5.815,3	0,0	0,0	5.620,5	12,8	165,8	0,0	Z	16,2
	Commercial	2.191,7	0,0	0,0	123,4	150,7	263,0	0,0	0,0	1.654,6
	Households	4.413,3	4,4	0,0	1.246,1	360,7	1.063,4	0,0	51,1	1.687,7
	Agriculture & Forestry	291,2	0,5	0,0	34,5	0,4	30,0	0,0	0,0	225,8
	Others	246,4	0,4	0,0	246,0	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0
Norway	Total	18.531,8	498,8	61,4	5.463,6	458,7	1.698,5	84,6	490,1	9.776,1
	Industry	6.042,2	498,8	61,4	854,6	290,7	257,0	76,4	47,1	3.956,1
	Transport	4.632,4	0,0	0,0	3.951,0	97,8	505,1	0,0	Z	78,5
	Commercial	2.836,6	0,0	0,0	264,7	49,2	30,6	8,3	333,2	2.150,6
	Households	4.097,1	0,0	0,0	65,2	7,7	501,3	0,0	109,3	3.413,6

	Agriculture & Forestry	307,9	0,0	0,0	134,5	13,4	0,0	0,0	0,5	159,5
	Others	615,6	0,0	0,0	193,5	0,0	404,4	0,0	0,0	17,7
France	Total	141.002,8	1.143,2	0,0	54.970,0	28.671,3	14.867,1	114,3	3.673,5	37.563,5
	Industry	26.538,9	1.065,1	0,0	2.463,7	9.745,1	1.638,6	3,6	1.472,4	10.150,5
	Transport	45.359,5	0,0	0,0	40.998,0	92,3	3.335,2	0,0	Z	934,1
	Commercial	23.831,5	40,9	0,0	2.750,5	7.285,7	803,8	110,7	861,0	11.978,9
	Households	40.649,2	35,2	0,0	5.342,4	11.339,6	8.910,8	0,0	1.331,8	13.689,3
	Agriculture & Forestry	3.801,0	2,1	0,0	2.670,0	207,7	170,4	0,0	8,2	742,7
	Others	822,6	0,0	0,0	745,4	1,0	8,3	0,0	0,0	68,0
Italy	Total	113.611,2	489,3	159,2	38.265,1	33.921,5	11.312,7	245,1	4.113,9	25.104,5
	Industry	24.925,7	489,3	159,2	1.954,3	8.870,6	392,7	245,1	2.873,9	9.940,6
	Transport	34.525,4	0,0	0,0	31.420,8	1.064,1	1.061,8	0,0	Z	978,8
	Commercial	18.242,2	0,0	0,0	546,4	6.590,2	2.758,6	0,0	308,1	8.038,9
	Households	32.898,6	0,0	0,0	2.087,5	17.260,6	7.014,4	0,0	904,9	5.631,2
	Agriculture & Forestry	2.695,8	0,0	0,0	2.010,0	136,0	50,8	0,0	10,5	488,5
	Others	323,5	0,0	0,0	246,2	0,0	34,4	0,0	16,4	26,6
Austria	Total	26.212,9	321,0	106,8	9.506,3	4.784,1	3.992,9	296,1	1.806,9	5.398,8
	Industry	8.052,3	302,2	106,8	457,4	2.699,2	1.362,3	296,1	279,2	2.549,2
	Transport	8.656,8	0,1	0,0	7.620,9	290,7	468,2	0,0	Z	277,0
	Commercial	2.386,6	0,0	0,0	156,3	324,0	179,1	0,0	738,8	988,4
	Households	6.594,5	18,4	0,0	1.045,2	1.448,8	1.817,6	0,0	778,0	1.486,5
	Agriculture & Forestry	520,8	0,4	0,0	226,5	21,3	163,7	0,0	11,0	97,8
	Others	2,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,1	0,0	0,0	0,0
Belgium	Total	32.888,0	484,9	171,6	13.268,6	9.432,9	1.930,1	140,2	415,7	7.043,9
	Industry	10.494,6	397,4	171,6	1.412,3	3.999,4	702,3	108,3	350,1	3.353,3
	Transport	8.856,4	0,0	0,0	8.197,4	37,5	478,5	0,0	Z	142,9
	Commercial	4.595,8	0,0	0,0	773,4	1.822,4	53,9	31,9	60,2	1.853,9
	Households	8.108,5	78,7	0,0	2.512,7	3.310,2	649,9	0,0	0,9	1.556,0
	Agriculture & Forestry	788,1	8,8	0,0	328,4	263,4	45,3	0,0	4,5	137,8
	Others	44,6	0,0	0,0	44,4	0,0	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0

4 FORECASTS OF POWER PRICES

4.1 Day-Ahead price in Germany

In the context of the BAMBOO project, N-SIDE has developed a price forecast for the electricity Day Ahead market for Germany.

4.1.1 Introduction

The *electricity day ahead market* is a two-sided auction, where participants submit bids of electrical energy in MWh per hourly slot of the next day at a certain minimal sell price or maximum buy price. In the clearing of this market, there are 24 prices determined, one for every hour.

For *industrial players*, consuming or/and producing a lot of electricity, it would be advantageous to know in advance what these prices will be towards the following 1 to 7 or 10 days. Indeed, if they possess some *time flexibility* in their order book or/and process scheduling, they can then schedule their processes that consume or produce electrical energy such that they minimize their total cost. Ideally a horizon of 1 to 10 days is needed for them. A price forecast would give them this information. Of course, a forecast does not give them certitude on these prices, but a *forecast* that includes a statistically known average error or/and confidence interval will be helpful.

This need is now being addressed by the forecast described here.

4.1.2 Required Output

The prices to be predicted are for the next day, for every hour or more generally for the next n days where n is 7 or 10, since that is the usual maximal horizon of the process planning in industrial plants.

4.1.3 Forecasting Principle

A forecast works by understanding and learning the relation between known inputs and known outputs from historical data of both these inputs and outputs and then assuming that that found relation / correlation remains valid in the future. With this assumption, and the resulting correlation model, we can then take known inputs and predict the unknown output(s).

There are quite some methods for modelling correlations. *Linear regression* would be the simplest one, but requires a linear relationship between inputs and outputs, which we a priori do not believe to exist.

Neural Networks and *Gradient Boost* technique are two techniques gaining popularity nowadays. We choose the latter since it gives us a more control parameters and also a means to extract the order of importance of input features in explaining the output feature.

4.1.3.1 Time Feature Inputs

As features defining the price, primarily, the price of any good or service in a liquid market is determined by the ratio of *supply and demand*. As initial features the production (generation) and consumption (load) of electrical energy are taken.

In electricity generation, there are different modes of generation: nuclear, solar, wind and fossil fuels (coal, gas, ...). Generally nuclear is used as base load, solar and wind are used whenever available and the fossil fuels are only used when necessary. This means that fossil fuels are determinants in the price formation. Because there are many fossil fuel types, this feature is not calculated as the sum of all forecasted fossil fuel capacities. Rather, this is calculated as the difference of the forecasts of load on the one hand and the forecasts of nuclear plus renewable energy production on the other hand. For this reason this is called ‘residual load’.

‘*time features*’ have been also included. For example, it is well known that there is a typical daily price pattern of energy in that there are two higher price peaks during most days, more or less coinciding with time where people get up and when people come home from work because they tend to consume more electricity during those hours. For this reason, the *hour of the day* is included as a feature.

The *day of the week*, can also make a difference on electrical energy consumption. For example, it differentiates weekend days from week days.

The *month of the year* is an indicator for the seasons: autumn, winter, spring, summer and will have some correlation with weather patterns, like temperature (influencing electrical consumption due to heating or cooling) as well as with the seasonal availability of production capacity from solar, wind and hydro.

All of the above ‘*time features*’ correspond to a certain time period. For each of these time features, they are not directly included as features, but rather a rotating normalized vector with the associated period is constructed and the sine and cosine projections of this vector are then used as basis. This gives as results smoothly changing functions, normalized between 1 and -1 for the relevant periods. The idea is that periodical components in the price variations could be composed out of combinations of these basic sine and cosine waves.

As for the German zone split from DEATLU to DELU and AT on 1 October 2018, the extra issue of bookkeeping in associating the right feature values with the right zones had to be faced. The prices to be trained on or predicted are considered as the ones for DEATLU before the zone split date and the one from DELU after the zone split date. So, depending on whether one is training or predicting for before across or after the zone split, the right data has to be taken into account. Essentially, single ‘continuous features’ are constructed across the zone split and the gradient boost method automatically can distinguish between a possible different feature interrelations before and after the zone split. It can do this since an extra Boolean feature, has been added which is False before the zone split data and a True after the zone split.

4.1.3.2 Neighbouring Countries Input Features

Next, it is assumed that price formation does not happen for a country in isolation, but that the price calculation results from a model that takes bids in consideration of a whole set of countries. These bids are not used directly, but are just taken as input features. For training reasons, historical data of these prices was taken and for an actual price forecast, a forecast for each of

these countries would be needed. So first the correlation of the German prices with the prices in the neighboring zones on historical data was checked. As neighboring zones, in ENTSOE notation, there are: Austria (AT), Belgium (BE), Switzerland (CH), Checkoslovakia (CZ), Denmark Zone 1 (DK1), Denmark Zone 2 (DK2), France (FR), The Netherlands (NL), Sweden Zone 4 (SE4), Poland (PL). After training and getting back the feature importance from that, it occurred that Belgium was feature number 2 or 3 in order of importance in explaining German prices, and that the other countries in the ordered list came at position 11 at best. This allows not to have to include these other countries and not have to arrange for or buy a forecast for these other countries.

4.1.3.3 Input Features that require a Forecast

Time features, as explained in the previous section are of course known in advance. The features used as input features for which a forecast is needed are the residual load components for Germany and the residual load components for Belgium.

For *German residual load*, for the load, solar and wind generation, at N-SIDE, the forecasts of these features are purchased with a week of horizon from Refinitiv. This data cannot be used for commercial purposes, but for research purposes, as in BAMBOO, its use is allowed. The horizon of availability is one week ahead.

For *Belgian residual load*, for load, solar, wind and nuclear, N-SIDE mines this from the ELIA website. ELIA is the Belgian TSO and makes this data available as part of their transparency platform obligations. The horizon of availability is one week ahead.

4.1.3.4 Possible Other Input Features

It is of course possible to do research into more input features to see if these would also help to further explain the German Day Ahead prices. Some ideas are to also use (forecasted) interzonal flows or gas prices. A satisfyingly low error between the predicted and true prices has been already achieved, as tested on the historical forecasted.

4.1.3.5 Time Shifting Input Features

Each of the input features mentioned in previous sections was shifted by a series of time deltas into the future. The time shifts used to shift all features are [-96h,-72h,-48h,-24h, 0h, 24h, 48h]. For example, a shift by 24 hours, takes values from yesterday and assumes them for tomorrow. So, a positive shift shifts values to later points in time and a negative shift to earlier points in time. So, with a negative shift one has to take care that, in simulation, values that are assumed to be not available yet are not 'shifted in from the future'.

4.1.4 Results

In previous sections, the needed output, the method of modelling correlation and used input features were presented. In this section, some results achieved with this setup are presented.

Historical data of all input and output features over a period of time have been used. This period is then split into a training and validation period. The model is trained over the first period, and from that a correlation model is obtained. This model is then tested for performance on the testing period. This procedure is repeated by shifting the validation versus test separation by 15 days at a time.

Table 4.1 shows the achieved MAE (Mean Absolute Error) over both train and test periods. It also shows the RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) also for both the train and test period. Naturally, during training, both error measures are lower for the data the model is being training on than for the new (test) data the model is not tuned to. The most relevant rows are the ones for the test, since that is the performance on unseen data that will be expected in practice as well.

Table 4.1: Key Forecast Error Measures for German Day Ahead Market Prices

Relation to zone split date	before (€/MWh)	across (€/MWh)	after (€/MWh)
MAE train	3,46	4,09	3,57
MAE test	6,57	6,97	5,86
RMSE train	6,19	6,92	5,37
RMSE test	9,18	9,59	7,60

Figure 4-1 shows the feature importance in explaining the German Day Ahead market prices for the case of taking training data only before the zone split. The input feature that most explains the output features, the German day-ahead market prices, is the residual load of Germany, called 'DEATLU_load_min_gen'. This represents the total German residual load, calculated as the difference of the forecasted load and forecasted solar, wind and nuclear production. So it refers to values of features that will be materializing, at least approximately, in 24 hours, just like the predicted value of prices that also refer to 'in 24 hours'. The next representative feature is called 'DEATLU_da_price_0H', where 'da' is misleading, since these are simply the prices of today. 'DEATLU_gen_real_wind' is feature 3, the generated wind of today. 'DEATLU_da_price_48H' are the prices of 48 hours ago. Next come some time features like 'time_weekF1_0H' and 'time_hourF1_0H', which are the sine functions of the normalized day of the week rotating vector and of the hour of the day respectively. Next comes 'DEATLU_load_real_quantity', which represents today's load quantities. There are many features which only have a very small correlation with the prices to predict. As for residual load of neighboring countries, the Belgian feature for this shows up as the first one, but it's only feature 11 in the importance list.

Figure 4-1: Feature importance in explaining German Day Ahead Market Prices only before the zone split

Figure 4-2 shows the feature importance in explaining the German Day Ahead market prices for the case of taking training data both before and after the zone split. Here, compared to the previous case of training and testing only on prices from before the zone split, the most important features explaining the prices to predict are interchanged. 'DEATLU_da_price_0h', so today's prices are explaining tomorrows prices better than the residual load of the old zone,

‘DEATLU_load_min_gen’. ‘DELU_load_min_gen_-24h’, which is residual load for the new zone DELU for tomorrow, comes in as third feature. The fourth feature is ‘DEATLU_da_price_48h’, which is actually the real prices of days ago. The real load of quantity of ‘DEATLU_load_real_quantity’, so of today is feature 5. Next features indicate that Austria has more influence on or at least more correlation with German prices here than Belgium.

Figure 4-2 Feature importance in explaining German Day Ahead Market Prices both before and after the zone split date

Figure 4-3 shows the feature importance in explaining the German Day Ahead market prices for the case of taking training data only from after the zone split. Here the main feature is ‘DELU_load_min_gen_-24h’ is feature 1 in explaining prices. This is the residual load as predicted for tomorrow. The day of the month, as ‘time_monthF2_0h’, is the secondary feature explaining prices and next come the Belgian residual load predicted for tomorrow as ‘BE_load_min_gen_-24h’.

Figure 4-3 Feature importance in explaining German Day Ahead Market Prices after the zone split date

4.1.5 Conclusion

N-SIDE built a forecaster to predict day ahead market prices for the next 7 to 10 days. Typical forecast errors are between 5.86 and 6.97 €/MWh. Via feature engineering, a set of most relevant input features have been selected. Some are related to neighboring countries and some require a forecast in their own right.

Industrial plants in Germany that inject electricity into or off-take electricity from the grid, can use this forecast to time-shift their electricity producing or consuming processes in their weekly planning so that they obtain a lower cost or a higher profit.

In a later phase of BAMBOO project, N-SIDE foresees to develop a similar forecast for Day-Ahead price in Spain, following the same methodology that was used for the German Day-Ahead forecast.

5 REQUIREMENTS FOR ENERGY FLEXIBILITY

This chapter provides an overview of the conclusions regarding the technological, legal and economic framework related to energy flexibility in the power markets of the analysed countries, with a particular focus on the balancing markets and the provision of ancillary services. Strategies to enhance energy flexibility in the near future are also presented. Main trends summarized in this chapter are based on the second and third section of the questionnaire. Information gathered by means of the questionnaire for each country is described in detail in ANNEX V - TECHNOLOGICAL, LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES.

5.1 Identification of trends and main differences

The most promising technology to enhance energy flexibility is energy storage, thanks to the recent advances in electrochemical storage. Digitalization, energy monitoring and the development of smart grids also play a central role in the transition of the power systems. The increased integration of renewable energy sources will indeed yield new challenges in terms of system stability, because of the volatile nature of wind and solar power. Demand side management strategies offer the opportunity of coping with this problem.

Balancing markets are not regulated in a uniform way in the analysed countries. Regulations are rather country-specific and neither thorough guidelines nor incentives for energy flexibility are available. New regulations are hence needed at country- and EU-level to enhance demand side management and balancing options.

In the analysed countries, different balancing mechanisms as well as implicit balancing options have been successfully introduced. Countries like Greece and Italy are still a step behind as concerns energy flexibility. Countries like Norway and France have instead high flexibility levels, thanks to hydro-power storage capacity in the case of Norway and the introduction of the capacity mechanism in France. Both countries will however face a transition: Norway strongly depends on its neighbouring countries and must adapt to their evolution; France needs to reduce the share of nuclear power, which will lead to changes in the local power system and a reduced security of supply.

Table 5.1 provides an overview of the provision of ancillary services, to highlight the main differences among the analysed countries.

Table 5.1: Ancillary services in the analysed countries [2] [3]

Country	Terminology ENTSO-E	Time ahead	Activation time	Minimum bid size	Participants
Germany	FCR	Day	30 seconds	1 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
	aFRR	Day	5 minutes	5 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
	mFRR	Day	15 minutes	5 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units

Spain	FCR	Mandatory for every generator connected to the transmission network			
	aFRR	Hour	N/A	10 MW for each unit	Large generators
	mFRR	On market-basis	15 minutes	10 MW	Generators, Pump Storage units
Turkey	FCR	N/A	30 seconds	N/A	Generators
	aFRR	N/A	15 minutes	N/A	Hydro power, thermal generators, gas-fired power plants
	mFRR	N/A	15 minutes	N/A	N/A
Greece	-	Balancing market not open Balancing settlement performed by the TSO			
Norway	FCR	Day	Seconds/minutes	1 MW	Generators
	aFRR	Day	N/A	5 - 10 MW	Generators
	mFRR	Day	15 minutes	1 MW	Generators, Load
France	FCR	Day	30 seconds	1 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
	aFRR	Day	15 minutes	1 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
	mFRR	Year	15 minutes	5 - 10 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
Italy	FCR	Currently not open to the market. Generators and conventional power plants with an installed capacity > 10 MW must provide FCR			
	aFRR	Currently not open to the market			
	mFRR	Day	15 minutes	1 MW	Participants must have hourly metering
Austria	FCR	Day	15 minutes	2 MW	Generators
	aFRR	Day	300 seconds	First bid: 1 MW Further bids: 5 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
	mFRR	Day	15 minutes	5 - 10 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
Belgium	FCR	Week	25 minutes	1 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units
	aFRR	Week	N/A	1 MW	Large generators > 25 MW
	mFRR	Month	N/A	1 MW	Generators, Load, Pump Storage units

6 CONCLUSIONS

In the course of the first project year, within task 2.5, research partners have performed a thorough analysis of selected energy markets, in order to get a general overview and identify the main challenges related to the implementation of energy flexibility measures.

A qualitative analysis of the studied energy markets has been presented in chapter 3, with the main focus on primary energy generation and demand and final energy consumption. Details related to the power and gas markets have been provided.

In chapter 4 models developed to forecast the German day-ahead price have been described and the main results have been shown. In future work, forecasts models for the Spanish market will be additionally developed. The models will serve as decision support for the demo-sites.

Technological and regulatory advances towards energy flexibility in the analysed countries have been discussed in chapter 5. The most promising technologies to enhance energy flexibility in the future are storage and conversion technologies, integration of renewable energy sources, implementation of smart grids and digitalization of the energy markets. New regulations and guidelines are required to increase the flexibility potential in the analysed countries.

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ANNEX I - QUESTIONNAIRE FOR QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENERGY MARKETS AND ASSESSMENT OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY REQUIREMENTS

The aim of this questionnaire is to collect relevant information related to energy markets for the assessment of energy flexibility requirements. Each RTO will be responsible for the assigned country as follows:

- TUBS - Germany, Norway, France
- IKL - Spain and Turkey (with RINA-C)
- CERTH - Greece
- RINA-C - Italy
- EI - Austria
- N-SIDE - Belgium

Please collect sources (papers, documents, databases) and complete the questionnaire using the gathered data. Always indicate the source. Text, graphs, figures and tables can be used to answer the questions. The questionnaire will be included in deliverable D2.7 *Definition of specifications and data requirements for electricity flexibility and energy market constraints*.

Country: please indicate the country you are analysing

ENERGY AND GAS MARKET

The aim of this first part is to gather general information and data, in order to get an overview of the energy and gas markets of the analysed country and understand its characteristics. You can add visual aids, like graphs and tables.

a. Generation and demand

- What is the country's primary energy mix?
- What is the total share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the energy mix? Please specify the type of RES and provide also the share of each RES on the total.
- Please indicate the installed power capacity by technology (nuclear, coal, gas, hydro, wind, solar, geothermal, etc.)
- What is the total electricity and gas demand at national level?
- Please indicate the energy consumption by sector
- What is the energy demand of the industrial sector? (electricity, fossil fuels, heat)
- What is the share of the industrial sector on the total energy consumption?
- Is there any storage capacity for electricity or gas? If yes, please indicate the capacity and the technology used.

b. Structure of power and gas market and main actors

- Who are the main actors of the power market? (Generators, suppliers, grid operators)
- Who are the main actors of the gas market? (e.g. for production, consumption, import, storage)
- Who are the decision makers for the power and gas market?
- Is the country importing/exporting electricity/gas? If yes who regulates the Import/Export?

c. Legal and economic framework

- What are the relevant energy policies at national level?
- How are energy prices regulated?
- Are there forecasting models for energy prices? If yes, please indicate sources
- What is the average energy price for industrial consumers?
- Are there any gas contracts at national level? With which countries?
- What is the average gas price for industrial consumers?

ENERGY FLEXIBILITY

The aim of this part is to resume the state of technology for energy flexibility and assess the energy flexibility potential in the analysed country, according to technological advances as well as to restrictions and specific regulations.

a. Technological framework

- Please indicate the technological advances related to energy flexibility
- What are the most common technical solutions used in the industrial sector to valorise the energy flexibility potential?
- Please indicate the time horizon of energy flexibility strategies:
 - Time delay (how long in advance should a flexibility decision be made)
 - Duration (for how long should the flexibility valorisation actions last)
- What are the main challenges for energy flexibility in the analysed country?
- What are the most common generation and storage options at factory level?

b. Legal and economic framework

- Please include specific regulations on provision of ancillary services [**explicit flexibility**], including:
 - Type of reserve (FCR, aFRR, mFRR, RR...)
 - Time aspects (reservation timing, activation delay, activation duration)
 - Economical aspects for reservation & activation (clearing or bid price)
 - Potential benefits from flexibility valorisation
- Please include specific regulations on potential valorisation of **implicit flexibility** (leveraging beneficial market prices fluctuations on DA, intraday, imbalance...):
 - Legal framework
 - Access to the concerned fluctuating markets from industrial consumers
 - Time horizon for valorisation on these markets

- Potential benefits from flexibility valorisation
- Are there any restrictions on energy flexibility (financial, political)?
- Are there guidelines for implementation of flexibility measures?
- Are there any financial incentives to implement flexibility strategies in the industrial sector?

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGY

The aim of this part is to evaluate the implementation potential of single flexibility strategies.

a. Assess implementation potential

- What are the main influencing factors that have to be taken into account? (e.g. regulations, society, state of technology)
- Is the strategy feasible within the national electrical system?
- What additional laws/regulations would be needed to enforce the strategy and increase its implementation potential?

b. Economic assessment

- Please include a rough estimation of costs related to the selected flexibility strategy (planning, design, implementation, management)

c. Environmental and social impact

- How do you estimate the social acceptance for the strategy?
- What could be the environmental impact of the selected strategy (e.g. raw materials, CO₂-emissions, etc.)

d. Advantages/disadvantages of selected measure (e.g. interaction with the local market, lower energy prices, etc.)

ANNEX II – NATIONAL ENERGY MARKET

GERMANY

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

As shown in Figure 0-1, in 2018 the primary energy consumption was 12963 PJ, 3,5% lower than the previous year, due to milder weather conditions, increased energy efficiency and higher energy prices [4]. Coal consumption fell by 11,2%, mineral oil by 5% and natural gas by 1,6%. Mineral oil has currently the highest share in the primary energy mix (34%).

Figure 0-1: Primary energy consumption in Germany [5]

Table 0.1 shows the break-down of the primary energy consumption by energy source for the year 2018. The share of renewables was 13,8%. A detailed structure of the renewable energy production is given in Figure 0-2.

Table 0.1: Structure of primary energy consumption in Germany (2018) [6]

Energy source	Primary energy demand [PJ]	Share on total [%]
Mineral oil	4.452	34,0
Natural gas	3.071	23,4
Hard coal	1.428	10,9
Brown coal	1.476	11,3
Nuclear power	829	6,3

Renewables	1804	13,8
Others	46	0,4

Figure 0-2: Renewable energy structure in Germany (2018) [6]

Figure 0-3: Primary energy generation in Germany (2018) [5]

In 2018 Germany produced 3.886 PJ of the demanded primary energy [5]. The break-down by energy source is shown in Figure 0-3.

FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

In 2018 the final energy consumption by the end-consumer was 8.997 PJ, as shown in Figure 0-4: 15% of the total energy consumption was required for industrial purposes, 30% for transport, 25% for households and 15% for trade, commerce and other services.

Figure 0-4: Final energy consumption in Germany (2018) [6]

Figure 0-5: Final energy consumption in the industrial sector in Germany (2018) [5]

Focusing on the industrial sector, the final energy consumption was 2651 PJ in 2018. Figure 0-5 and Table 0.2 provide an overview of the industrial energy consumption by energy carriers and by applications.

Table 0.2: Final energy consumption by application in the industrial sector (Germany, 2018) [5]

Application / Energy carrier	Energy consumption [PJ]
Heating	148,6
Oil	11,5
Gas	89,2
Electricity	2
District heating	17,3
Coal	9,0
Renewables	18,4
Other	1,2
Hot water	17,1
Other process heat	1.787,1
Oil	86
Gas	821
Electricity	140,1
District heating	150,1
Coal	420,9
Renewables	94,5
Other	74,4
Cooling (electricity)	17,9
Other process cooling (electricity)	36,8
Mechanical energy	577,1
Oil	2,3
Gas	24,2
Electricity	550,6
ICT (electricity)	32,8
Lighting (electricity)	33,4

ELECTRICITY

Germany has the highest installed power plant capacity in Europe and is also the biggest consumer. Table 0.3 shows the installed generation capacity by power plant in Germany up to November 2019.

Table 0.3: Installed power generation capacity in Germany [7]

Power plant	Installed capacity [MW]
Biomass	7.752
Hydro	5.281
Wind offshore	6.393
Wind onshore	52.792
Photovoltaics	45.299
Other renewable	487
Nuclear	9.516
Fossil brown coal	21.205
Fossil hard coal	25.293
Fossil gas	31.664
Hydro pumped storage	9.422
Other conventional	7.277

226 billion kWh were generated from renewable energy sources, reaching a share of 37.8% on the gross electricity consumption [8].

Germany profits from its central geographical position in Europe, exporting/importing power to/from neighbouring countries, mainly France, Switzerland, Poland, Denmark, Austria, Check Republic, the Netherlands, Sweden and Luxembourg [9]. Germany exported 82.7 billion kWh of electricity in 2018 and imported 31.5 billion kWh [8].

The power storage capacity was 10 GW in 2010. The main storage technologies are pumped storage power plants, batteries and solar power storage.

NATURAL GAS

Germany is the 9th biggest gas consumer worldwide, after the USA, Russia, China, Iran, Japan, Canada, Saudi-Arabia and Mexico. The primary natural gas consumption was equal to 3.071 PJ in 2018, 1,6% lower due to a decreased use for heating purposes [4].

The natural gas supply from other countries was 4.656 PJ in 2018. The main suppliers of natural gas are Russia (55,3 billion m³ in 2018), Norway and the Netherlands (see Figure 0-6).

Figure 0-6: Natural gas supplier in Germany (2017) [10]

Figure 0-7: Gas consumption in Germany by consumers (2018) [10]

Figure 0-7 shows the final gas consumption divided by consumers. Despite the installation of new gas heating systems, the gas consumption by private households decreased by 3,2% due to better weather conditions. In the industrial sector there was also a decline of 0,1%.

Gas reserves in Germany are mostly located in Lower Saxony (up to 98,6%) and in Saxony Anhalt (1,1%). In 2018 0,05 billion m³ were stored in the mentioned reserves [10].

SPAIN

The Spanish energy sector has been experiencing changes. After the rise of its economy in the 1990's, including energy, Spain suffered a recession in 2008 that plunged the country into cutbacks, restrictive policies and a total lack of investments. The economic recession has restrained both consumption -mainly dominated by hydrocarbons- and production of primary energy, that has included renewable energy in recent years as one of the main sources, followed by nuclear energy. The total energy demand has barely evolved from 30.278 tons of oil equivalent in 2009 to 33.623 in 2014, which has posed new challenges, especially for the domestic market, free from 1997 but limited to few operators that control electricity, oil and gas. After that, in 2015, the GDP recovered reaching 3,2 %.

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

Spain is still highly dependent from oil to satisfy its energy demands, so a greater diversification of local sources of energy is one of the energy challenges. In addition, as a member of the European Union, Spain is increasingly pushed to meet emissions targets, incorporate renewable energies to the energy mix, and assure energy efficiency by 2020.

Figure 0-8: Primary energy mix Spain in 2016

The primary energy mix production [11] and consumption [12] in are shown in Figure 0-8, in which it is mainly seen the great dependence in oil imports.

ELECTRICITY

In terms of electricity, on one hand, the electricity power installed capacity [13] in 2018 is as follows in Figure 0-9. It is seen that 46,7 % of the total installed power is renewable energy in which 22,6% is wind power, 16,4% is hydro power, 4,5% is photovoltaic solar power, 2,2% is thermal solar power and other renewables comprises the 1%. Moreover, in Figure 0-10 the evolution of renewable installed power in the Spanish electrical system is represented.

On the other hand, the electricity power generated [13] in 2018 is illustrated in Figure 0-9. The nuclear power is still an important source as about 20% of the electricity consumed is produced by nuclear power plants when compared to the share in the total installed capacity. The renewable generation has also a relevant role in terms of production in the total mix, above one third of the generated power.

Figure 0-9: Electricity power installed in Spain

Figure 0-10: Evolution of renewable installed power in Spain

Figure 0-11: The electricity power generated in Spain

Overall, as it is stated in the report of the Spanish system operator [14], the total electricity demand at national level in 2018 was 253.493 GWh. In 2018, Exports decreased by 23,1% to 10.499 GWh, as well as imports that decreased to 21.590 GWh (-5.4%). Therefore, the net balance is again an importer, with a value of 11.090 GWh, 20,9% higher than the previous year 2017.

NATURAL GAS

In terms of natural gas, the consumption was 31 bcm¹ in 2018, from which the 99,66% is imported. The main gas contracts are with Algeria, Norway, Qatar, Nigeria, France and Trinidad and Tobago as seen below in Figure 0-12. The global energy commodities can be consulted in reference [15].

¹ Billion cubic meters

Figure 0-12: The origin of the natural gas in Spain [16]

The final energy consumption by sectors in Spain consists of 23,9% industrial sector and 40% transport activities. Regarding to the industrial electricity consumption, which represents about 30% of the total demand, it registered a growth of 2,0% in 2017 (2,2% after having factored for the effects of seasonal and working patterns).

Within the energy storage field, the storage capacity is one of the best options for improving flexibility. Currently, in the Spanish peninsula, only electricity-pumped-storage hydroelectric power stations are operating, corresponding to 4.749 MW. The electric system operator, Red Eléctrica de España, is researching other possibilities such as:

- Large-scale (GW): reversible hydroelectric (pumping), thermal storage.
- Network storage (MW): batteries, capacitors and superconductors, flywheels.
- At the end user level (kW): batteries, superconductors, flywheels.

The only underground storage facilities for natural gas are in Yela (2000 million m³), Serrablo (2100 million m³) and Gaviota (2681 million m³).

TURKEY

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

For Turkey, energy production is 36.47 Mtoe, net energy import is 124.6 Mtoe, while export is 7.9 Mtoe. Total primary energy supply is calculated as 146.7 Mtoe. These data show the growing economy and growing demand to energy of Turkey. As expressed in 2018 Budget Presentation, one of the targets of Turkey is being one of the first 10 economies in the world [17]. This target brings the increasing demand to energy supply.

Figure 0-13: Turkey Primary energy mix [1]

With the economic growth, the need for energy increased dramatically and urged Turkey to diversify its energy policies. As indigenous resources could not meet the growing energy demand, the external energy dependency of Turkey increased gradually. Today nearly 70% of its energy demand is provided by imported energy.

Different energy sources and import/export position of Turkey are explained below. The data shows the domination of fossil fuels and highly dependence on imported energy sources. In 2016, the greatest crude oil import is done from Iraq with 36,9%. Political stability of Iraq country is crucial for Turkey in terms of energy supply security. For oil product, Russia is the greatest provider with 24,9 Mt. Similarly, natural gas amount of export to Greece with 3,2 TWh, electricity is imported mostly from Bulgaria with 7.1 TWh.

Table 0.4: Different energy sources and import/export positions of Turkey [18]

Fuel		Quantity
Crude oil	Import	25,1 Mt
	Export	0,6 Mt
Oil products	Import	24,9 Mt
	Export	5,8 Mt
Natural gas	Import	46,3 bcm
	Export	0,7 bcm
Coal	Import	36,2 Mt
	Export	0,1 Mt
Electricity	Import	7,1 TWh
	Export	3,2 TWh

As per the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources ("Ministry") data, according to energy sources, the number of existing plants in Turkey is as follows [19]:

- 613 hydraulic;
- 40 coal;
- 186 wind;
- 33 geothermal;
- 288 natural gas;
- 1.773 solar; and
- 165 other power plants.

FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

The final energy consumption is 100,4 Mtoe, considering that the energy consumption in the industry sector is 32,1 Mtoe, in the transport sector is 28,3 Mtoe and in other sectors is 40 Mtoe. In Table 0.5 the specific consumptions in each macro category (Industry, transport and other) are reported [1].

Table 0.5: Final energy consumption [1]

Industry Sector	Amount (Mtoe)	Transport Sector	Amount (Mtoe)	Other Sectors	Amount (Mtoe)
Iron & steel	4,5	Rail	0,2	Commercial & public services	13,5
Chemical & petrochemical	2,7	Road	26,12	Households	22,16
Non-ferrous metals	0,92	Domestic aviation	1,27	Agriculture & forestry	4,1
Non-metallic minerals	9.6	Domestic navigation	0.3	Fishing	0.144
Transport equipment	0.163	Pipeline transport	0.39	Not elsewhere specified (other)	0.0
Machinery	0.93	Not elsewhere specified (transport)	0.0011		
Mining & quarrying	0.49				
Food, beverages & tobacco	2.5				
Paper, pulp & printing	0.72				
Wood & wood products	0.37				
Construction	0.903				
Textile & leather	3.1				
Not elsewhere specified (industry)	5.1				

ELECTRICITY

Gross electricity consumption in Turkey increased from 175 TWh in 2006 to 305 TWh in 2018 and to satisfy the increasing needs of the country, the current capacity is expected to reach 110 GW by 2023 through further investments to be commissioned by the private sector as underlined in the 11th Development Plan for 2019-2023 [20].

Peak load, which was 27.5 GW in 2006, rose to just shy of 44 GW by the end of 2016. While the exact level of growth in the coming decade is the subject of some debate, there is broad consensus that demand growth will continue. Decoupling demand growth from economic growth will be a key challenge and can help contain cost for residential and industrial consumers, increasing Turkey's competitiveness globally. In Turkey, electricity demand peaks in the summer. As electricity is still widely used for heating in winter, the winter peak is only about 5% lower than the summer peak. Demand is more and more centralized in urban areas in the mid-western and western part of the country, and this trend is likely to continue.

The development of peak demand and gross electricity consumption between 2006 and 2016 are presented in Figure 0-14.

Figure 0-14: Peak demand and gross electricity consumption, 2006-2016 [20]

Installed power capacity outpaced demand growth, increasing from 32 GW in 2002 to 88.5 GW at the end of 2018 [20].

As most of the growth in the past decade was due to investment in large hydro and gas-fired power plants, Turkey's power generation park is dominated by hydro (26,7 GW) and natural gas (25,5 GW) plants, followed by lignite (9,3 GW) and hard coal (8,5 GW). All lignite and 1 GW of hard-coal fired power plants are fuelled by local resources, while most hard-coal power plants operate on imported fuel (7,5 GW). When it comes to output, thermal generation features more prominently due to higher full load hours, especially in coal and lignite plants. The generation mix in 2016 was dominated by natural gas power plants (33%) and lignite and coal (31%). Hydro contributed 25% to overall supply. The power generation sources are illustrated in Figure 0-15 below.

Figure 0-15: Breakdown of total installed capacity (left) and electricity generation (right), 2016 [20].

Turkey’s total electricity import and export amounts in 2016 were 6.4 TWh and 1.4 TWh, respectively. That is, net import is 5 TWh, which corresponded to 1.8% of total consumption (278.4 TWh) in 2016. Turkey is largely self-reliant in terms of electricity supply, while exchange with neighboring countries does balance supply and demand locally [21].

Similarly, the buildings and services had a share of 47.4% in end-use electricity consumption in 2000, and reached a share of 49.9% in 2015 exceeding that of the industry. In the same period, the total increase in demand was 135%, with an average annual increase of 9% in demand.

Figure 0-16: Changes in Electricity Consumption in Buildings and Services Sector by Year [21]

The industry with a share of 26% in GDP 2015 has continued in recent years to grow and drive the economic growth in our country as in many other countries. With the industry accounting for 32.4%

of the end-use energy consumption and 47.6% of the net electricity in 2015, the Turkish economy is more “energy-intensive” compared to developed countries [22].

NATURAL GAS

As of the end of 2018, the natural gas consumption was 48,9 billion m³.

According to the studies on the natural gas supply-demand balances, there is no problem concerning the meeting of the annual natural gas demand. However, during the winter months, when demand is high, the fall of temperatures to levels below seasonal norms, and as a result the rise of consumption to maximum levels, and any faults in the source countries or countries en-route during the same period, can lead to periodic imbalances between supply and demand. Within this framework, the Silivri, Kuzey Marmara and Değirmenköy Natural Gas Storage Facility, which has a working gas capacity of 2.84 bcm, was taken over by BOTAŞ in order to be used effectively for ensuring seasonal supply-demand balance and supply security. Within the scope of Kuzey Marmara Natural Gas Storage Expansion Project, developed by the reason of increasing the capacity of related facility, it's planned to increase total storage capacity to 4.6 bcm and withdrawal capacity to 75 mcm/day. [23]

The following table contains information regarding the amount of exported and imported natural gas (year 2018) [18]

Table 0.6: Import/Export of natural gas in Turkey (2018) [19]

Fuel	Quantity
Import	46.3 bcm
Export	0.7 bcm

The import ratio of Turkey's natural gas, which is one of its most important sources of electricity production, is 99%. In natural gas, which seriously affects the dependency ratio of energy imports, 80 trillion cubic metres (43%) of total reserves are located in the Middle East; 54 trillion cubic metres (29%) of total reserves are located in the countries of Russia and the Commonwealth of Independent States; and 30 trillion cubic metres (16%) of total reserves are located in Africa/Asia-Pacific countries [19].

Residential and commercial is the third largest energy consuming sector in Turkey with an 18.6% share. The domestic sector in Turkey has shown the greatest natural gas demand growth among other sectors for the last three years and this trend will continue in the following years. By the end of 2016, 43.1 million end users had access to natural gas which is 53% of the total population. The number of eligible subscribers as of the end of 2016 was 12,5 million and it is expected that by 2020 this will reach 16,7 million. This sector accounted for 25% of total gas consumption (46 bcm) in 2016 and it is expected that the share of gas in the residential sector will reach 29% by 2025. The demand for natural gas in the residential sector has been growing modestly, with average annual growth of 1-2 bcm/year. In 2014 the consumption in this sector was 9.3 bcm, and rose to 11 bcm/year in 2015, growth of 1.7 bcm/year. In 2016 it grew by a further 1.7 bcm to 12.7 bcm, 24.7% of total natural gas consumption, up from 22.98% in 2015.

The industrial sector has the lowest gas usage among the sectors described in this document with 504,161 independent consumers consuming 14 bcm of natural gas in 2016. Coal is the main energy source with a 57% market share and natural gas is the second largest with 30%. Cement, iron and steel are the main sub-sectors for energy consumption in industry. The share of gas in the fuel mix in industry rose from 25.4% in 2014 (12.375 bcm) to 29.1% (13.965 bcm) in 2015 and to 30% (14 bcm) in 2016. In previous years, demand in this sector was growing by, on average, approximately 1 bcm year-on-year with the revival of the economy and subsequent GDP growth after the economic crisis in 2009. However, in 2012 GDP growth fell to 2.3% due to political tensions in Turkey's immediate neighbourhood, and gas consumption growth in the industrial sector fell by about 15%. Industrial demand growth is more or less correlated with GDP but at a lower rate because of energy saving. Almost all industry has access to natural gas.

The most gas-intense sphere of the industrial sector is the production and manufacturing sector that includes chemical and petrochemical products production (2.6 bcm in 2015), the textile, leather and clothing industry (0.856 bcm in 2015), transport vehicle production (0.150 bcm in 2015), organized industrial zones (3.268 bcm in 2015). This sector is likely to contribute most to gas demand growth as GDP growth and an increase of FDI in the Turkish economy will contribute new gas consumers to the industrial sector, potentially easing sluggish growth. In 2015 natural gas demand growth in this sector was only 4% and in 2016 natural gas demand stagnated, due mainly to slowed GDP and FDI growth, despite the connection of 30,000 new eligible consumers to the grid [24].

RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

Figure 0-17 below reports the total share of RES in the energy mix in Turkey. [1]

Figure 0-17: Total share of RES in the energy mix [1]

Turkey has a substantial amount of renewable energy potential, and utilization of this potential has been on the rise over the last decade. As of end-2018, hydro, wind, and solar resources constitute the vast majority of the country's renewable energy resources, accounting respectively for 28.29 GW, 7.01 GW, and 5.07 GW of the total installed capacity.

Turkey has excellent solar, wind and hydro resources. While there is a considerable variation of wind resources across the country, wind speeds above 7 m/s can be found in almost all regions of

Turkey. Particularly attractive conditions are present in the Aegean, Marmara, and Eastern Mediterranean regions; these are also the areas where most wind power projects have been realized and are planned by developers. The Ministry of Natural Resources and Energy estimates the potential for attractive wind power generation with wind speeds above 7.5 m/s, measured at 50 m above ground, to be at 48 GW. Taking into account the rapid technology and cost development, which allows wind power to be generated economically also at less ideal wind speeds below 7.5 m/s, the actual economic potential may actually be substantially higher than this figure.

Installed capacity of the wind power plant has increased from less than 1 GW in 2009 to almost 6 GW by the end of 2016. Between 2013 and 2015, annual new installations were close to 1 GW, and, in 2016, for the first time, well above 1 GW.

Despite these very attractive solar resource conditions and considerable investor interest, until very recently, very few PV installations had been implemented in Turkey. Total installed capacity of PV was only about 300 MW by the end of 2015. However, recently, installations have picked up considerably: In 2016, more than 650 MW were installed, followed by 550 MW additional capacity in the first half of 2017, with the Solar association GÜNDER estimating new installations to exceed 1 GW for the first time in this year. To the largest extent, these are 1 MW installations, as investments up to this size do not require a lengthy licensing process.

Figure 0-18: Development of total installed wind power capacity in Turkey [20]

As part of the ongoing efforts to promote localization, the Turkish government has made it a priority to increase the share of renewables to 30 percent, with geothermal installed capacity to be 3 GW by 2023, as well as to have 16 GW of installed capacity in solar and wind each by 2027. In order to create a favourable investment environment to strengthen renewables' position in the market beyond the 2020s, the government has designed various investment models such as unlicensed (small-scale), licensed (medium-scale), and YEKA (large-scale) models, which address different sorts of investors and are encouraged by lucrative incentive instruments [20].

The main requirement to reach these targets is to support renewable generation in the electricity market. In order to achieve this, significant reforms have been undertaken since 2005, when the first law on renewable energy was enacted, as shown in Figure 0-19.

Figure 0-19: Turkish Electricity Market Reforms and Laws, 2001-2017

Investments in renewable energy technologies remained limited between 2005 and 2010, as the regulatory environment and in particular feed-in tariff levels were considered not attractive enough by investors. In order to encourage investment, the government of Turkey decided to amend the existing Law No. 5346 in 2010, which provided for more attractive feed in tariffs. Under the Law No. 6094, technology specific feed-in tariffs (FiT) were introduced. Accordingly, FiTs have been provided to renewable energy facilities that were commissioned before 31 December 2020 for a period of ten years with the tariff levels (quoted in US dollars to avoid exchange rate risk) shown in Table 0.7. Additionally, local content bonuses are offered to encourage local value creation.

Table 0.7: Feed in tariffs after Law 6094 in 2011

Renewable Energy type	Feed-in Tariff (USD ct/kWh)	Domestic production support (USD ct/kWh)	Total (USD ct/kWh)
Hydro	7.3	2.3	9.6
Wind	7.3	3.7	11
Geothermal	10.5	6.7	18.209
Biomass	13.3	9.2	22.5
Solar	13.3	5.6	18.9

In 2013, EMRA announced the renewal of renewable energy support mechanism (YEKDEM). The retail companies assigned by EMRA have been required to purchase the produced electricity from manufacturers which are subject to this mechanism. Renewable energy investors may select annually in October, whether they will operate under the day-ahead market regime in the following year (which also yields balancing requirements) or prefer direct sale according to the FiT plan (instead of trading on the market, and free of balancing requirements). With high market prices in the past, most wind and hydro investors had originally opted to operate under the market regime; however, since 2015 (Figure 0-20), when wholesale prices dropped below FiT levels, they have moved almost entirely under the FiT regime.

Figure 0-20: Average wholesale market prices and the FiT, 2009-2017

According to Turkey's market regulation, power plants that have an installed capacity greater than 1 MW are required to obtain a generation license from the EMRA. Generation facilities with a maximum installed capacity of 1 MW can benefit from the feed-in tariffs without having to undergo the enduring licensing procedure. The auction regime for grid connection, in particular, has become a major bottleneck for larger solar investments. This is due to the fact that bidders, initially focused on securing grid connection entitlements because of the limited number of capacity, then delayed implementation as they waited for further PV system price decreases which would make their offers economically viable. As a consequence, almost all solar investment up until now fell under this "unlicensed regime". Supplementary incentives set for all renewable energy generation investment include an 85% discount in the treasury and lease fees for 10 years after commissioning; 99% discount for the licensing fee and the annual license fee for first 8 years of operation; grid connection priority and VAT / custom taxes exemptions. Although the support scheme has increased investment in renewable energy generation in Turkey, there are still major barriers that cut investments short. These relate to the short period of feed in tariffs of 10 years (in many countries, FiT cover 15-20 years) and uncertainty on the period post-2020. The fact that renewable energy generators, who participate in the YEKDEM, do not have balancing responsibility, increases overall system cost and weakens the cost argument in favor of Renewables in the discussion.

In 2017, a new investment model for renewables, REDA mechanism, was introduced in order to bring costs down for Renewables generation and incentivize local manufacturing of renewable generation assets in Turkey. Public and government-owned land that is categorized as highly suitable for the renewable energy generation may be defined as REDA. Within REDA, a large generation capacity of either wind or solar (1 GW in the first two tenders) is assigned to a single private consortium through tenders. Beyond the size of the investment, which shall allow for economies of scale, investors benefit from additional exemptions:

- Renewable energy investments shall be exempt from customs tariff and value added tax for their investment costs (imported solar panels are not within the incentive scope);
- Lower license fees (only 10% of licensing fees) and annual license fee exemption for the first eight years of the operations;

- Network connection priorities;
- Simplified project preparation and land acquisition procedures;
- For the first ten years of the investment and operation periods, an 85% discount is applied to the cost of right of easement, usage right and rent.

REDA tenders in 2017 are in line with Turkey's domestic and renewable energy strategy. The wind tender resulted in a highly competitive electricity price of USD 3.48 ct/kWh. This compares to USD 10.3 ct/kWh under the YEKDEM regime and is 40% below 2017 spot market price.

The 2017 tender for the 1 GW Karapınar solar PV REDA, won with USD 6.99 ct/kWh. Within the scope of the Karapınar solar power project, a plant with a production capacity of a minimum of 500 MW of photovoltaic modules per year will be built in Turkey and research and development (R&D) activities will be carried out for the next 10 years [21].

STORAGE CAPACITY

Policy mechanisms that consider different requirements of flexibility options as well as a market design that allows competition to arrive at the cost-optimum system flexibility are needed.

The role of battery storage is being discussed for several years in Turkey. At the end of January 2019, a draft legislation on energy storage was released for public consultation. In addition, energy companies are looking into options for investing in battery storage technologies and related business models to operate them. While the issue is attracting much interest, there is a need to better understand in which areas should investments be directed, to what extent should storage capacity be built, which technology should be employed for which purpose, and when does battery storage makes the most economic sense.

The results of the study contained in the report from SHURA show that a total distributed battery storage capacity of 600 MW would be an important source of flexibility to integrate 30% share of wind and solar energy into the system. However, such capacity may not be necessarily needed to integrate a wind and solar share of 20%, because TEİAŞ's existing grid planning would be sufficient for wind and solar integration at this level. This is an outcome of the benefits that follow a nonlinear function of solar and wind share: as the share of renewable energy increases, the benefits from these options also increase compared to the case without flexibility [25].

Additionally, one of the other results of this study is that the pumped-hydro storage capacity can be one of the most attractive flexibility options with installed capacities offering a long lifetime of operation. Considering a long-term vision with increasing levels of wind and solar energy over time, pumped-hydro storage can be a strategically beneficial decision for the power system. Such long-term vision would also allow improving the cost effectiveness of the system in the long run for grid integration of renewables. Moreover, Battery storage systems can provide flexibility, but the initial capital costs of most technologies are still too high compared to the benefits they bring to the system. Thus, the required storage capacity should be planned in conjunction with large shares of wind and solar capacity to minimise additional system costs and to bring the most benefits where needed. One possible way forward for the deployment of these systems is to start with smaller scale installations, provide niche services and complement other flexibility options [25].

GREECE

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

The economy of Greece faced a period of severe recession after the financial crisis in 2008, where GDP at current prices had a significant decline. During the period of economic crisis, Greek economy lost approximately 25% of its GDP. However, since 2018, the Greek economy has returned to positive GDP growth. This is due to regulatory reforms, taxation fittings and increase in the investments. Moreover, as a result of the extended financial crisis, Greece has achieved the national target of 20% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions in respect 1990 levels. In contrast to the rest of the European Union, Greek households faced a gradual increase in the utility bills, which led to energy poverty, which means that there was a significant inability in the Greek households to meet their energy utilities obligations. The last years Greece has introduced numerous stages towards the liberalization of the electricity, with HEnEX (Hellenic Energy Exchange) being a major reform. Moreover, HEnEX aims to enhance competition, to guarantee transparency, liquidity and to achieve the integration with other European electricity markets. The Greek electricity market operated via LAGIE (Greek Operator of Electricity Market). This organization is responsible to undertake the operation and the monitoring of the Day-Ahead market and Intra-Day coupling. Other responsibilities of the aforementioned organization include clearing, settlement and reporting of transactions to RAE (Greek Regulatory Authority for Energy) and ACER (Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators). Since the early 2017, LAGIE and ATHEX (Athens Stock Exchange) are collaborating towards the establishment of the Hellenic Energy Exchange, which aims to substitute the system of mandatory pool until late 2019.

Figure 0-21: Distribution of Energy Production in Greece

Table 0.8 provides an overview of the energy consumption per sector, in 2017.

Table 0.8: Total Energy Consumption by Sector in Greece [1]

Energy Consumption (ktoe)							
Type	Total	Solid Fossil Fuels	Oil & petroleum products	Natural gas	Renewables & biofuels	Heat	Electricity
Sectors	16,054.2	195.7	8,329.2	1,180.1	1,657.7	51.1	4,640.5
Industry sector	3,096.3	190.4	1,058.7	655.5	135.4	0.0	1,056.2
Iron & steel	128.5	0.0	14.5	27.9	0.0	0.0	86.1
Chemical & petrochemical	121.1	0.0	21.2	42.4	0.0	0.0	57.5
Non-ferrous metals	869.8	153.6	7.8	315.3	0.0	0.0	393.0
Non-metallic minerals	680.5	36.8	537.0	16.4	3.3	0.0	87.0
Transport equipment	18.3	0.0	13.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.6
Machinery	49.9	0.0	10.5	2.8	0.0	0.0	36.5
Mining & quarrying	90.9	0.0	85.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.4
Food, beverages & tobacco	423.6	0.0	161.3	60.3	112.8	0.0	89.2
Paper, pulp & printing	48.4	0.0	15.8	11.5	3.0	0.0	18.2
Wood & wood products	27.1	0.0	2.4	4.3	14.8	0.0	5.7
Construction	165.2	0.0	110.4	12.1	0.0	0.0	42.7
Textile & leather	38.0	0.0	7.2	11.1	0.0	0.0	19.8
Not elsewhere specified (industry)	434.9	0.0	71.3	151.4	1.6	0.0	210.6
Transport sector	5,815.3	0.0	5,620.5	12.8	165.8	Z	16.2
Rail	55.5	0.0	39.7	Z	1.7	Z	14.1
Road	4,992.1	Z	4,813.7	12.8	163.6	Z	2.1
Domestic aviation	195.2	Z	195.2	Z	0.0	Z	Z
Domestic navigation	570.6	0.0	570.1	Z	0.4	Z	Z
Pipeline transport	0.0	Z	0.0	0.0	0.0	Z	0.0
Not elsewhere specified (transport)	2.0	0.0	1.9	0.0	0.1	Z	0.0

Other sectors	7,142.6	5.3	1,650.0	511.7	1,356.5	51.1	3,568.1
Commercial & public services	2,191.7	0.0	123.4	150.7	263.0	0.0	1,654.6
Households	4,413.3	4.4	1,246.1	360.7	1,063.4	51.1	1,687.7
Agriculture & forestry	291.2	0.5	34.5	0.4	30.0	0.0	225.8
Fishing	12.4	0.0	12.3	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0
Not elsewhere specified (other)	234.0	0.4	233.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Based on the data of the Greek Ministry of Environment & Energy [26], the energy consumption of the industrial sector, in 2017, was 3.096,3 ktoe. The distribution of the energy consumption of the industrial sector is illustrated on the following figure.

Figure 0-22: Distribution of Energy Consumption of Greek Industrial Sector

According to these data, the industrial sector’s energy consumption is approximately 19,29% of the country’s total energy consumption.

ELECTRICITY

Due to economic crisis, in Greece, the gross electricity generation remained stable from 2005 to 2018. Greek power generation is highly dependent on fossil fuels which were responsible for the production of more than 70% of electricity in the last decades. The last years a significant reduction of fossil fuels is achieved due to introduction of RES, mainly solar and wind. Based on the most recent data provided by the Greek Operator of Electricity Market (July 2019) [27]. Greece’s produced energy in 2018 was 50.91TWh, whereas 68.28% is attributed to fossil fuels and the 31.72% to RES.

The installed power capacity for each of the aforementioned energy sources are based on the data of Greek Operator of Electricity Market (January, 2019) [28]. The following data concern the installed power capacity connected to the country’s electrical grid [29].

1. Fossil Fuels

- Lignite: 4,337 MW
- Oil: 1,845.3MW
- Gas: 4,482.3 MW (3,999.8 MW Gas-fired Combined Cycle, 147.8 MW Open Cycle Gas Turbine, 334 MW large-scale Gas-fired CHP)

2. Renewables

- Solar energy: 2,492 MW
- Wind energy: 2,579 MW
- Hydroelectric energy: 3,409.7 MW (239 MW small hydros, 3,170.7 large hydros)
- Biomass: 82 MW

The total electricity demand, according to the Independent Power Transmission Operator, concerning the period between January 2018 - December 2018, was 51.462 TWh [30]. The demand for Natural Gas in 2017 recorded was 4.9 bcm (4,46 Mtoe (HHV)), out of which approximately seventy percent (70%) came from the power generation sector [31]. According to the latest data of the Greek Ministry of Environment & Energy [5].

NORWAY

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

Norway has the second highest share of renewable energy sources in Europe after Sweden. Thanks to hydropower sources, the fossil fuel consumption is lower compared to other European countries. The share of hydropower is indeed 6% on the total energy production and 40% on the total primary energy supply [32]. Figure 0-23 shows the primary energy supply by energy source in Norway.

Figure 0-23: Total primary energy supply by source in Norway [ktoe] [32]

FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Figure 0-24: Total final energy consumption by sector in Norway [ktoe] [32]

The largest energy consumer is the industrial sector, with around 40% of the final consumption (see Figure 0-24) [33].

Focusing on the industrial sector, the most consumed energy source is electricity, followed by oil, natural gas, coal, biofuels and waste and least heat (see Figure 0-25).

Figure 0-25: Total final energy consumption by energy source in the industrial sector in Norway [33]

ELECTRICITY

Norway has 1,000 hydropower storage reservoirs, providing 50% of the storage capacity in Europe (86.5 TWh). The production capacity is therefore highly flexible. Electricity is the most consumed energy source in the industrial, residential and commercial sectors. Figure 0-26 and Figure 0-27 show the final electricity consumption by sectors and the imports/exports of electricity, respectively.

Figure 0-26: Electricity final consumption by sector in Norway [ktoe] [32]

Figure 0-27: Electricity imports/exports in Norway [ktoe] [32]

NATURAL GAS

Since 2017 heating installation based on fossil fuels is forbidden in Norway. The mayor consumer is the industrial sector (see Figure 0-28).

Norway is one of the main oil and gas producers and exporters worldwide [33]. In 2018 Norway produced nearly 5,000 PJ of gas. Most of the produced natural gas is exported to the UK and continental Europe through the North gas pipeline network [34]. Figure 0-29 shows the imports/exports in Norway up to 2018.

Figure 0-28: Natural gas final consumption by sector in Norway [TJ] [32]

Figure 0-29: Natural gas imports/exports in Norway [TJ] [32]

FRANCE

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

Figure 0-30 shows the evolution of the primary energy supply by energy source in France.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

Figure 0-30: Total primary energy supply by source in France [ktoe] [32]

ELECTRICITY

Electricity production was equal to 549 TWh in 2018, 3.7% higher than in 2017, mainly due to higher renewable and nuclear generation. The consumption remained stable with 474 TWh.

Figure 0-32 provides an overview of the main trends in the electricity market, related to generation, consumption and cross-border exchanges.

France is the biggest exporter of electricity in Europe, exchanging electricity with Great Britain, Switzerland, Italy and Spain. The exchange balance in 2018 was equal to 60.2 TWh (see Figure 0-33) [35].

As shown in Figure 0-31, the gross consumption was 478 TWh in 2018, slightly lower than 2017 (-0,8%).

Figure 0-31: Gross energy consumption in France [35]

Figure 0-32: Overview of the French electricity market in 2018 [35]

Figure 0-33: Imports/Exports of electricity from France to neighboring countries [35]

The residential sector was the largest consumer (35,7%), followed by the business sector (26,6%); heavy industry had a share of 16,9% on the final consumption, SMEs/SMI 11% and professionals 9,9% (see Figure 0-34).

Figure 0-34: Final electricity consumption by sector [35]

Figure 0-35: Electricity generation by technology (2018) [35]

The net electricity generation was 548,6 TWh in 2018. As depicted in Figure 0-35, wind generation had a share of 5,1% in the energy mix, while solar 1,9%. Nuclear had the highest share, with 71,7%.

Figure 0-36 shows the installed power capacity in France.

Figure 0-36: Installed capacity in France up to April 2019 [MW] [36]

NATURAL GAS

As shown in Figure 0-37 the mayor consumer of natural gas is the industrial sector, with 34,2%, followed by the residential sector (32,1%) [37].

Figure 0-37: Gas demand by sector in France (2016) [37]

France imports gas from Qatar, Nigeria, Algeria, Russia, Netherlands and Norway (main supplier representing 36% of imports). France has 7 main interconnection points with European gas networks. The gas exchange capacity with neighbouring countries reached 2.285 GW in 2015 [38].

France owns several natural gas storages, essential as it does not produce gas itself. Gas is injected into storage during summer and extracted in winter. The withdrawal capacity from storage is around 2.700 GWh per day at full stocks [38].

ITALY

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

The total energy demand in 2018 was equal to 172,3 million tons of oil equivalent (Mtoe), increasing by 1,6% compared to the previous year, as reported in the national energy balance 2018 (Table 0.9).

Table 0.9: Italian energy balance in 2018

Italian energy balance (Mtoe)						
	Solid fuel	Gas	Oil	RES	Electrical energy	Total
Production	0,252	4,462	4,684	34,021		43,419
Import	9,479	55,588	81,494	1,572	10,378	158,511
Export	0,252	0,320	29,526	0,272	0,719	31,089
Stock change	0,241	0,216	-1,920	-0,004		-1,467
Gross inland consumption	9,238	59,514	58,572	35,325	9,659	172,308

The national energy production was 43,4 Mtoe, increasing by 10,9% respect to 2017, while the net energy import decreased to 127,4 Mtoe (-1,6%).

The energy mix composition is the following: 34,5% gas, 5,4% solid fuel, 20,5% RES, 34% oil, 5,6% electric energy, as can be seen in Figure 0-38. It changed respect to 2017: the gas contribution was decreased by 1,8% as well as the solid fuels one was decreased by 0,7%, while renewable sources and imported electricity was increased by 1,8% and 0,7%, respectively. Oil remains substantially unchanged with a coverage percentage of 34% [39].

Figure 0-38: Italian primary energy mix 2018

FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

The total energy consumed by end-users was 127,3 Mtoe, increasing by 1,5% on previous year. This increase concerned all sectors: transport (3,2%), bunkers (2,7%), agriculture (1,3%), civil uses (0,7%), non-energetic use (0,5%) and industry (0,4%).

Among the sources of energy, renewables (11,2%), oil (2,1%) and electricity (0,6%) increased (0,6%); while solid fuels (1,2%) and gas (0,6%) decreased.

The contribution of each energy source is different between various sectors. The use of gas in the industrial sector increased (1%) while it decreased in non-energetic uses (-5,8%), in agriculture (-2,9%), in civil uses (-1,5%) and in transports (-0,5%).

The consumption of petroleum products intensified in transports (2,9%), in bunkers (2,7%), in non-energetic uses (1,4%) as well as in agriculture (1,2%), on the contrary decreased in industry (-2,9%) and in civil uses (-1,8%) [39].

Table 0.10: Final energy consumption by sector 2018 [39]

Final energy consumption [Mtoe]						
	Solid fuel	Gas	Oil	RES	El,energy	Total
Industry	2,106	12,638	2,878	0,125	9,484	27,231
Transport		0,858	37,028	1,267	0,992	40,145
Civil use		23,552	2,793	7,523	14,25	48,118
Agriculture		0,132	2,306	0,041	0,525	3,004
Non energetic use	0,053	0,616	5,021			5,69
Bunker			3,154			3,154
	2,159	37,795	53,180	8,956	25,251	127,341

ELECTRICITY

The electrical energy demand 2018, equal to 321,4 TWh (+0,3% compared to 2017), was covered for 86,3% by national production (277,5 TWh: -1,9% compared to 2017) and for the remaining portion by net imports from abroad (43,9TWh: + 16,3% on 2017).

Gross national electricity production, equal to 289 TWh, was covered for 60,3% by thermoelectric production (9,8% from fossil fuel, 5,6% from oil and 44,9% from gas), for 17,1% by hydroelectric production, which recorded a significant increase due to higher rainfall, for 13,9% by electricity production from wind and solar sources and the remaining 8.7% from geothermal and bioenergy sources.

The major contribution to the national electricity production is still represented by traditional thermoelectric plants, although recorded a significant decline respect to 2017. Figure 0-39 shows in details the structure of the electricity supply in 2018 [39].

Figure 0-39: Structure of electricity supply 2018

In terms of capacity, the gross power capacity installed in Italy amounted to 118,1 GW, whose 54,2% is represented by thermoelectric plant (64GW), 19,4% by hydroelectric power plant (22,9 GW) and 26,4% by renewable power plants.

Electricity consumption, up 0,5% compared to 2017, amounted to 303,4 TWh. A more detailed analysis highlighted a positive trend change in all sectors: agriculture (1,8%), industry (+0,6%), tertiary (+0,6%) and domestic (+0,1%).

Figure 0-40 shows the electricity consumption by sector. The industrial sector is still the more relevant, consuming 41,6% of national consumption, following by tertiary sector (34,8%), domestic (21,6%) and agriculture (2%).

Figure 0-40: Electricity consumption 2018 by sector

Focusing on industrial sector, the total consumption was equal to 29.932 GWh. Consumptions recorded by type of industry are reported in Table 0.11. It is noted that the year 2018 ended with an increase of consumptions in chemical industry (+ 4,4%), metallurgical (+ 1,2%) and building materials industries (+ 2,9%); while consumptions of the remaining were down [39].

Table 0.11: Electricity consumption by industrial sector in 2018 [39]

Electricity consumption by industrial sector [GWh]			
	2017	2018	YoY [%]
Mechanic industry	3,097	3,096	0,0%
Steel industry	13,808	13,967	1,2%
Chemical industry	3,597	3,753	4,4%
Building materials	2,679	2,756	2,9%
Refining and cooking	667	672	0,8%
Means of transport	1,394	1,293	-7,3%
Non-ferrous metals	1,529	1,503	-1,7%
Other	2,935	2,892	-1,4%
Total	29,705	29,932	0,8%

NATURAL GAS

The natural gas demand 2018 was equal to 72,7 billion cubic meters (bcm), decreasing by 3,3% compared to the previous year mainly due to a decrease in consumption in the thermoelectric sector. The coverage of this requirement was guaranteed by imports for 93% and by national production for 7%. The national production was 5,4 bcm, including biomethane production (29 bcm).

Imports of natural gas via pipeline, amounting 59 bcm and 87% of total imports, decreased by 1,9 bcm, in particular imports from Algeria (17,1 billion cubic meters, -9,5%), from Russia (29,7 bcm, -1,6%), and from Libya (4,5 bcm, -3,8%); on the other hand, those from Northern Europe (Holland and Norway) showed an increase by 7,1% (7,8 bcm).

The contribution of LNG was approximately 8,7 bcm, 13% of total imports, with an increase by 6.3% compared to the previous year.

The industrial sector consumed 15,4 bcm of natural gas (+0,1%) corresponding to 21% of total consumption. The table below (Table 0.12) reports the direct consumptions of gas in each area within industrial sector. The glass and ceramic, chemical and steelmaking sectors showed an increase in consumption by 5,5%, 1,0% and 0,9% respectively [39].

Table 0.12: Gas consumption by industrial sector interconnected directly to Snam Rete Gas [39]

Gas consumption by industrial sector [MSm ³]						
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	YoY [%]
Glass and ceramic	1,963	1,942	1,979	2,117	2,233	5,5%
Chemical industry	2,078	1,813	2,043	2,116	2,138	1,0%
Paper industry	1,593	1,634	1,656	1,654	1,643	-0,6%
Steel industry	1,562	1,396	1,532	1,626	1,640	0,9%
Other	5,166	5,122	5,257	5,586	5,362	-4,0%
Total	12,361	11,908	12,467	13,099	13,017	-0,6%

RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

In the last decade, there has been an increasing diffusion of renewable energy sources in all sectors. In 2018, the RES confirmed their crucial role in the national energy system for a sustainable development of the country.

Regarding the electric sector, the preliminary estimations provided by Terna-GSE indicate a substantially increase of electrical energy production from RES, depending only on increase of hydropower. RES account for 34,5% of total electricity mix (approximately 115 TWh) with the following sources distribution: 43% hydropower, 15% wind, 20% solar, 5% geothermal, 17% bioenergy, as reported in Figure 0-41 [39].

Figure 0-41: Gross electrical energy production from renewable energy sources in Italy (2018)

Figure 0-42: Thermal energy from RES in Italy (2018)

Concerning the thermal energy sector, the preliminary estimations indicate a thermal energy consumption from RES equal to 10,9 Mtoe, according to the RES distribution reported in Figure 0-42. Bioenergy is the most important renewable source for thermal energy production, in

particular biomass is used for heating in the residential sector. Figure 0-42 shows the RES contribution for the thermal energy production [39].

STORAGE CAPACITY

The overall installed storage capacity in Italy is more than 7,6 GW [40] , which is mainly represented by technological solutions of mechanical type, and even more particularly by pumped hydropower storage [41].

Pumped hydropower storage is actually the most widespread technology in Italy for large-scale applications. Their function is to pump the water during the night with a lower cost of electrical energy and to provide power during the day in peak hours.

However, the electrochemical storage is one of the most rapidly growing market segments, although operational installed power capacity is still only around 82 MW.

The most relevant examples of electrochemical storage systems in Italy are represented by Terna plants. At today, 35 MW NAS storage for Energy Intensive applications and 13 MW of different technologies, lithium (9,2 MW, 5 types) ZEBRA (3,4 MW, 2 types) and flow (0,85 MW, 2 types) for Power Intensive applications have been installed by Terna [42].

Regarding the gas market, Snam is the largest storage operator in Italy, through its subsidiary company Stogit, which manages nine storage facilities for a total storage capacity of 16,9 bcm, as reported in Figure 0-43 [43].

The gas storage system allows to compensate for the different requirements for gas supply and consumption. Storage also ensures that quantities of strategic gas are available to compensate for any interruption or reduction in non-EU supply or crises in the gas system.

Figure 0-43: Natural gas storage capacities of Snam's plants from 2014 to 2018 [43]

AUSTRIA

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

The Austrian primary energy production was 499,6 PJ in 2018 (see Table 0.13), whereby 81,7% of the energy mix was produced through renewables. In the same year, Austria imported 1327,3 PJ, exported 411,9 PJ, and stored 7,3 PJ [44]. The main energy carriers of the imported energy were gas (34,1%) and oil (46,8%). In 2018, 430 PJ of oil and 196 PJ of gas were consumed. The electricity consumption was 227 PJ [45].

Table 0.13: Structure of primary energy production in Austria [44]

Energy source	Primary energy production [PJ]	Share of total production [%]
Biogenic energies	226,8	45,4
Heat (solar, heat pumps, geothermal)	19,1	3,8
Hydro power	135,5	27,1
Wind	21,7	4,3
Photovoltaic	5,2	1,0
Combustible waste	26,1	5,2
Gas	36,0	7,2
Coal	0,0	0,0
Oil	29,2	5,9
Nuclear	0,0	0,0

The structure of the primary energy production through renewables is provided in Figure 0-44. Austria produces around one third out of hydro power, and around 41% out of solid biogenic resources like wood chips and briquettes, waste wood from saw mills or biogenic resources from households [44].

Figure 0-44: Production structure of renewables in Austria [44]

FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Figure 0-45 provides the Austrian final energy consumption of 2018 divided into economic sectors. The total final energy consumption was 1122,5 PJ, whereby 29,1% was consumed by the industry, 35,8% by the transportation sector, and the remaining part from the agriculture, private households, and services [44].

Figure 0-45: Structure of the Austrian final energy consumption by economic sectors [44]

Figure 0-46: Final energy consumption of Austrian industry by energy carriers [46]

The industry sector consumed 326,4 PJ in 2018. The main carriers were gas with 35% and electric power with 32%, which account together for around two thirds of the final energy consumption. The share of renewables was 17% [46].

ELECTRICITY

Table 0.14 lists the net installed power capacities of Austria grouped in the different types of power production plants [47]. The total installed capacity in the Austrian control area is 22.021 MW. Besides, Austria has gas storage capacities of 8,2 billion m³ [44].

Table 0.14: Installed net capacity in Austria [47]

Type of plant	Installed capacity [MW]
Gas	4.468
Coal	598
Hydro pumped storage	3.401
Hydro run-of-river and poundage	5.605
Hydro water reservoir	2.985
Oil	178
Solar	1.193
Waste	150
Wind	2.887
Geothermal	1
Other renewables	42
Other	23

BELGIUM

PRIMARY ENERGY GENERATION AND DEMAND

Primary energy consumption in Belgium in 2016 was 657 TWh, mainly based on fossil fuels namely oil (39,9%) and natural gas (25,3%), as shown in Figure 0-47. It is followed by nuclear energy which represents 20,1% of the primary energy consumption. The part of renewable energy has been steeply increasing over the past years, multiplied by 4 between 2007 and 2016 (Figure 0-48), yet it still only represents in total 8,1% of the primary energy consumption in 2016.

Renewable energy production in 2016 amounted to 14,17 TWh which was mainly from solar (21,8%) and wind power (38,4%). There was a substantial increase compared to 2007, when wind and solar production were almost negligible. Biomass energy has been relatively stable over the years, and amounts to 31,1% of the total renewable energy production.

ELECTRICITY AND NATURAL GAS

On the aspect of installed capacity for electricity production, Belgium has around 14 GW of generation units including 6 GW of nuclear power plants (42,1%), as shown in Figure 0-49 (2017 values). Natural gas-based power plants represent 3,7 GW of installed capacity (26,6%). On the side of renewable power plants, most of the capacity comes from offshore wind turbines in the North Sea, with a total of 878 MW in 2017 (6.2%).

Total power consumption in Belgium has seen a slight decrease over the 2007 to 2017 period, from 86,6 TWh to 77,4 TWh yearly electricity consumption (Figure 0-50). Natural gas consumption has been relatively stable despite year-to-year fluctuations and amounts to 182,2 TWh in 2017.

Figure 0-47: Primary energy consumption in Belgium in 2016 [48]

Figure 0-48: Renewable energy sources in Belgium in 2016 [48]

Figure 0-49: Installed generation capacity by plant type in Belgium in 2017 [49]

Power plant type	Installed capacity	
	MW	%
Nuclear plants	5 919	42.1
CCGT and gas turbines	3 736	26.6
Conventional power plants	315	2.2
Cogeneration	807	5.7
Incinerators	247	1.8
Diesel engines	5	0.0
Turbojets	195	1.4
Hydro (excluding pumping power plants)	86	0.6
Pumping power plants	1 308	9.3
Onshore wind farms	187	1.3
Offshore wind farms	878	6.2
Biomass	385	2.7
Total	14 069	100.0

Figure 0-50: Total power consumption in Belgium 2007-2017 [49]

	Power (GWh)	Peak capacity (MW)
2007	86 619	14 033
2008	87 760	13 431
2009	81 575	13 513
2010	86 501	13 845
2011	83 350	13 201
2012	81 717	13 369
2013	80 534	13 446
2014	77 161	12 736
2015	77 184	12 634
2016	77 295	12 734
2017	77 414	12 867

Figure 0-51: Natural gas consumption in Belgium in TWh by user segment 2003-2017 [49]

User segment	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Distribution	83.1	88.3	87.2	88.3	82.6	88.5	87.6	101.2	82.5	91.9	97.9	79.6	88.1	93.0	91.9
Industry (direct customers)	50.7	49.3	50.2	50.2	50.0	47.8	39.2	46.9	47.0	45.5	42.8	41.1	43.1	41.8	43.9
Electricity generation (centralised facilities)	51.1	49.7	52.5	51.9	56.7	54.6	67.3	67.1	53.9	48.1	42.5	39.7	44.6	44.7	46.3
Total	184.9	187.3	189.9	190.4	189.3	190.9	194.2	215.3	183.4	185.6	183.2	160.4	175.8	179.4	182.2

ENERGY USE IN THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR

The share of the industrial sector in the final energy consumption in Belgium was stable around 26% over the 2007 to 2016 period, amounting to 122 TWh in 2017 (Figure 0-53). The dominant industry in terms of energy use is the chemical and petrochemical sector, with a share of 38,3% of the industrial energy consumption (46,8 TWh in 2017). It is followed by food, beverages & tobacco, non-metallic minerals, iron & steel, and pulp & paper, which represent together 44,5% of the industrial energy demand (54,3 TWh).

Figure 0-52: Final energy consumption per sector in Belgium in 2016 [48]

The share of the industrial sector on the total energy consumption is 26%

Figure 0-53: Final energy consumption from the Industry sector in Belgium in 2017 [50]

Final consumption > Industry sector

Indicator Level 1	Indicator Level 2	Product group	Terajoule								All products
			Solid fossil fuels	Manufactured gases	Oil and petroleum products	Natural gas	Renewables and biofuels	Non-renewable waste	Heat	Electricity	
Industry sector	Iron and steel		559,745	7,183,760	522,780	20,861,460	.	66,700	.	16,053,120	45,247,565
	Chemical and petrochemical		298,942	.	49,238,140	55,516,410	327,760	121,800	11,749,600	51,076,800	168,329,452
	Non-ferrous metals		.	.	40,260	5,556,510	.	1,000	.	7,450,920	13,048,690
	Non-metallic minerals		12,898,656	.	1,735,520	22,099,050	5,160,400	3,750,600	.	10,093,320	55,737,546
	Transport equipment		.	.	183,180	1,938,960	.	.	2,300	3,334,320	5,458,760
	Machinery		.	.	670,740	5,087,430	79,850	500	.	6,368,760	12,207,280
	Mining and quarrying		.	.	.	432,000	.	.	.	1,628,280	2,060,280
	Food, beverages and tobacco		1,155,274	.	313,960	36,968,670	3,364,870	.	1,691,600	20,257,920	63,752,294
	Paper, pulp and printing		975,433	.	388,860	5,904,270	12,669,400	565,800	1,193,800	9,299,160	30,996,723
	Wood and wood products		.	.	.	993,780	7,588,600	.	.	1,315,440	9,897,820
	Construction		.	.	3,060,180	2,640,330	.	.	.	2,959,200	8,659,710
	Textile and leather		.	.	29,820	3,760,110	10,500	26,900	21,000	3,740,760	7,589,090
	Non-specified industry		750,757	.	2,948,800	5,686,470	63,700	.	.	6,816,600	16,266,327
Industry sector			16,638,807	7,183,760	59,132,240	167,445,450	29,265,080	4,533,300	14,658,300	140,394,600	439,251,537

Source: Statbel (Directorate-general Statistics - Statistics Belgium)

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ENERGY STORAGE

Electricity storage capacity in Belgium mainly relies on the 2 pumped-storage hydroelectric power stations:

- Coo-Trois-Ponts: maximum power output of 1,2 GW power during 6 hours (total energy storage 7200 GWh [51])
- Platte Taille: maximum power output of 140 MW [52]

Natural gas storage capacity is summarized in Figure 0-54, and comprises one underground storage in Loenhout, one tank storage in Dudzele and LNG storage capacity in Zeebrugge.

Figure 0-54: Natural gas storage capacity in Belgium [53]

Natural Gas Storage Capacity (H-gas, June 2009)			
Location	Type	Working capacity (mcm) ¹	Peak output (mcm/day) ²
Loenhout	Underground	625	12
Dudzele	Tank	59	12
Zeebrugge	LNG	228	
Total		912	24

(1) Working gas capacity= total gas storage minus cushion gas

(2) Peak output= the maximum rate at which gas can withdrawn from storage

ENERGY IMPORTS

Belgium heavily relies on imports for its primary energy supply, due to the absence of local fossil fuels and nuclear resources. In 2016, total energy imports were 568 TWh, representing 86,4% of the 657 TWh primary energy supply (Figure 0-55). Main imports are oil (62%) and natural gas (29,4%). Belgium is also a net importer of electricity, with a total import that fluctuates and was 6.18 TWh in 2016, 8% of the 77,3 TWh total power consumption that year.

Figure 0-55: Net imports of energy per energy source in Belgium in 2016 [48]

Figure 0-56: Natural gas imports by Source in Belgium, 1973-2008 [53]

ANNEX III – STRUCTURE OF ENERGY MARKETS AND MAIN ACTORS

GERMANY

The Federal Network Agency and the regulatory authorities for the regions are responsible for regulating the electricity and gas supply grids.

The traditional tasks of the Federal Network Agency in the energy market are to define the conditions for electricity and gas suppliers to use the grid to supply their customers and to regulate the fees that may be charged for this. The Federal Network Agency pays particular attention to ensuring that network operators can master the major tasks of energy system transformation without placing an excessive financial burden on consumers [54].

There are over 80 generators, producing over 100 MW electricity; the main generators are RWE, E.ON, Vattenfall, EnBW, Uniper and Innogy. Over 900 companies are operating the power grid. The transmission system is operated by four TSOs: 50Hertz, Amprion, TenneT, TransnetBW.

Figure 0-57: Power transmission system operators in Germany [55]

Figure 0-58: Gas market areas in Germany [56]

The power grids required for the distribution and transport of electricity is a natural monopoly, as competition can hardly be created. The transport and distribution of electricity are therefore regulated by the state. Therefore, the state is an additional player on the electricity market. State-regulated transmission and distribution grid fees currently account for around a quarter of electricity prices. Additional government charges, taxes and levies - including concession fees,

EEG levies, grid fees, offshore liability levies and others - contribute to the fact that almost 70% of the electricity price consists of statutory levies [57].

The German gas market is characterized by a large number of privately organized operators in the areas of network operators, storage operations and gas trading. There are currently two market areas in Germany (NetConnect Germany - NCG - and Gaspool), each with their own coordinator who ensures that access to the gas grid and market activities are both carried out in an efficient way. 16 gas transmission system operators are currently operating in Germany. Other players are the distribution system operators, storage facility operators and commercial enterprises. The EU internal market package for the liberalization of the market for electricity and natural gas, most recently amended by the Third Internal Energy Market Package, redefines the areas of activity of market players. To promote competition, the operators of gas supply networks and storage facilities are separated from natural gas trading activities [8].

SPAIN

The electricity sector has changed substantially in the last two decades due to the implementation of European directives creating (and therefore liberalising) a single internal electricity market. Since liberalisation, electricity activities are primarily carried out by private entities on the basis of free competition. The Spanish electricity market is structured in different activities such as generation, supply, regulation, transmission, distribution, and economic and technical management of the system. Spanish regulations distinguish between regulated (transmission, distribution, and economic and technical management of the system) and non-regulated activities (generation, supply, load managing services). These activities are performed by different actors involved in the electricity sector.

The main generators, who have the major market share, are Iberdrola, Endesa, EON, EDP and Naturgy. The most known suppliers are Iberdrola, Endesa, EON, EDP, Naturgy, Holaluz, Lucera, CEPSA, Repsol, etc. All the suppliers integrated in the Spanish retail activities are listed in [58]. The system operator is Red Eléctrica de España (REE), who is also the transmission company. The market operator is OMIE, who is in charge of the economic transactions in the Iberian market (Spain and Portugal). The main distribution companies are Iberdrola, Endesa, Viesgo, Naturgy (Fenosa) and Hidrocantábrico, each of them having the ownership of the distribution network in a part of the whole country. The National Commission on Markets and Competition, abbreviated as CNMC, is a Spanish competition regulator responsible for enforcing competition law. It was established by virtue of the Spanish Competition Act.

Regarding the gas sector the main actors are the operator (Enagás), the suppliers (such as Naturgy, Repsol, Shell, BP and Engie), and the responsible of the transmission and storage which is also performed by Enagás. All the distributors, suppliers and direct gas consumers can sell or buy gas through these products based on their commitments and needs. Also, and according to the balance network code, the transport network manager will participate in the organized gas market to buy or sell the gas necessary to perform its balance actions and ensure the viability of the programs.

TURKEY

ELECTRICITY MARKET

The Electricity Market Law (EML) of 2001 established a wholesale electricity market in Turkey. The EML envisioned a market design based on bilateral contracts as the best way to achieve competition in the Turkey's power industry (EMRA, 2003). After the enactment of EML, the EMRA was established, and previously vertically integrated segments of generation and transmission were unbundled.

The electricity market is based on a power exchange (PX) market operated by Energy Exchange Istanbul (EXIST). The main function of this market is to identify the most economically efficient dispatch of available power generation.

The transmission grid is the backbone of the power system, connecting the country's regions and enabling long-distance power transport to the main demand centers in the West. Turkey's transmission grid consists of both 400 kV and 154 kV systems. The state-owned TEİAŞ is the sole owner of transmission assets in Turkey and is responsible for new investments in the transmission infrastructure as well as system operation. Since it is a monopoly, the company is regulated by EMRA using a cost-based revenue cap approach. The electric power system of Turkey has been synchronized with ENTSO-E via 400 kV transmission lines in Bulgaria (two lines) and Greece (one line) since September 2010. The N-1 secure thermal capacity of the lines are above 1,500 MW, though at present transition is limited to 550/450 MW (import/export) due to inter-area oscillation phenomena and limitations in the Bulgarian network. The main advantages of the interconnection with the ENTSO-E system include frequency stability and sharing of spinning reserves among ENTSO-E countries. To the East, power exchange occurs only with Georgia, via a controllable, high-voltage direct current (HVDC) link [21].

GAS MARKET

According to Natural Gas Market Law No. 4646 which forms the legal framework of Turkey's natural gas market, import, distribution, storage, wholesale, export, transmission, compressed natural gas (CNG) distribution and transmission are defined as market activities for which obtaining a license is compulsory. Natural gas exploration and production (E&P) activities are performed within the framework of Turkish Petroleum Law No. 6491 and E&P and operation licenses as given by the General Directorate of Petroleum Affairs. Although production is not regarded as a market activity in the Law, production companies can sell the natural gas that they produced to wholesale companies, import companies, export companies, distribution companies, CNG selling companies at well head, CNG transmission and distribution companies and eligible consumers provided that they obtain wholesale license from the Authority. Moreover, production companies can export the natural gas they produced provided that they obtain export license [59].

Figure 0-59: Natural gas market value chain [60]

A BOTAS is the Turkey’s pipeline operator and gas procurement company owned by the Turkish Treasury and managed by the energy ministry. BOTAS imported 85% of Turkey’s natural gas needs last year. The company is party to Turkey’s long term pipeline gas import contracts with Russia, Azerbaijan and Iran as well as long term liquified natural gas (LNG) import contracts with Nigeria and Algeria. The company also imports spot LNG from up to 13 countries including US and Qatar. Last year BOTAS pipeline gas imports were 39 billion m³, LNG imports were 11.3 billion m³. Around 5 billion m³ of LNG imports were from the spot market according to energy markets regulator. BOTAS imported 444 mln m³ of US LNG last year versus 884 mln m³ in Jan-July 2019. The company operates national oil and gas pipeline and onshore and offshore LNG infrastructure. International subsidiaries include BOTAS International Limited, Turkish Petroleum International Inc (TPIC). The company also owns 30% of TANAP gas pipeline through local subsidiary [61].

GREECE

The following table 0.15 presents the main actors of the Greek power market

Table 0.15: Main Energy Market Actors in Greece

Energy Market Actors	
Energy producers	
1.	Public Power Corporation S.A. (PPC)
2.	Heron S.A.
3.	Elpedison S.A.
4.	Mytilinaios Group
Active Electricity Suppliers	
1.	PPC S.A.

2.	ELPEDISON ENERGY S.A.
3.	WATT & VOLT S.A.
4.	HERON THERMOELECTRIC S.A.
5.	GREEK ENVIRONMENTAL & ENERGY NETWORK S.A.
6.	VOLTERRA S.A.
7.	PROTERGIA THERMOELECTRIC AGIOS NIKOLAOS S.A.
8.	NRG TRADING HOUSE S.A.
9.	NOVAERA ENERGY S.A.
10.	GREEK POST OFFICES S.A.
11.	ECONOMIC GROWTH S.A.
12.	VI.ENER. S.A.
13.	INTERBETON S.A.
14.	OTE REAL ESTATE S.A.
15.	GREENSTEEL CEDALION COMMODITIES S.A.
16.	KEN S.A.
17.	VOLTON S.A.
18.	EPA THESSALONIKIS-THESSALIAS S.A.
19.	EPA ATTIKIS S.A.

The certified Transmission System Operator (TSO) is ADMIE S.A., whereas the distribution system operator is DEDDIE S.A. In 2017 RAE has proceeded with a power market restructuring plan which is essentially the implementation of “the Target Model” in the Greek wholesale electricity market, based on the European Regulations, Directives and Guidelines. For this purpose, RAE in cooperation with the TSO (ADMIE S.A.) and the wholesale market operator (LAGIE S.A.) made their proposals and recommendations to the Ministry of Energy and Environment for the necessary legislative reforms and amendments in line to the European electricity target model. The electricity target model aims at the establishment of the following 4 markets: the establishment of a day-ahead market, an intra-day market, a balancing services market and a forward market. In this regard, Law 4425/2016 was issued for the transposition of the European electricity target model to the legislative framework of the national wholesale market in September 2016. For the implementation of Law 4425/2016, RAE after a consultation with ADMIE S.A. and LAGIE S.A., and a public consultation, issued Decision (Ref no. 67/2017) about the Regulator’s Guidelines to the national TSO and to the Market Operator for the development of the necessary network codes for the operation of these four (4) markets. Based on the timeline set by RAE’s Guidelines/Decision, the completion of the network codes is expected to take place, in 2018. RAE is closely following and monitoring this procedure. The responsible entity for the development and completion of the network codes for: a) the intra-day market, b) the day-ahead market and c) the forward market, is the domestic market operator LAGIE S.A. The responsible entity for the development and completion of the network code for the electricity flows’ balancing is the national TSO, ADMIE S.A [29].

NORWAY

The main actors of the Norwegian energy market are [33]

- The Ministry of Petroleum and Energy (MPE), managing the petroleum resources as well as the water and hydropower resources
- The Norwegian Energy Regulatory Authority, the national regulator for the electricity and downstream gas market
- The Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE), an independent legal entity, subordinate to the MPE, responsible for the energy and water resources and regulating the electricity sector
- The Norwegian Petroleum Directorate (NPD), also subordinate to MPE, managing petroleum resources
- The Ministry of Climate and Environment, responsible for the environmental policies
- Gassco AS, a state-owned company, operating the gas transport network and advising the MPE on gas transport matters
- Gassnova SF, a state enterprise, managing solutions related to the capture, transport and storage of carbon dioxide
- Statnett, a state-owned enterprise, the TSO of the central grid
- Enova, another state-owned enterprise, with the main objectives of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing the security of supply

ELECTRICITY MARKET

The electricity network consists of transmission, regional distribution and local distribution. The transmission grid, with a length of 11.000 km, connects producers with consumers at national level and includes the interconnections with other countries. The regional grid is about 19.000 km long and includes links between the transmission and the distribution grid. The distribution grid consists of the local grid supplying power to smaller end-users. It is divided into high voltage (100.000 km) and low voltage. Large consumers, as power-intensive manufacturing are connected either to the transmission or to the regional grid. Households, service industries and small-scale manufacturing are generally connected to the local distribution grid [34].

Statnett is the only TSO, while the distribution network is operated by 146 companies [62]. Statnett responsibilities include frequency regulation, maintaining balance of the power supply system, regulating cross-border interconnections and promoting efficient development of the system through the implementation of market-based solutions [34].

Figure 0-60: Electricity network structure in Norway [71]

GAS MARKET

The gas network is an integrated system, with a transport capacity of 120 billion Sm³ dry gas per year and a total length of 8.800 km, serving most of the Norwegian continental shelf.

There are three onshore gas processing plants (Kårstø, Kollsnes and Nyhamna) and six receiving terminals in Europe (two in Germany, one in Belgium, one in France and two in the UK).

Most of the gas network is owned by the joint venture Gassled, regulated by the Petroleum Regulations, while Gassco is the network operator [63].

Figure 0-61: Gas pipelines in the Norwegian continental shelf [108]

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FRANCE

ELECTRICITY MARKET

In France the main actor of the power market is EDF (a state-owned company), dominating the generation, retail supply as well as transmission and distribution. EDF owns 80% of the installed capacity and generates 85% of the national production. The transmission system operator (RTE) and the distribution network operator (ERDF) are indeed owned by EDF. Figure 0-62 offers an overview of the power market structure in France [64].

The main electricity suppliers are Alpiq, Alterna, Axpo, Direct Energie, E.ON, Enalp, EDF, Enel France, Enercoop, Energem, Enovos, GDF Suez, GEG, Iberdrola, Sella, Lampiris, Lucia, Planete Oui, Proxelia, Vattenfall [65].

Figure 0-62: Main actors of the French power market [109]

GAS MARKET

The French natural gas transmission network (see Figure 0-63) allows gas to be transported from import points at borders to delivery points throughout the country or to underground storage sites. It is operated by two operators: GRTgaz (a 75% subsidiary of ENGIE and 25% of Société d'Infrastructures Gazières) and TIGF, a former Total subsidiary, managed by a consortium of Snam-GIC-EDF-CAA companies. Gas transmission networks are regulated by the Commission de régulation de l'énergie (CRE).

Gas storage facilities are managed by Storengy (subsidiary of Engie) and TIGF (former Total subsidiary).

Natural gas supply to domestic, tertiary or small industrial consumers network is provided via distribution networks owned by local authorities and managed under the concession regime. Gas

distribution networks are operated by GRDF (subsidiary of Engie), Antargaz, Veolia and Vedig, plus local distribution companies.

The French gas market consists of two wholesale marketplaces, called Points d'échange de gaz (PEGs): the PEG Nord, in the northern half of France, part of the GRTgaz network area, and the TRS (Trading Region South) corresponding to the area of the TIGF network and the southern part of the GRTgaz network.

Figure 0-63: Natural gas network in France [111]

ITALY

ELECTRICITY MARKET

The national electricity market consists of four distinct segments: production, transmission, distribution and end users Figure 0-64.

Production: electricity generation is achieved by exploiting fossil or renewable sources under a free market regime. However, in order to meet Italian energy requirements, electricity also needs to be purchased from other countries. Most of the electricity, which is imported through the 25 interconnections with foreign countries, comes from France and Switzerland.

Transmission: Terna S.p.A. is responsible for the energy transmission, i.e. the management, maintenance and development of the Italian high voltage electricity grid, and for dispatching, which consists of managing the electricity flows on the grid at any time. Terna operates in a natural monopoly system- a widespread method of governance at the European level, since the optimal configuration is to have a single operator for the Italian territory - and within a market regulated by the Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (ARERA).

Distribution: A complex network infrastructure allows the transport of electricity to the end user, through the primary substations (which transform high voltage electricity into medium voltage electricity), the secondary substations (from medium voltage to low voltage) and the transformers.

The distribution companies, operating under concessions, operate local, low-voltage electricity grids and maintain them.

End users: Sales companies, the final segment of the market, market electricity to agriculture, industrial and tertiary enterprises and to households [66].

Figure 0-64: The national electricity system supply chain [79]

The main actors involved in the national electricity market are the following:

- **Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (ARERA)** is an independent entity, which operates in the context of the regulation of the free electricity and gas market, aiming at:
 - ✓ promoting the competition and efficiency in the public utility services sector;
 - ✓ guarantying an adequate quality and usability levels in the services and a homogeneous distribution throughout the national territory;
 - ✓ defining of a certain, transparent tariff system based on predefined criteria;
 - ✓ protecting the interests of users and consumers [67].
- **Gestore dei Servizi Elettrici (GSE S.p.A.)**, a company wholly owned by the Ministry of Economy and Finance, aims to guarantee the sustainability development of the country. It promotes and manages the economic incentives for the energy production from renewable sources and energy efficiency [68].
- **Acquirente Unico (AU)**, that is part of the GSE group, ensures the supply of electricity, at competitive prices and via a continuous, secure and efficient service, to distributors of captive customers. Acquirente Unico is responsible for regulating electricity import/export [69].
- **Gestore del Mercato Elettrico (GME)** is the company of the GSE group responsible for the organization and economic management of the electricity and gas market, according to

criteria of neutrality, transparency, objectivity and competition between producers, ensuring adequate availability of the power reserve [70].

- Terna S.p.A. is the transmission system operator, which manages the high voltage Italian transmission grid and dispatching of electricity throughout the entire national grid [66].
- Operators: producers, distributors and suppliers. The main operators involved in the national electricity supply chain are reported in the following table 0.16.

Table 0.16: The main operators for each phase of the national electricity supply chain in 2018 [116]

Producers		Distributors		Suppliers	
Enel	19,4%	e-distribuzione	85,1%	Enel	37,8%
Eni	9,2%	Unareti	4,2%	Edison	4,9%
Edison	7,0%	Areti	3,6%	Hera	4,3%
A2A	6,2%	Ireti	1,2%	Eni	4,3%
EPH	4,6%	Edyna	1,0%	Axpo Group	3,7%
Iren	2,9%	Inrete distribuzione energia	0,8%	A2A	3,5%
ENGIE	2,3%	Set distribuzione	0,8%	Green Network	2,9%
ERG	2,1%	Megareti	0,7%	Iren	2,7%
Tirreno power	2,1%	Servizi a Rete	0,4%	Duferco	2,6%
Sorgenia	2,0%	Deval	0,3%	E,on	2,2%
Other producers	42,2%	Other distributors	1,8%	Other suppliers	31,0%

GAS MARKET

The natural gas supply chain consists in different phases from the gas procurement to sale to end costumers, as showed in figure 0-65. The main phases of the gas supply chain are described below [71].

Procurement: The first phase of the supply chain consists in the production and import of natural gas. 7% of the national demand is satisfied with national production, while the remaining 93% is imported by gas pipelines or by ship.

Imports via pipeline take place through the international gas pipelines that connect Italy with major foreign producers (Libya, Algeria, Russia, Norway, etc.).

Procurement via ship takes place for the import of liquefied natural gas. In this case, the gas extracted in the production locations (Qatar and Egypt) is cooled until reaching a liquid state for the transport and regasified once arrived at the destination, subsequently injected into national gas pipeline network.

Figure 0-65: The natural gas supply chain [117]

Transport: At national infrastructure level, natural gas is transported under high pressure through large-diameter underground pipelines separated into two gas pipeline networks: the **national transport network** (approximately 10.299 km) and the **regional transport network** (24.709 km). The first originates at the national entry points (gas withdrawn from production or import locations) and flows through the national network to the regional transport network. The regional transport network encompasses the set of pipelines (secondary lines), which link the national network and consumption centres (delivery points).

Snam Rete Gas S.p.A. controls 96% of the overall network; **Società Gascotti Italia S.p.A.** manages roughly 1.300 km of methane pipelines and holds control over the remaining 4% of the overall network.

Storage and dispatching: The natural gas storage allows the management of peak demand on the market, guarantying a higher energy flexibility. The dispatching process manages the gas network in order to guarantee a balance between demand and supply and ensure the requirements of consumers.

Distribution: Distribution activities include the delivery of natural gas to end customers through networks of functionally integrated local gas pipelines. Technically, the distribution structure consists of the set of delivery points (regulation and measurement stations) and connection points, the network itself, reduction units and/or final reduction units and the utility distribution plants to the end customer.

Distribution is a public service activity, subject to the granting of a concession during a public procurement procedure, and relations between the commissioning authority and the operator are governed by a service agreement.

Wholesale: Wholesaling is carried out by shippers, who buy gas from importers or domestic producers and sell it to end customers (industries or thermoelectric plants) or to retail companies. This activity has been liberalized and today it is among the most fragmented phases in terms of number of operators, of the gas supply chain.

Retail: The retail is managed by the traders, who buy gas from wholesalers and sell it to end customers. To carry out their activities, traders use local distribution networks to withdraw natural gas from delivery points and deliver it to redelivery points (or end customer supply points).

The distribution service between traders and distributors is regulated by "distribution contract" and is subject to a tariff defined by the Authority (ARERA).

The main actors involved in the national gas market are the following:

- **Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (ARERA)** issues the relevant legislation for energy markets, and carries out control, inspection and sanctioning activities.
- **GME** is responsible for the organization and economic management of the gas market, including the Natural Gas Trading Platform (P-GAS) and the Gas Market (MGAS) [70].
- **Producers and importers.** The main operators involved in production and importation of natural gas are reported in table 0.17.

Table 0.17: The main operators involved in production and importation of gas [116]

Producers		Importers	
Eni	76,2%	Eni	52,3%
Royal Dutch Shell	13,9%	Edison	21,8%
Edison	6,8%	Enel Global Trading	9,4%
Gas Plus	2,0%	Dxt Commodities SA	2,9%
Other producers	1,1%	Other importers	13,6%

- **Transport operators.** Snam Rete Gas S.p.A. is the main gas utility in Italy (96% of the overall network), which manages the transport, storage and regasification of natural gas and dispatching activities. Other significant transport operators are Società Gasdotti Italia and Infrastrutture Trasporto Gas [72].
- **Storage operator:** Stogit, Edison Stoccaggio, Ital Gas Storage and other operators [72].
- **Distributor operator, wholesalers and retailers.** The main operators involved in these phases are listed below.

Table 0.18: The main operators involved in wholesale, distribution and retail phases [116]

Distributors		Wholesalers		Retailers	
Italgas	28,4%	Eni	15,3%	Eni	19,3%
2I Reta Gas S,p,A	18,6%	Engie Global Markets	9,9%	Edison	13,2%
Hera	9,4%	Eni Trading & Shipping	9,1%	Enel	11,0%
A2A	7,5%	Enel Global Trading	9,0%	Iren	4,5%

Iren	4,4%	Edison	6,9%	Hera	3,7%
Ascopiave	3,2%	Engie Italia	4,7%	A2A	3,3%
E,S,Tr,A,	1,9%	Sheel Energy Europe Limited	3,6%	Energeticky A Prumyslovy Holding A,S,	3,3%
Eg Holding	1,3%	Dxt Commodities Sa	3,2%	Sorgenia	2,2%
Other distributors	25,3%	Other wholesalers	38,3%	Other retailers	39,5%

AUSTRIA

The Austrian Power Grid AG (APG) controls the Power Grid of Austria and maintains the supply-demand balance. As TSO, they monitor, coordinate and control the cross-boarder flow of electricity. In addition, they are responsible for the exchange of electricity with neighbor countries and ensure a sustainable power supply. Thus, the APG is also a member of the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) [73].

Since 2001, the Austrian energy markets for electricity and gas are liberalized. The regulator for the Austrian electricity and gas market is called E-Control. They are politically and financially independent and are responsible for a fair market competition, which compromise the security and sustainability of supply. Their main responsibilities involve legal tasks, regulatory functions for the electricity and gas market, monitoring and supervision aspects, dispute settlement tasks, renewables issues, equalized payments tasks, stranded costs and the compilation of electricity and gas statistics [74].

ELECTRICITY MARKET

The Austrian power market consists of around 290 suppliers and 130 grid operators. The main ones are listed below. The APCS Power Clearing and Settlement AG is the balance group coordinator in the Austrian power grid zone. They calculate, clear and settle the energy used by the balance groups [75].

MAIN GENERATORS:

Verbund AG, BEWAG, KELAG, EVN, Energie AG, Linz AG, Salzburg AG, Energie Steiermark, TIWAG, Vorarlberg Kraftwerke AG, Wien Energie

MAIN SUPPLIERS:

Energie AG Oberösterreich Vertrieb GmbH, Energie Burgenland Vertrieb GmbH & Co KG, Energie Steiermark Kunden GmbH, Energie Klagenfurt GmbH, EVN Energievertrieb GmbH & Co KG, KELAG-Kärntner Elektrizitäts-Aktiengesellschaft, Linz Strom Vertrieb GmbH & Co KG, Salzburg AG für Energie, Verkehr und Telekommunikation, Verbund AG, Vorarlberger Kraftwerke AG, WIEN ENERGIE Vertrieb GmbH & Co KG

MAIN GRID OPERATORS:

Wiener Netze GmbH, Energienetze Steiermark GmbH, Vorarlberger Energienetze GmbH, TINETZ-Tiroler Netze GmbH, Salzburg Netz GmbH, Netz Oberösterreich GmbH, Netz Niederösterreich GmbH, Netz Burgenland GmbH, KNG-Kärnten Netz GmbH, LINZ NETZ GmbH, Energie Klagenfurt GmbH, Stromnetz Graz GmbH & Co KG, Innsbrucker Kommunalbetriebe AG

GAS MARKET

Austria is divided into three gas market regions, namely region “Ost”, region “Tirol” and region “Vorarlberg”. The market consists of around 85 suppliers and 20 grid operators. The main ones are again listed below. The AGCS Gas Clearing and Settlement AG is the balance group coordinator of the “OST” zone. They calculate and provide the balance energy for respective balance groups [76].

The main demand of gas is covered by Russia, the remaining part is coming from Norway and Germany. Worth mentioning is, that Austria is the interconnection point for gas transit from east to west in Europe. The location “Baumgarten” is one of the largest gas hubs in Europe and supplies several countries through a number of pipeline systems with gas [77].

MAIN SUPPLIERS:

Energie AG Oberösterreich Power Solutions GmbH, Energie Burgenland Vertrieb GmbH & Co KG, Energie Graz GmbH & Co KG, Energie Steiermark Kunden GmbH, EVN Energievertrieb GmbH & Co KG, KELAG-Kärntner Elektrizitäts-Aktiengesellschaft, LINZ GAS VERTRIEB GMBH & CO KG, RAG Austria AG, Salzburg AG für Energie, Verkehr und Telekommunikation, TIGAS-Erdgas Tirol GmbH, Verbund AG, WIEN ENERGIE Gasnetz GmbH

MAIN GRID OPERATORS:

Energie Graz GmbH & Co KG, Energie Klagenfurt GmbH, Energienetze Steiermark GmbH, GAS CONNECT AUSTRIA GmbH, KNG-Kärnten Netz GmbH, LINZ NETZ GmbH, Netz Burgenland GmbH, Netz Niederösterreich GmbH, Netz Oberösterreich GmbH, Salzburg Netz GmbH, Wiener Netze GmbH

GAS STORAGE OPERATORS:

OMV Gas Storage GmbH, RAG Energy Storage GmbH, astora GmbH & Co KG, Uniper Energy Storage GmbH, GSA LLC.

BELGIUM

The main actors of the power market in Belgium are:

- a. Generators: Engie Electrabel, EDF Luminus, E-ON, T-Power, Others (see Figure 0-66)
- b. Suppliers: Engie Electrabel, Lampiris (Total), EDF Luminus
- c. TSO: Elia
- d. DSO: ORES, Tecteo (Resa), Régie de Wavre, AIESH, AIEG, Sibelga, Eandis, Infrax
- e. Regulators: CREG (national), VREG (Flanders), CWaPE (Wallonia), BRUGEL (Brussels-capital region)
- f. Power exchange: EPEX (formerly Belpex)

Figure 0-66: Power generation wholesale market shares in Belgium [47]

	Power generated (TWh)										Market share (%)										
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Electrabel	65,8	70,3	62,7	58,9	50,7	49,9	40,7	37,2	55,0	54,4	85%	82%	72%	73%	71%	71%	68%	67%	79%	77%	
EDF-Luminus ⁽¹⁾	9,4	12,2	12,2	9,3	8,5	8,6	7,6	6,6	6,5	7,8	12%	14%	14%	12%	12%	12%	13%	12%	9%	11%	
E.ON	0,0	0,5	8,8	8,5	7,8	6,9	6,3	4,6	0,9	0,0	0%	1%	10%	11%	11%	10%	11%	8%	1%	0%	
T-Power	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,5	0,4	1,4	2,2	2,6	2,5	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	2%	4%	4%	4%	
Other (<3%)	2,2	2,6	3,0	2,8	4,4	4,9	4,0	5,1	4,9	5,5	3%	3%	3%	4%	6%	7%	7%	9%	7%	8%	
Total	77,4	85,5	86,6	80,5	71,9	70,7	59,9	55,8	69,9	70,2	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	
											HHI	7 299	6 868	5 439	5 599	5 242	5 223	4 893	4 679	6 303	6 152

(1) The shares of SPE and EDF Luminus have been combined since 2010, following the takeover of SPE by EDF.

The main actors of the gas market in Belgium are:

- a. Suppliers: Engie Electrabel, Eni, EDF Luminus [49]
- b. Transmission & storage: Fluxys
- g. Regulators: CREG (national), VREG (Flanders), CWaPE (Wallonia), BRUGEL (Brussels-capital region)

The four regulators (CREG, VREG, CWaPE, BRUGEL) are the main responsible to regulate the power and gas markets. The government is the final decision-maker: federal (SPF/FOD/FGOV) and regional (SPW, Flamish government, Brussels government).

ANNEX IV – LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

GERMANY

ELECTRICITY MARKET

The German electricity market is facing a radical transition, the so-called *Energiewende*, towards a safe, flexible and sustainable power grid. The relevant energy policies at national level are

- Energy Industry Act (EnWG)
- Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG)
- Combined Heat and Power Act (KWKG)
- Incentive Regulation Ordinance (ARegV)
- Measuring point operating law (MsbG)
- Network Expansion Acceleration Act (NABEG)
- Law for the Acceleration of the energy line extension (NABEG-Novelle)

In 2016 the Acts on the Further Development of the Electricity Market and on the Digitalization of the Energy Transition was adopted, setting new rules for the competition between flexible supply, flexible demand and storage and allowing the development of new business models [8].

In Germany power prices are regulated by long-term contracts or by short-term spot market prices. The short-term spot market consists of two markets, the day-ahead and the intraday markets. In the day-ahead market bids and offers for the following day are submitted by midday. The wholesale price is determined based on the exchange. In the intraday trading, electricity can be traded up to 30 minutes before supply [78].

In 2018, the average electricity price was 29,4 ct/kWh for private households and 17,2 for industrial consumers (including the electricity tax) [4].

Different companies deal with forecasting of energy prices in Germany

- EEX Transparency²
- Fraunhofer ISE - Energy charts³
- SMARD⁴
- EPEXSPOT⁵
- Agora Energiewende⁶

² www.eex-transparency.com

³ www.energy-charts.de

⁴ www.smard.de

⁵ www.epexspot.com

⁶ www.agora-energiewende.de

- Next⁷

GAS MARKET

The German gas market was gradually liberalised from 1998 onwards and it is constantly facing changes according to the energy system transition. As mentioned above, because of its geographical location, Germany is a relevant transit country for gas transport in Europe.

As a consequence of the liberalisation, production, trade, distribution and transport were separated. Customers are free to choose their gas supplier. The Federal Network Agency (BNetzA) regulates the gas market and monitors compliance with the assess rules established by the European Gas Directive.

The main policies are the Ordinance on Access of the Gas Supply Network (GasNZV) and the Ordinance on Charges for Access to the Gas Supply Networks (GasNEV).

Natural gas prices are set according to supply and demand. In 2018 the gas price was equal to 6,5 ct/kWh for households and 2,8 ct/kWh for industrial consumers [4].

SPAIN

In general, the decision makers for the power and gas market are the regulators and the government. The most important energy policies at the Spanish national level are the following:

- The electricity market operating rules are defined by the electricity market operator in the Day-ahead and intraday electricity market operating rules [79]
- The technical operating procedures are established by the system operator in the Operating Procedures defined by the system operator in [80]
- The regulated electricity tariff for the consumer, the voluntary price for the small consumer, is defined in Spanish state official newsletter in [80]
- In [81], the remuneration for the operation of the renewable energy sources are established corresponding to the first natural semester of the year 2018 and by which a type installation is approved and its corresponding remuneration parameters are established
- The gas applicable regulations are collected in the Iberian gas market website in which a network code on interoperability and data exchange rules are set up in [82]

The electricity and gas prices are regulated by the government; however, in 2020 the CNMC will also participate more actively. In the electricity sector, the energy price is based on the clearing process of the electricity market. In terms of consumers billing, this can be free or regulated. In the gas sector, the energy price can be regulated for the consumers with a fixed term and a term for consumption.

⁷ www.next-kraftwerke.com

TURKEY

The Energy Efficiency Law No. 5627 enforced in 2007 defines its fundamental purpose as to use energy effectively, avoid waste, ease the burden of energy costs on the economy, and improve efficiency in using energy resources and energy to protect the environment.

The National Climate Change Strategy of 2010-2023 aims to increase energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in buildings, industry, transport and energy sectors.

The Energy Efficiency Strategy of 2012-2023 defines a set of policies supported by result-oriented goals and devises actions that must be taken to achieve the goals.

Further, the Tenth Development Plan of 2014-2018 defines energy efficiency measures that will be taken in the period in line with “1.14 Energy Efficiency Improvement Programme.”

In addition, the 2015-2019 Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources defines energy efficiency goals under “Goal 4: A Turkey that Uses Energy Efficiently” and “Goal 5: Developed Capacity for Energy Efficiency and Saving” under “Theme: 2 Energy Efficiency and Energy Savings”.

The Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and Council of 25 October 2012 on Energy Efficiency requires the Member States to draft national energy efficiency action plans that proposes a structural framework and implementation methodology on energy efficiency. The introduction of the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan in our country is an important step in harmonising with the said Directive.

On the other hand, the goals of the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan interlinked with the legislative texts listed above are also included in the National Energy and Mining Policy issued by the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources [22].

GREECE

The national Legal basis was Law 4414/2016 on a new support scheme for RES and HECHP. The support scheme intends to incentivize electricity production from RES to contribute to the achievement of the target set by Directive 2009/28/EU on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources at 20% share of energy from RES sources on the EU overall gross energy consumption in 2020. Directive 2009/28/EU, set this target for Greece, based on GDP/capita, energy consumption and other indicators, at 18% share of RES on Greece’s overall consumption in 2020. Based on the latest data Greece’s RES share on total final gross energy consumption was 15,32% in 2016, with electricity from renewable sources (RES-e) representing almost 23,2% of the total electricity generation (Big Hydro Units included) [30]. Significant new investment is still required to reach the national RES target (18% by 2020). The Greek gas market is still based on the execution of bilateral contracts between the suppliers importing natural gas, mainly the incumbent DEPA S.A., and their customers (i.e. industries and retailers); no organized wholesale market exists yet. Transactions that have been recorded so far are the result of the following mechanisms: a) wholesale trade of LNG quantities in-tank, b) resale of gas to eligible customers, and c) the gas release (sale) program by DEPA S.A. per the provisions of the Hellenic Competition

Commission (HCC) Decision 551/VII/2012. Moreover, for the first time in 2017, suppliers other than the incumbent were able to import pipeline gas.

ELECTRICITY MARKET

The Greek wholesale electricity market has been organised as a pure mandatory pool since its inception in 2005. After gradual refinements, a transitional market design, implemented over a five-year period, was substituted on 30th September 2010 by its final provisional form. The revised market design, which is termed as the 5th Reference Day, reflects the full implementation of the 2005 Grid and Market Operation Code.

In essence, the new market design introduced a distinction between the day-ahead market and the balancing mechanism that follows, as in other countries with compulsory pools. This structure reflects with more clarity the factors influencing prices, the uncertainties involved and the implied risks at these distinct time scales. More specifically, during the transitory market regime, the Day Ahead market provided an indicative unit commitment schedule and a reference spot price (SMP forecast), which served purely as a signal. Cash-flows were based on ex-post SMP prices. These were derived by re-solving the same cost-minimization algorithm as in the day-ahead schedule by inserting metered values of the various inputs (mainly demand, plant availabilities and renewables' output) instead of day-ahead forecasts. These ex-post prices were applied to the actual quantities consumed or produced (the latter reflecting to a large extent the real-time dispatch orders of the TSO).

As opposed to an overall market settlement (through ex-post SMP prices), the current market design involves two distinct settlement processes:

1. The settlement of the day-ahead market, in which generators' payments (suppliers' charges) are computed, based on the SMP prices and the plant schedules derived from the day-ahead dispatch (load declarations submitted)
2. The settlement of imbalances, in which deviations from day-ahead schedules are charged or compensated, depending on whether they are exogeneous or reflect the TSO' dispatch orders.
3. There is also a provision for imbalance penalties, if certain limits are violated regarding the magnitude and the frequency of the deviations.

In the day-ahead market, uniform pricing still applies, reflecting the offer of the most expensive unit dispatched so that predicted demand is satisfied. Zonal pricing, intended to reveal congestion problems and signal the location of new capacity, has not been activated yet, although two zonal prices, applicable to generators, are explicitly derived, currently only as an indication. Participants may enter into bilateral financial contracts (CfDs), but physical delivery transactions are constrained within the pool and related contracts do not exist. A cap of 150 €/MWh has been imposed on generators' offers.

The following rules or supplementary mechanisms still apply:

1. A lower limit is imposed on generators' offers, equal to the minimum variable cost of each unit in each trading period, as -in the current structure- the incumbent has a strong incentive to suppress wholesale prices.

2. A cost-recovery mechanism ensures that generators dispatched by the TSO, beyond the day-ahead schedule, are remunerated based on their declared minimum variable costs plus a 10% margin. This mechanism creates a safety net, which often makes participants rather indifferent to the price levels.
3. A Capacity Adequacy Mechanism is applied for the partial recovery of capital costs, with suppliers being obliged to buy capacity certificates from generators. The value of these certificates was revised in November 2010 from 35.000 to 45.000 €/MW, in order to alleviate the impact of low demand on generators' revenues. Adjusting the value of the certificates based on the technical flexibility and environmental impact of each plant was also explored as a possible future refinement.

From February 2012 onwards, an ITO model (as opposed to an ISO) was adopted for the Greek market and this implied the re-structuring of the former TSO into two discrete entities:

- The Market Operator (LAGIE), which solves the day-ahead market, conducts its clearing, and engages into contracts with renewable producers.
- The System Operator (ADMIE), which owns the network, as a subsidiary of PPC, conducts the real time dispatch, the clearing of the imbalance market and the settlement of all other charges or payments.

Given the above development, the market code was decomposed into the Grid Code and the Transactions Code (Code documents on Greek). RAE determined the principles for the certification of the new ITO in accordance with the Law 4001, which reflected the EC directive. The TSO's certification process is expected to be completed by the end of 2012. A Distribution Network Operator was also formed and RAE is currently assessing its compliance procedure.

The day-ahead market yields the reference price for the industry, as it constitutes the major component on which generators' cash-flows are based. Due to the mandatory physical trading in this market, the traded volume of electricity is equal to the annual demand (including the interconnection balance), i.e. 51.872.288 MWh. This represents a decline of 0,94% relatively to 2010. Alternatively, we may consider imports and exports as distinct trading volumes in the market and add them to the local plant production. Adopting the latter definition, the yearly trading volume attains the value of 59.766.618, which represents an increase of 3% relatively to 2010. A futures market has not been developed yet, while OTC trading has not been activated either.

Regarding the market structure, PPC retained its dominant position over 2011 but its market share declined substantially, both in the generation and the supply side. In the generation sector, a significant change towards a less concentrated structure occurred in 2010, as two new IPP units entered into commercial operation, and this change was reinforced in 2011, with the addition of two other IPP plants. In terms of thermal capacity, this direction of market evolution is not expected to persist in the future, as all private plants have now been completed, and the new plants expected are owned by PPC. This would change however, if plant divestments, intensively discussed under Troika's pressure or alternative measures of PPC's capacity allocation are implemented in the coming years. Apart from conventional generation, changes in market structure were enhanced by a steady, currently explosive, renewables' penetration, in which PPC's share is minor.

More specifically, regarding new capacity, significant additions occurred in 2011, intensifying competition for mid and peak load. The market dynamics changed as a result, but only to the extent that the details of the market design allowed. A critical factor for market outcomes was the market rule that allows generators to offer 30% of their plant's capacity at a price below its minimum marginal cost. This rule allows the dispatch of various plants for reserve provision, which is crucial for the plants' viability in an era of capacity surplus, but suppresses prices to levels not reflective of the full production cost. In this context, RAE has proposed the removal of this rule, which turned out to be rather distorting. Focusing again on market structure features, after the entry of two new CCGT plants (Elpedison Thisvi and Heron CC) in April 2010, two additional plants, Protergia (444,5 MW) and Korinthos Power (437 MW), entered the system in 2011. The former initiated its commercial operation in December 2011, after trial operation since January 2011. The latter started its trial operation in December 2011, with commercial operation expected in April 2012. Both plants belong to the Mytilinaios Group. In particular, Korinthos Power is a subsidiary company of Mytilinaios Group, owned jointly with Motor-oil, with shares 65% and 35% respectively. Given the above developments, Mytilinaios Group became the largest IPP player in terms of installed capacity, followed by Elpedison with capacity of 812 MW. Given the above developments, IPP gas plants are currently active in the wholesale market.

Their ownership structure is delineated below:

Enthess (395 MW) and Thisvi (422 MW), both CCGT plants, are owned by Elpedison.

Heron II (432 MW, CCGT) and Heron I[2] (147.5 MW, OCGT) are owned by Heron Thermolectric (GEK Terna- Gdf Suez).

Protergia (444.5 MW, CCGT), Korinthos Power (437 MW, CCGT), and Alouminion (334 MW, large-scale CHP) are owned by Mytilinaios Group.

Motoroil is a cogeneration unit of 2 MW net capacity, owned by the refinery.

Moreover, as stated by the TSO in its ten-year Grid Development Plan, six other thermal units, of total capacity 2476 MW, had also applied for connection until December 2011. This capacity amount included the incumbent's new CCGT units and more specifically, Aliveri V (417MW), projected to be completed by Autumn 2012, and Megalopoli V (811MW), which seemed to be progressing in terms of the expansion of the gas network in the region. The above capacity amount does not include however, Ptolemaida V (660 MW), for which private involvement along with PPC has been discussed. In addition, five hydro units, of total capacity 335 MW, had applied for connection by the end of 2011, while other 287 MW got licensed, but not applied for connection yet (including Mesochora). The obsolete lignite units Megalopoli I and II, of capacity 250 MW, were decommissioned.

Despite the substantial amount of capacity that had applied for connection in the past, the TSO estimated that due to the economic recession, various investment plans were cancelled, which seems a reasonable assessment. In particular, the units expected to be added to the system over the next decade, which were used for system analysis, are Aliveri V, Megalopoli V, Ptolemaida V and Ilarion (a 153 hydro unit in Aliakmonas river).

Electricity demand remained fairly stable over 2011 at 5.1872 GWh, exhibiting a minor decline of 0,94% relatively to 2010 at the interconnected system. At the national level, demand was also unaffected, amounting to 6.1834 GWh (relatively to 6.1817 GWh in 2010). It is notable that demand recovered over the last quarter, exhibiting an increase of 2% relatively to Q4 2010, as air-

conditioning was used quite intensively for heating, perceived by consumers as a less expensive option than oil.

Given the addition of substantial capacity over two consecutive years, the market share of PPC declined significantly in 2011. In the interconnected system, PPC's share, in terms of volume, dropped to 75% of local production, relatively to 85% in 2010, while independent gas producers achieved a share of 20% (Elpedison 8,9%, Mytilinaios 5,6% and Heron Thermolectric 5,3%). Renewables captured 5,2% of local production. While IPP's share more than doubled, PPC's gas production declined by 816 GWh (13,5%). It is interesting that despite this decline, the gas cost for PPC increased by €10 million due to an increase in gas prices of 18,4% and a €21 million tax contribution due to the levy imposed on gas.

There are two forecasting models which are implemented in Greece:

- **AleaSoft:** Public Power Corporation (PPC), the largest electric utility in Greece, is using AleaSoft price forecasting models to optimise its operations [83].
- **PRIMES:** The PRIMES (Price-Induced Market Equilibrium System) is a large scale applied energy system model that provides detailed projections of energy demand, supply, prices and investment to the future, covering the entire energy system including emissions. The distinctive feature of PRIMES is the combination of behavioral modelling (following a micro-economic foundation) with engineering aspects, covering all energy sectors and markets. The model has a detailed representation of instruments policy impact assessment related to energy markets and climate, including market drivers, standards, and targets by sector or overall. It handles multiple policy objectives, such as GHG emissions reductions, energy efficiency, and renewable energy targets which provides pan-European simulation of internal markets for electricity and gas [84].

Finally, Greece imports and exports electricity to the following countries: a) Turkey, b) FYROM, c) Italy, d) Bulgaria and e) Albania. RAE is the authority that regulates imports and exports.

GAS MARKET

The TSO of the National Natural Gas System (NNGS) in Greece was established as a “société anonyme” under the name of “DESFA S.A.” in February 2007. DESFA S.A. is a 100% subsidiary of DEPA S.A., the incumbent and vertically-integrated gas company in Greece. DESFA S.A. applied to RAE to be certified as an Independent Transmission System Operator. DESFA S.A. is the owner and operator of the national network gas system (NNGS), which is comprised of the main high-pressure pipeline and its branches, as well as the LNG Terminal at Revithoussa Island, and is a certified ITO under the unbundling rules of the Third Energy Package. DESFA S.A. has exclusive rights for the operation, maintenance, development and exploitation of the NNGS and is currently the only gas transmission system operator in the country [29].

The National Natural Gas System (NNGS) transports Natural Gas to consumers connected to the NNGS in the Greek mainland, which is imported from the Greek-Bulgarian borders, the Greek-Turkish borders and the Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) terminal, which is installed at Revithoussa Island at Megara (Athens/Attica region). DESFA S.A. prepares and submits every year to RAE an

annual balancing plan for approval. The balancing plan includes TSO's estimated natural gas needs for network balancing as well as an evaluation of possible balancing gas supply sources for the next year. The plan also includes DESFA's proposal regarding the characteristics of the balancing contracts for the next year. To this effect, DESFA S.A. can either procure balancing gas directly from the long-term LNG contract of the incumbent (in line with an interim - transitional - provision of the Greek Gas Law), or procure balancing gas through a market-based approach, in the form of an international tender procedure (in line with the basic provisions of the Gas Law).

Based on the data of DEPA S.A., the company has signed long term contracts with the Russian Gazprom (until 2026), the Turkish BOTAS (until 2021) and the Algerian Sonatrach (2021). DEPA's contract with Gazprom ensures the supply of Greek market up to 2026. The natural gas volumes are injected into the NNGS at Strimnochori Sidirokastrou, near the Greek - Bulgarian borders. The contract with the Turkish BOTAS concerns supply of natural gas up to 2021. Natural gas is injected into the NNGS at Kipoi Evrou, through the existing Interconnector Turkey-Greece. Likewise, the contract with Sonatrach (LNG) ensures supply of LNG in the Greek market up to 2021. Algerian LNG enters the NNGS at the re-gasification terminal on Revithousa Island, in the gulf of Megara. Furthermore, DEPA is supplied with LNG from the global spot market. Finally, DEPA has recently entered into a long term supply contract with the Azeri AGSC for gas to be produced at the Shah Deniz II reserve [85].

According to RAE, Greece has no indigenous production of gas. Therefore, gas supply so far was realized by long-term, take-or-pay import contracts. The existing contracts are summarised in the following:

- Contract for pipeline gas from Russia (1996-2016): 2,80 bcm p.a.
- Contract for LNG from Algeria (2000-2021): 0,68 bcm p.a.
- Contract for pipeline gas from Turkey (anticipated from 2007 onwards, as soon as the interconnection is completed): 0,75 bcm p.a.
- Apart from the existing contracts mentioned above, it is anticipated that another contract for pipeline gas from Russia of potentially 3 bcm p.a. be affected by an independent supplier.

Revithousa Terminal is of the greatest importance for the safety of supply of LNG to the system as it is the only storage facility that exists in Greece. The expansion of the terminal will allow an annual capacity of 7bcma. There are also plans for the construction of underground storage in Kavala, which will consist the only natural gas storage facility (capacity 1bcm).

Several refineries are engaged in projects aimed at using or producing the so-called "green hydrogen". Green hydrogen's advantages include the lowering of emissions from fuels and the storage of excess renewable electricity when supply exceeds demand.

Finally, by taking into account the prices of the main gas suppliers in Greece for 2019, the average gas price for the industrial consumers is approximately: 34,04 €/MWh.

NORWAY

The main regulations in Norway for the management of energy and water resources are [34]:

- Waterfall Rights Act
- Watercourse Regulation act
- Water Resources Act
- Energy Act
- Offshore Energy Act
- Electricity Certificate Act

Other regulations to manage energy and water resources are [34]:

- Planning and Building Act
- Nature Diversity Act
- Expropriation Act
- Competition Act
- Consumer Purchases Act
- Pollution Control Act
- Neighbouring Properties Act
- Cultural Heritage Act
- Outdoor Recreation Act
- Reindeer Husbandry Act
- Public Administration Act

The EU Water Framework Directive (200/60/EC) has been implemented in the Norwegian law through the Water Management Regulations.

Norway participates together with Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania to the Nord Pool, a regional power exchange, which includes a day-ahead market (Elsport) and a continuous intraday market (Elbas). 90% of the physical power trade in Norway takes place at the Nord Pool. Nord Pool controls the operation up to one hour before real time, afterwards the responsibility is given to the national TSOs. The Nordic power market participates to the Price Coupling of Regions in Europe [33].

Electricity prices are not regulated in Norway and vary depending on the DSOs. Customers can compare prices online⁸ and choose between spot, fixed or variable prices. 60% of customers currently have contracts at spot prices. Electricity prices in Norway are the lowest in Europe, both for industries and households [33].

⁸ www.strompris.no

FRANCE

After hosting the COP21 in 2015, France has developed an integrated energy and climate policy. The Commission de régulation de l'énergie (CRE) is the energy regulator, responsible for both the electricity and the gas market. The CRE consists in the Board of Commissioners and the Standing Committee for Disputes and Sanctions. CRE's responsibilities include [65]:

- Market regulation
- ensuring non-discriminatory access to the transmission and distribution networks
- establishing transmission and distribution tariffs
- approving investment programmes of RTE and reviewing the Ten Year Network Development Plan
- monitoring the retail market and the transactions on the wholesale electricity, natural gas and CO2 markets
- setting the price for nuclear power

The Ministry of Ecology, Sustainable Development and Energy (Ministère de l'Ecologie, du Développement durable et de l'Energie, MEDDE) is responsible for energy, environmental and climate policies. The Supreme Council of Energy (CSE -Conseil supérieur de l'énergie) advises the MEDDE on national energy policy. ADEME (Agence de l'Environnement et de la Maîtrise de l'Energie) is the French Environment and Energy Management Agency and focuses on the implementation of policies related to energy efficiency and renewable energy. The Nuclear Safety Authority (Autorité de sûreté nucléaire, ASN) regulates nuclear safety and radiation protection [65].

The main laws are the 2005 POPE Law and the 2007-10 Grenelle Environment Acts. The Energy Transition for Green Growth Act entered into force in 2015, including over 150 regulations, as a result of the National Debate on the Energy Transition (DNTE). The main targets are [65]:

- reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 40% in 2030 and by a factor of 4 towards 2050 (compared to 1990)
- reduction of final energy consumption by 20% in 2030 and 50% in 2050 (compared to 2012)
- renewables share of 32% in gross final energy consumption and 40% of total electricity generation by 2030
- reduction of fossil fuel consumption of 30% by 2030 (in comparison to 2012)
- reduction of nuclear share in the electricity mix to 50% by 2025
- reduction of municipal waste production per capita of 10% over 2010-20, with 50% less landfill by 2025
- a long-term carbon trajectory, implemented through the annually confirmed carbon component in energy taxation and the EU-ETS.

Since 2011, a regulatory framework has been put in place to develop and support the injection of bio-methane into natural gas networks. This framework allows producers of bio-methane to benefit from a regulated feed-in tariff for 15 years. The feed-in tariff, financed by a part of the domestic tax on natural gas consumption (TICGN) paid by the final consumer, varies between 50

and 140 €/MWh. This bio-methane can be purchased by any natural gas supplier. France aims at injecting 8 TWh bio-methane per year by 2023, contributing to the achievement of the objective of consuming 10% of renewable gas in 2030 set by the law on the energy transition for green growth [38].

ITALY

At the end of the 90s the Legislative Decree n. 79 of 16 March 1999 (Bersani Decree) started the process of liberalization of energy market, dismantling of the existing monopoly held by ENEL. This decree, which officially included the indications of the 1996 EU directive aimed at creating the Single Energy Market in Europe, has allowed a gradual liberalization of the production, import, export, purchase and sale of electricity. Since July 2007 the energy market in Italy has been completely liberalized, each supplier can decide to enter the market at any time and users can freely decide which supplier to contact.

Following the 1996 EU directive, the Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (ARERA) is established by Law No. 481 of 1995 for carrying out regulatory and supervisory activities in the sectors of electricity, natural gas, water services, waste cycle and district heating. ARERA is an independent administrative authority that operates to ensure the promotion of competition and efficiency in public utility services and protect the interests of users and consumers [67].

The National Energy Strategy (SEN 2017) is the ten-year plan that the Italian Government drew up to anticipate and manage the change of the national energy system: a document looking beyond 2030, and laying the groundwork for building an advanced and innovative energy model.

The Strategy aims to make the national energy system more:

- competitive: improving the country's competitiveness, continuing to reduce the price and energy cost gap with Europe, in a context of increasing international prices;
- sustainable: achieving in a sustainable way the environmental and de-carbonization objectives defined at European level, in line with the future targets established in COP21;
- safe: improving the security of supply and flexibility of energy systems and infrastructures, strengthening energy independence [86].

Regarding the Power Exchange, there are different types of electricity market with their specific characteristics:

- **MGP (Day-Ahead Market)**, where energy is negotiated by setting prices based on the relationship between demand and supply. Prices are set for the next day and the amount of energy to be used is also defined;
- **MI (Intra-Day Market)**, which is made up of different sections and which can change what is established in the Day-Ahead Market;
- **MPEG (Daily Products Market)**, which is linked to the daily negotiations between electricity market operators involved in the sale or purchase of electricity.

- **MSD (Dispatching Service Market)**, which comes into play for solving intra-national congestions, creating energy reserves and real-time balancing. The necessary energy is purchased and sold to counterbalance any imbalance on the network. On the MSD market, Terna acts as a counterparty central and the offers from those who are able to supply energy (or reduce their production), once accepted, are remunerated at the price presented (pay-as-bid).)

GME, the Electricity Market Operator, manages these markets and defines system marginal prices at which the energy is traded [70].

Instead, the Natural Gas Exchange is divided as follows (see Figure 0-67):

- **MP-GAS (Spot Market)** comprises the set of the following markets:
 - **MGP-GAS (Day-Ahead Market)** takes place according to the continuous trading method. Purchase and sale offers are selected for the three gas-days following the one in which the trading session opens.
 - **MI-GAS (Intra-Day Market)** takes place according to the continuous trading method. On the MI-GAS gas, purchase and sale offers are selected for the gas-day corresponding to the day in which the trading session opens.
 - **MPL-GAS (Locational products Market)** is based on auction trading. The MPL sessions take places at the request of Snam Rete Gas, which procures gas needed to manage physical requirements located within the balancing area or any expected differences between injections and total withdrawals in the grid;
 - **MGS (Storage Market)** takes place according to auction trading. Purchase and sell offers of gas in storage are negotiated by authorized users and by Snam Rete Gas
- **MT-GAS (Forward Market)** takes place according to the continuous trading method. Many trading books are organized on the MT-GAS for each type of negotiable product, referring to different delivery periods, within which gas purchase and sale offers are selected [70].

Figure 0-67: The Natural Gas Exchange in Italy [115]

From the industrial consumers' point of view, the average electricity price is 0,0885 €/kWh (excluding taxes and levies; 0,1662 €/kWh including all taxes and levies), while the average

gas price is 0,0277 €/kWh (excluding taxes and levies; 0,0325 €/kWh including all taxes and levies) [87].

AUSTRIA

The following list represents the relevant legal frameworks and energy policies for electricity and gas in Austria [88]:

- Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2010 - ElWOG 2010
- Gaswirtschaftsgesetz 2011 - GWG 2011
- Energie-Control-Gesetz - E-ControlG
- Energielenkungsgesetz 2012 - EnLG 2012
- Energie-Infrastrukturgesetz - E-InfrastrukturG
- Bundes-Energieeffizienzgesetz - EEffG
- Alternative Streitbeilegung-Gesetz (AStG)
- Verrechnungsstellengesetz
- Wettbewerbsgesetz - WettbG
- Kartellgesetz 2005 - KartG 2005

In Austria, the overall price for the consumed energy in the industry consists of the actual energy price, the system charges, and the taxes and surcharges. A precise composition of the final energy price depends always on the consumer, as energy prices vary depending on the annual consumption. In many cases, consumers and providers have certain contracts regarding the energy price based on their consumption profile. An average composition of the industry electricity and gas prices are illustrated in Figure 0-68 the prices are representative for the consumption segments of electricity from 500 MWh to 1999 MWh, and for gas from 10.000 GJ to 100.000 GJ [89] [90].

Figure 0-68: Average price for electricity and gas in Austria [cent/kWh] [133]

Contrary to the energy price, system charges are regulated in Austria. In general, a free competition is ongoing for the energy price, where each market participant determines the energy

price for the provided energy, unless there are no contracts between provider and customer. However, the system charges are regulated by the E-Control and thus they determine the system charges. Taxes and surcharges are levied by the state, the federal provinces or the municipalities [89].

BELGIUM

The basic legislation at federal level is as follows: the Act amending the Electricity Act of 29 April 1999 on the organisation of the electricity market (published in the Belgian Official Gazette on 8 January 2012), and the Royal Decree establishing a grid code governing operation of and access to the electricity transmission system.

At regional level, the basic legislation for each region is as follows [91]:

- Flanders: the Energy Decree of 8 May 2009, the Energy Decision of 19 November 2010, and the Grid Code on the local electricity transmission system in the Flemish Region;
- Wallonia: the Decree of 12 April 2001, and the Walloon Government Decision on the reform of the grid code governing operation of and access to the electricity transmission system in the Walloon Region;
- Brussels-Capital Region: the Ordinance of 19 July 2001, and the Decision of the Government of the Brussels-Capital Region approving the grid code governing the operation of the regional electricity transmission system.

In the study [92] the average price paid by industrial customers have been analyzed. The results are shown in the following tables.

Table 0.19: Average electricity price for industrial consumers in the 3 Belgian regions [€/MWh] [135]

[€/MWh]	Flanders			Wallonia			Brussels Region			Average
Consumer profile	2016	2017	2018	2016	2017	2018	2016	2017	2018	2018
E1 (10 GWh/y)	76,1	83,3	74,6	82,6	86,7	80,0	80,2	84,2	79,8	78,1
E2 (25 GWh/y)	68,2	74,2	65,7	72,9	76,2	70,9	65,9	69,1	64,4	67,0
E3 100 (GWh/y)	58,8	61,6	55,6	56,6	58,7	53,6	58,7	61,1	56,8	55,3
E4 (500 GWh/y)	50,6	52,4	46,9	51,0	52,5	47,3	55,4	57,4	53,0	49,1

Table 0.20: Average gas price for industrial consumers in the 3 Belgian regions [€/MWh] [135]

[€/MWh]	Flanders			Wallonia			Brussels Region			Average
Consumer profile	2016	2017	2018	2016	2017	2018	2016	2017	2018	2018
G1 (100 GWh/y)	22,1	15,8	18,8	22,3	16,0	19,0	23,6	17,1	20,3	19,4
G2 (2500 GWh/y)	21,4	15,1	18,1	21,4	15,1	18,1	22,6	16,3	19,4	18,5

Table 0.21: Definition of electricity consumption profiles used in [92]

		E1 (Electricity 1)	E2 (Electricity 2)	E3 (Electricity 3)	E4 (Electricity 4)
When?		January 2018	January 2018	January 2018	January 2018
Annual demand	MWh	10.000	25.000	100.000	500.000
Consumption profile		Baseload (working days only)	Baseload (working days only)	Baseload (including weekends)	Baseload (including weekends)
Consumption hours eq.*	h/year	5.000	5.000	7.692	8.000
Connection	kV	26-36	30-70	≥ 150	≥ 150
Grid operator		DSO (TransHS)	LTSO	TSO	TSO
Contracted capacity	kW	2.000	5.000	13.000	62.500

Table 0.22: Definition of gas consumption profiles used in [92]

		G1 (Gas 1)	G2 (Gas 2)
When?		January 2018	January 2018
Annual demand	MWh	100.000	2.500.000
Consumption profile		Baseload	Baseload
Consumption hours eq.*	h/year	6.667	8.333
Grid operator		DSO (T6)	TSO
Contracted capacity	kW	15.000	300.000

ANNEX V – TECHNOLOGICAL, LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

GERMANY

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Several strategies have been implemented in the industrial sector, with aim of increasing energy flexibility. The most important include

- Introducing control and monitoring technologies
- Adopting efficient procedures
- Adjusting process intensity
- Improving energy and material buffers

Flexibility of manufacturing systems is defined as the ability to react to grid instabilities and to adapt energy demand accordingly. The most common technical solutions to increase energy flexibility are [93]:

- 1) Demand Side Management (DSM)
 - Load shaping (peak clipping, valley filling, load shifting, energy efficiency, flexible load shape), shown in Figure 0-69
 - Demand response (price-based, incentive-based)
- 2) Energy storage options
 - compressed air
 - thermal storage
 - decentralized options like batteries
- 3) Energy conversion options
 - waste-heat recovery

Figure 0-69: load shaping for demand side management [93]

In Germany the main challenge related to energy flexibility is the harmonization of operational and investment decisions with changing system requirements. Besides, flexibility strategies can be in conflict with energy efficiency strategies [94].

Some of these barriers relate directly to the price signals of the wholesale market such as [95]

- the lack of transmission of the price signal from the wholesale market to the final consumers
- Deficits in the market design of flexibility markets
- Incorrect incentives due to the structure of grid usage fees
- Incorrect incentives due to taxes, levies and other fees
- High investment costs for the implementation of flexibility strategies

The most common generation and storage options at factory level are [94]

Generation

- Electricity: Combined Heat and Power plants (CHP), steam turbine power plants, gas and steam turbine power plants, ORC systems.
- Steam: steam boilers, heat exchangers
- Heat: hot water boilers, CHP, heat pumps

Storage: heat storage, cold storage, compressed air storage, water storage, natural gas storage, material buffers

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

Implicit Flexibility

One of the most important types of ancillary services is the so-called load-frequency control, which is regulated at European level by the ENTSO-E (European network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity) and ACER (Agency for Cooperation of Energy Regulators).

At national level the Energy act (EnWG) as well as the regulation on access to power systems (StromNZV) define TSOs responsibilities and requirements for the provision of ancillary services. The German renewable Energy Act (EEG) defines how RES operators can participate in control reserve markets.

In order to ensure a balance between generation and demand, the balancing group system regulates the exchange schedule. Every producer and consumer must report its balance and must be part of a balancing group. In case of unbalance, the transmission system operators can apply different types of control reserves (primary, secondary and tertiary). The price of the control reserve is paid by the balancing group, which caused the unbalance [78].

Table 0.23 provides an overview of the balancing market rules.

PCR (primary control reserve), also called FCR (frequency containment reserve), serves to stabilize frequency in the event of failure. PCR is regulated by the total interconnected system in a non-selective manner. (Large scale thermal and hydro power plants).

SCR (secondary control reserve), also called aFRR (automatically activated frequency restoration reserve), takes into account responsibilities for imbalances and is only activated in the areas where the imbalances occur. It is regulated by the TSO of the corresponding area. (Thermal power plants in dispatchable operation, pump-storage power plants)

TCR (tertiary control reserves), also called mFRR (manually activated frequency restoration reserve) is not activated automatically, but is electronically activated by TSOs through the merit-order list server (MOL). It is activated when necessary or even as a prevention measure. (Open-cycle gas turbines, demand-side-management resources, virtual power plants, RES generators as biomass).

PCR, SCR and TCR are provided as positive as well as negative reserves (for deficits and surplus of system balance).

In case of emergency (high imbalances) in Germany other measures can be activated, as for instance exchange of emergency reserve with other control area, deployment of non-operating power plant and provision of contracted interruptible load.

Table 0.23: Demand response access in the balancing and ancillary services market [96]

Terminology ENTSO-E	Terminology German TSOs		Total capacity contracted	Demand response access and participation	Aggregated demand response accepted	Aggregated generation
FCR	Primary control reserve	+/-	830 MW	yes	yes	yes
aFRR		SCR +	1.976 MW	yes	yes	yes

	Secondary control reserve	SCR +	1907 MW	yes	yes	yes
mFRR	Minute reserve	MR +	1.850 MW	yes	yes	yes
		MR -	1.654 MW	yes	yes	yes
Interruptible loads	Immediately interruptible loads (SOL) - AbLaV		750 MW	yes	yes	DR only programme
Interruptible loads	Quickly interruptible loads (SNL) - AbLaV		750 MW	yes	yes	DR only programme
Other ancillary services (re-dispatch, voltage control)	Re-dispatch (winter reserve)		7.000 MW	no	no	no
Capacity mech.	Capacity reserve		2.000 MW	no	no	no
Distribution network services	Does not exist in Germany (only bilateral deals between DSOs and generators)					

The activation is regulated as follows (see Figure 0-70)

- PCR has to be realized within 30 seconds
- SCR: includes capacities that can be deployed for short term and for a longer time period. The maximum lead time is 5 minutes
- TCR: deployment time within 15 minutes

Figure 0-70: Activation rules of reserves [97]

In Germany deployment follows a merit order based on costs for procured SCR. TCR is activated through the merit of order list server, which manages the merit order list, containing the offers received on the reserve market. The economic aspects of the control reserve are given in Table 0.24

Table 0.24: Economic aspects of control-reserve qualities tendered in Germany [97]

	PCR	SCR	TCR
Tender period	Weekly	Weekly	Daily
Tender time	As a rule on Tuesdays (W-1)	As a rule on Wednesdays (W-1)	As a rule Mo-Fri, 10 am
Product time-slice	None (total week)	Peak: Mo-Fri, 8 am - 9 pm, without public holiday Off-peak: residual period	6x4 blocks of hour
Product differentiation	None (symmetric product)	Positive/negative SCRL	Positive/negative TCR
Minimum bid amount	1 MW	5 MW	5 MW (submission of bid for a block of max. 25 MW possible)
Increment of bid	1 MW	1 MW	1 MW
Call for tender	Capacity price merit-order	Energy price merit-order	Energy price merit-order
remuneration	Pay-as-bid (capacity price)	Pay-as-bid (capacity price and energy price)	Pay-as-bid (capacity price and energy price)

Potential benefits of energy flexibility valorisation are

- Reduction of energy costs for the involved factory
- Fast reaction in the event of failure
- Increased security of supply of the power system
- Possibility to increase the share of RES in the energy mix

Explicit Flexibility

The Regulation on agreements on disconnectable loads (AblaV) defines an additional product, which is contracted by TSOs: the use of flexibility to avoid energy-balancing measures. Very short-term markets such as intraday markets can also be described as markets for flexibility, as the high price volatility of these markets can be benefited by consumers. Table 0.25 provides an overview of the access rules in the wholesale market.

Price forecasts and the prices of long-term electricity products theoretically indicate the long-term need for efficiency and flexibility. In this area, however, product development and the liquidity of the relevant markets are still in their early stages. A first step towards specialised products is the "Cap Future" launched by the German electricity exchange EEX in September 2015. This product guarantees the intraday price with a cap of €60/MWh [95].

Table 0.25: Demand response access in the wholesale market [96]

Terminology ENTSO-E	Terminology German TSOs	Total volume traded	Demand response access and participation	Aggregated demand response accepted	Aggregated generation
Day-ahead	EPEX Spot	235 TWh	yes	yes	yes
Intraday	EPEX Spot	41 TWh	yes	yes	yes

After the liberalization of the European energy market, power trade has gained importance, as end consumers can choose between different suppliers. EPEX SPOT manages the power trades in a transparent way, ensuring reliable prices for short-term electricity (day-ahead/intraday).

On the intraday market the minimum volume increment is 0.1 MW and the minimum price increment is 0.1 €/MWh. Electricity is traded for a delivery on the same day or on the following day, either on single hours, on 15-minute periods or on block of hours. Each block can be traded up to 30 minutes before supply begins and until 5 minutes before delivery within the control zone. From 3 pm on of the current day, all hours of the day after can be traded. From 4 pm on all 15-minute periods of the day after can be traded [98].

There are two standardised blocks in Germany [98]:

- Baseload: 1-24 h
- Peakload: 9-20 h (Mo-Fri)

Deliveries are made in the zones [98]:

- Amprion GmbH
- TenneT TSO GmbH
- TransnetBW GmbH

Trading is possible 7 days a week, 24 hours a day [98].

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

In order to increase the share of renewable energy sources in the electricity mix, cross-border operation must be increased and combined with a flexible operation of conventional power plants [99].

From a market perspective the following actions are needed to enhance energy flexibility [100]

- Open up the balancing energy market
- Short-term tender and products, pre-qualification
- Ensure balancing group responsibility via balancing energy price system
- Launch 1/4h products on Day Ahead market
- Later close of trading

From a regulation perspective, new regulations are needed [100]

- Allow CHP flexibility

- Network charges & EEG levy
- Incentive for privileged consumers (own generation, band purchase) to react to stock exchange price
- Sector coupling shall not be penalized
- Power plant shutdowns shall be allowed

Expected flexibility incentives in the wholesale electricity market are volatility of spot and intraday prices on short-term, and volatility of wholesale prices in the long-term [94].

SPAIN

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The state of technology for energy flexibility and assessment of the energy flexibility potential is stated in Spain according to technological advances as well as to restrictions and specific regulations.

According to the International Energy Agency [101] the flexibility of a power system refers to "the extent to which a power system can modify electricity production or consumption in response to variability, expected or otherwise". Another source described it as "the modification of generation injection and/or consumption patterns in reaction to an external signal (price signal or activation) in order to provide a service within the energy system".

The digitalization has positive effects on the flexibility of the energy balance as digitalized energy systems in the future may be able to identify who needs energy and deliver it at the right time, in the right place and at the lowest cost. Digitalization is already improving the safety, productivity, accessibility and sustainability of energy systems.

Spain's flexibility challenges will be volatility and a decline in the need for base-load capacity running throughout the year. With adoption of wind and solar, required base-load capacity could decline by 45 to 75 percent by 2030, so power plants that run continuously today will need to become more flexible in their production. The size of demand fluctuations could increase by 30 to 70 percent, with the slope of fluctuations rising by 55 to 95 percent. Spain has pumped hydro power plants to manage variability and volatility, but it has relatively few interconnections beyond the Iberian Peninsula.

Flexibility is the ability to manage variability and volatility to balance supply and demand, within infrastructure constraints (see Figure 0-71). Firstly, the flexibility use for balancing supply and demand occurs in wholesale and balancing markets. Secondly, flexibility is also used for managing network constraints. Finally, operators of the high-, medium- and low-voltage networks can use flexible resources locally to lower the network load where grids have become congested (congestion management).

Historically, flexibility has mainly been supplied by generators, such as gas-fired power plants and hydropower plants. These generation sources are well-suited to adjust production to respond to changes in the rest of the system. Active control of renewable generation technology also can

provide some flexibility. For instance, the increase and decrease of production of a wind farm can be slowed down to mitigate impacts on the balance of the power system.

Demand-side resources can provide flexibility through demand response. Industrial consumers are already offering flexibility this way to the system operator, by agreeing to reduce or increase consumption as needed, in return for compensation. Residential or small commercial consumers can also provide demand response, but the relatively small scale of the flexible loads of these consumers and relatively high costs per site have limited its use.

Storage provides flexibility by creating a buffer between times of shortage and oversupply of electricity. Different types of storage technology are being applied in different parts of the electricity system—at end-user sites, in the network or close to generators.

A range of existing and new flexibility solutions can be called upon to meet the growing supply and demand matching challenges that will arise in the power industry over the next decades. This will require wider use of current proven solutions as well as new flexibility sources (see Figure 0-72). The most commonly used flexibility sources (centralized, large-scale solution in generation and demand-response programs for industrial users) will still be used, however they can only partly accommodate the flexibility needed. Moreover, investing in additional flexible fossil-based generation capacity may be less attractive, with increasingly stringent GHG emissions policies and a decrease in the average number of operating hours of flexible capacity. The potential for building new pumped-hydropower capacity is also limited for geographic reasons. Technical solutions to make base-load and renewable generation more responsive can also help mitigate the growing need for flexibility. Advanced control of steam turbines and nuclear power plants, for example, allows them to respond more easily to changes in the system, and renewable generators can slow down the increase and decrease of production.

Figure 0-71: Flexibility uses and sources

Figure 0-72: Existing and new sources of flexibility: illustrative examples

SCALE	Residential	Commercial	Large-scale/industrial
FLEXIBILITY SOURCES	Generation	Solar PV Micro-CHP	Medium-size CHP On-site generators Building-integrated PV Industrial CHP Renewables curtailment
	Storage	Electric vehicles Home batteries	Pumped hydropower Grid-based battery storage Large-scale mechanical storage
	Demand-response	Electric vehicles Electric heating/cooling (warm water boilers)	Smart buildings Heating/cooling installations Steam/heat generators

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

Currently, in Spain, the mechanisms for electricity flexibility are the following:

- **Load balancing:** as demand management, done traditionally by pumped storage and interruptibility service.
- **Frequency response:** which are active power ancillary services. Traditionally, the conventional generators provide this service. The future situation is that the batteries are an important source that can stabilize the system frequency.
- **Voltage response:** renewable energy sources can regulate reactive power. Traditionally, it was done by conventional generators.

In terms of gas, the thermal inertia has been traditionally used to improve the energy efficiency of buildings and provide a stable indoor temperature. Another benefit, not taken advantage of, is the use of thermal storage capacity (heat storage) offered by the structure to provide flexibility in energy networks and increase the use of renewable energy.

Delving in the main electricity flexibility strategies in the Spanish system, the interruptibility service [102] and ancillary services [103] are the more common services in the operation.

In the first one, according to Order ITC/2370/2007 there are 5 different types of power reduction, which depend on the minimum notice time (ranging from 2 hours to 0 minutes). In addition, the maximum total duration (ranging from 12 hours to 1 hour) and the maximum hours of interruptibility is 120 per year. In the interruptibility service [14], the retribution scheme is based on an auction. In the last auction the average allocation price has been 96.925 € / MW and year for products of 40 MW and 75.307 € / MW and year for those of 5 MW. Thus, the weighted average allocation has been placed at 81.220 € / MW and year.

In the second one, the ancillary services are the ones provided by the electric grid that facilitate and support the continuous flow of electricity so that supply will continually meet demand. There are various types of ancillary services in the Spanish electricity system, which are defined in the procedures [103]. Each has its strengths; for instance, in terms of response time, duration and up and down regulation it can provide. Hence, we are referring to the active system balancing services which are:

- Primary regulation reserve:

In the Spanish system, the primary regulation is considered a service of the system that is mandatory and unpaid due to the great difficulty in measurement and quality assessment. According to the operational procedure 1.5 any generator with power has to provide 1% of the total installed power for this system service.

Its objective is the automatic and almost instantaneous correction (complete response in maximum 30 seconds) of the frequency imbalances. Generating units must be capable of modifying 1% of their rated output in less than 15 s for frequency variations less than 100 mHz, and linearly up to 30 s for frequency deviations up to 200 mHz. The potential benefit is the quick regulation of the frequency of the network.

So, mostly, the primary reserve is based on action of speed regulators from generation units responding to changes in system frequency in real-time. The flexibility action takes from 30 seconds to 15 minutes.

- Secondary regulation reserve:

In Spain, the secondary reserve is not a mandatory service and it is a paid complementary service regulated by the electricity market.

The regulation band is matched in the market the day before. Nevertheless, the automatic and hierarchical control time horizon of action reaches from 20 seconds to 15 minutes.

It allows the SO to have a very flexible reserve of available capacity (start of the response in no more than 30 seconds and with the ability to stay for a period of 15 minutes until it can be replaced by tertiary regulation) to automatically resolve significant imbalances between generation and demand.

- Tertiary regulation reserve:

The tertiary reserve is not a mandatory service (however, send the bid is mandatory) and it is a paid complementary service regulated by the electricity market.

The tertiary energy assignment is done 25 minutes before the start of the programming horizon. The maximum power variation that a production unit can make in a maximum time of 15 minutes, and that can be maintained for at least 2 hours.

It allows the System Operator to have a very flexible reserve of available capacity to automatically resolve significant imbalances between generation and demand. The tertiary reserve that generating units bid to the tertiary reserve market must be restricted to the active power increase and decrease that can be accomplished in 15 min and sustained for at least 2 h.

The guidelines for implementation of flexibility measures are based on ENTSO-E Guidelines on Energy Balancing at EU level which define the direction that all EU countries shall take related to balancing. In Spain, the regulator CNMC and the Government establish the guidelines.

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

In Spain, an energy flexible strategy is focused on local energy markets. The development of local electricity markets is a challenge and a necessity to achieve the energy transition. Within the framework of the development of the IREMEL Energy Resources Integration project through Local Electricity Markets that IDAE and OMIE are carrying out, and in order to know the flexibility requirements, the existing distributed energy resources management capabilities that allow the entities join the Stakeholders Group of the aforementioned project.

TURKEY

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

In Turkey there are no storage options at the moment, beside hydro dams. Possible storage technology that could be developed in the future are batteries and large pump-storage plants. Both storage technologies could provide short-term frequency support [104].

Turkey has few base-load resources and could profit from the installation of energy storage to increase energy efficiency and reduce grid imbalances. Thanks to the technological development and the decrease in storage costs both for households and industry, energy storage is gaining attractiveness in Turkey [105]. At the end of January 2019, the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA) has indeed published a draft legislation on energy storage activities [106]. The draft regulation classifies energy storage into [105]:

- Energy storage facility integrated with a licenced electricity generation facility or with a consumption point
- Separated energy storage facility
- Integrated energy storage facility, operated by a distribution network operator

Moreover, the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources of Turkey will issue the final form of energy storage system at the end of 2019 in order to implement storage options for renewable energy plants. TÜPRAŞ is also planning to build a storage system for reliability concerns and for compensating the fluctuating productions.

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

As stated in the Electricity Market Law n. 6446, the Turkish electricity market consists of [107]:

- Balancing Power Market (BPM) and ancillary services market, operated by TEIAS
- Day-ahead and intraday market, operated by EXIST
- Derivatives market on power contracts, operated by Borsa Istanbul
- Central settlement and clearing, operated by Takasbank

The balancing market offers to TSOs the possibility of providing a reserve capacity. Within 15 minutes, balancing units can participate to the balancing market with a load of minimum 10 MW.

The ancillary services market includes [108]:

- Primary Frequency Control (PFC)
- Secondary Frequency Control (SFC)

In Turkey, Electricity Market Ancillary Services Regulation took effect as of 01.02.2018. Since then, the primary and secondary frequency control reserve capacities have been supplied from generators in scope of the regulation. In scope of agreements between primary frequency control service providers (generators) and TEIAS, generators continuously provide primary frequency control reserve amount that will meet frequency control obligation determined within the scope of Electricity Market Ancillary Services. Price that will be paid by TEIAS in return of the service is

calculated according to the formulation defined upon the primary frequency control service unit cost that is calculated by TEIAS in line with the Electricity Market Ancillary Service Regulation.

Specifically, primary and secondary reserves are provided by conventional power plants in Turkey. For the provision of secondary reserves hydro- and gas-fired power plants are used. Currently minimum reserve amount is set at 1200 MW during the day and 700 MW during the night [104]. In Figure 0-73 and Figure 0-74 the monthly average reserve volumes for primary and secondary frequency control in 2018 are shown.

Figure 0-73: Monthly average PFC reserve volume in 2018 [108]

Figure 0-74: Monthly average SFC reserve volume in 2018 [108]

The main function of EXIST is to identify the most economically efficient dispatch of available power generation. As generators bid at their marginal cost, a merit order is created, and generators receive production orders according to their offers, until demand of that specific hour is met. Network and reliability constraints are ignored in this day-ahead market clearing. The example in Figure 0-75 illustrates the identification of the market clearing price (MCP), which is determined on an hourly basis in the day-ahead market, based on the bids of generators and requests of consumers in the market for that hour.

Figure 0-75: Average market clearing price on hourly basis in 2018 [108]

Security and reliability criteria are taken into account only in a second step, after market clearing: Final commitment and dispatch of power plants are determined by the national dispatch centre (NDC) of TEİAŞ in day-ahead and intra-day balancing markets, as illustrated in Figure 0-76: . The security criterion, laid out in the grid code, is based on the N-1 contingency criteria: In case of failure of any single network equipment, undisturbed operation of the entire needs to be guaranteed. In addition, reliability criteria need to be fulfilled, including the availability of sufficient amounts of spinning reserves, as defined by regulations introduced by ENTSO-E.

Figure 0-76: Responsibilities of TEİAŞ in PX day-ahead and intra-day balancing markets

Three different kinds of re-dispatch and commitment orders are given, if necessary, for either achieving supply-demand- balance at this hour (called “Code 0” order), for avoiding network constraints due to branch overloading (congestion) (“Code 1” order) or for meeting spinning reserve requirements (“Code 2” order). According to the current market rules, re-dispatch costs are defined as system marginal prices (SMP) and allocated to all market participants according to their consumption and peak demand level in power purchase agreements. Re-dispatch orders according to the different codes mentioned on a sample day, January 21, 2017 are presented in Figure 0-77.

Figure 0-77: Redispatch orders on January 21, 2017

As system operator, TEİAŞ takes an active role in managing its operational costs by redispatching resources in short-term markets (day-ahead and intra-day balancing markets) based on market participants' bids for balancing the system load, managing congestion, and maintaining system security and reliability [21].

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

In [104] different strategies to integrate renewable energy in the Turkish grid have been analysed (see Figure 0-78). To facilitate the integration of renewable energy, flexibility measures need to be implemented in Turkey. Possible flexibility strategies are storage and flexible thermal generation, combined with demand response mechanisms.

In the study the flexibility options within strategy 2 are [104]

- Flexible thermal power plants, in terms of ramping and minimum load
- Pumped storage power plant, with a capacity of 1400 MW, near Gökçekaya power plant, offering secondary frequency control
- 600 MW of distributed batteries, for secondary frequency control
- Reduce demand up to 5% at a specified hour

Figure 0-78: Scenarios for renewable energy integration and grid flexibility in Turkey [104]

Strategies for RE Grid Integration		Simulation Cases	Parameters for Assessment of Result
Main Scenarios Resource Driven Allocation	Allocate Wind and Solar Generation by Resource Quality	Base Case 20 GW Wind and Solar Resource Driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transmission Investments (in Million Euros) Redispatch Amounts (in TWh/year and % of total generation) Wind and Solar Curtailment (in TWh/year and % of total generation) Congestion Duration on Lines (in hours per years)
Strategy 1 System Driven Allocation	Reallocate Wind and Solar Generation by Balancing Resource Quality and Local Demand	Doubling (x2) 40 GW Wind and Solar Resource Driven	
Strategy 2 Flexibility Options	Storage Systems (Pumped Storage and Battery) Wind and Solar Curtailment & Demand Response Flexible Thermal Units	Tripling (x3) 60 GW Wind and Solar Resource Driven	

In a more recent study [106], cost and benefits of the most promising flexibility strategies are introduced:

- Retrofitting old coal-fired power plants would have the benefit of a faster response and an increased secondary control reserve capability. However, investments would be required.
- Demand response would not require any additional investment, but it has the lowest benefit among the options, due to the high utilization costs.
- Energy storage can be used for frequency control and energy shifting. It requires investment and operation costs.

In addition, Turkey is trying to increase the total installed capacity of renewable energy sources. Hydropower and coal plants are the main players for the current electricity production. The strategy is to add a nuclear power plant in Sinop (Northern part of Turkey) and promote renewable energy production from wind, solar and bioenergy as long as the economic aspects sounds feasible. As Turkey is an important transition point for important natural gas pipelines, natural gas cogeneration plants are expected to compensate for the requirement energy flexibility in national electricity distribution grid.

GREECE

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The technological advances related to energy flexibility in Greece includes Battery Energy Storage Systems (with increased lifetime and reduced costs), which is a generic solution for every industrial sector. In each sector, there are special cases technicalities that can be exploited. The most common generation and storage options at factory level are mainly BESS and heat storage.

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

The Transitory Flexible Remuneration Mechanism (TFRM), which was elaborated and was approved by the European Commission in 2016 was terminated by the end of April 2017 according to the provisions of the Decision of the European Commission (SA 38968 /2015/N). The aim of this mechanism was to compensate electricity generators in the interconnected system for the provision of “flexibility services” to the TSO [29]. In particular, on instruction from the TSO and subject to a specified notice period, beneficiaries increased or decreased the amount of electricity injected into the electricity system at a specified minimum rate on a multi-hour time-scale. The scheme entered into force for a period of 12 months, from 01.05.2016 to 30.04.2017 and the level of remuneration was set administratively to 45.000 €/MW/year. In 2017 RAE issued Decision 346/2017 for the amendment of the provisions of System Operation Code (Government Gazette B103 / 31.01.2012) and the Market Clearance Manual for the implementation of the Methodology for the imposition of sanctions (Government Gazette B1655 / 15.05.2017), for the implementation of the TFRM. In view of the expiry of the TFRM, and taking into account the continuing needs of the System for flexibility until the full implementation of the Target Model, RAE, within its remit to monitor the security of the energy supply of the country (No.12 N.4001 / 2011), assessed the need to adopt a new flexibility remuneration mechanism. In this context, RAE asked from ADMIE the elaboration and submission of a Flexibility Needs Study for the period 2018- 2027. Based on the findings of this study, RAE proceeded to an inventory of the basic principles of the new mechanism, called Transitory Flexible Capacity Remuneration Mechanism ("FCRM"), which were put in a public consultation in June 2017. This proposed mechanism, given its transitory nature, resembles the basic parameters of its predecessor. However, an essential differentiation point is the introduction of a competitive tendering procedure for the determination of the compensation. RAE provided technical support to the Greek authorities to submit this mechanism to the European Commission and, following its evaluation and approval, RAE within the framework of its competencies and related legislation authorization will make the necessary modification and specialization of the regulatory framework to secure its credible and workable implementation of this mechanism to the benefit of the country's security of supply.

The legislation and the regulatory framework in Greece are still trying to adapt to more advanced schemes (as the one applied in Germany). Nothing conclusive yet, but since the RES percentage is increasing, the framework will most probably adopt to this change.

Provisions of Balancing Services (The Imbalance Settlement Mechanism) Balancing are not performed through a separate balancing market, but as an extension of the day-ahead market (a second submarket), through the Imbalance Settlement Mechanism, with the following rules [109]:

- All imbalances - referring to deviations between the day-ahead schedule and the real production or withdrawal of electricity - are settled through the Imbalance Settlement Mechanism.
- The imbalance settlement is conducted for each hourly trading period.
- During real-time operation, balancing energy is provided by the responsible body, based on the economic merit order of the offers that are submitted by the committed units on the day-ahead market.
- As soon as the relevant meter measurements are available, the imbalances are settled. Without explicit reference to technical details, the main concept is that each imbalanced

party pays or receives an amount, depending on whether it injected or withdrew energy from the System, considering whether the change of its output compared to its day-ahead schedule is consistent with the TSO's instruction, or is caused due to other, plant-specific reasons. The final amount is mainly determined by three (3) parameters: a) the ex-post clearing price, b) the imbalance quantity (TSO instructed or not), and c) the real (metered) quantity.

- The ex-post clearing price results from the re-run of the day-ahead scheduling algorithm under the realized values of the stochastic variables and corresponds to the “Market Clearing Price” (i.e. uniform price).
- Moreover, a cost recovery mechanism is included, to ensure that generators will receive at least their marginal cost whenever they operate. The objective of the imbalance mechanism setting is to minimize the total cost of operation of the System, while reimbursing plant flexibility

The Balancing Settlement is performed by the TSO. Under certain circumstances (emergency cases), it is possible to use “balancing energy” from abroad, by using the residual capacity of interconnectors. In view of the EU Target Model implementation, RAE is elaborating the necessary market design changes, including the introduction of intra-day and balancing markets. During 2017, RAE initiated the procedure for the redefinition, and notably the significant increase of the existing Administrative Defined Maximum Offer Price to provide Primary and Secondary Reserves (from the current price of 10 € / MWh to 50 € / MWh).

Finally, in Greece there are not yet any restrictions, guidelines or financial incentives, concerning the energy flexibility, either in political or in financial level.

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

Since the initiation of the deregulation process in 2000, the market design has evolved, not independently of the underlying market structure, but in response to its asymmetries or inefficiencies, intending to alleviate the distortions arising from structural features. In 2011, the market got more mature, in the sense that substantial new capacity had entered the system, intensifying competition for medium and peak demand. Still, severe liquidity problems and credit risks started to emerge in the energy sector, partially reflecting the economic recession but also the effects of policies regarding retail and renewables tariffs. The implemented policies had been appealing to governments in the context of social policy and renewables growth respectively, but interpreted as revenue streams, they were internally inconsistent. Costs were not correctly reflected or adequately transferred across the value chain, creating sustained debts in the renewables account, managed by the TSO, and diminishing gradually its liquidity. Two other political choices applied in 2011, the introduction of a tax levy on natural gas and of a property tax on the electricity bill, created adverse effects on competition and consumers' payments respectively. Debt issues, which were expected to escalate in 2012, raised unprecedented challenges for the market participants, the TSO and the regulator. This explosive situation stimulated the exploration of alternative ways to move forward and is likely to initiate structural reforms in the coming years, consistently with the need for market adjustment to the internal market paradigm envisaged for 2015.

More specifically, the Greek wholesale electricity market has been organised as a pure mandatory pool since its inception in 2005, so as to allow competition to emerge in a context with a severe constraint: no structural reforms were implemented on PPC, the previous monopolist, such as plant divestures or consumers release, as elsewhere in Europe. In particular, the incumbent remained dominant in both generation and retail sectors, retaining exclusive access to cheap lignite and hydro resources, while retail prices, despite the gradual removal of cross-subsidies, remained not linked to wholesale costs. This combination of market features posed severe obstacles to new entry in early years of market liberalisation, signifying capacity shortage over the following years. The capacity certificates introduced in 2006 created incentives for new investment, which turned out to be adequate, as almost 2000 MW of new, IPP gas capacity were added to the system by the end of 2011. Still, projections for strong and prolonged demand growth (around 2.5% at the annual level) were disrupted in 2009, when demand sank by 7% due to the erupting economic crisis, and has not recovered since then. Hence, a substantial capacity surplus has emerged, with limited export possibilities and limited cost-reduction flexibility. In addition to diminished demand levels, the increasing renewables penetration steadily curtails gas generation to an extent that may even expose them to the take-or-pay penalties implicit in their gas supply contracts.

Furthermore, wholesale prices remain low, not reflective of the full energy production cost. Their levels are suppressed due to significant amounts of compulsory quantities, including mandatory hydro, plants' minimum operational levels, and renewables, which currently constitute a fast escalating component. The deviation between the depressed wholesale levels and the high feed-in-tariffs applied for renewables reimbursement has created a sustained (not temporal but structural) debt in the renewables account, managed by the TSO, which reduces its liquidity and hence, its ability to pay conventional generators and importers over 2012. Simultaneously, consumers' debt (unpaid electricity bills) escalated to 1.4 billion (estimated value) at the end of 2011 due to the severe economic recession and the incorporation of a property tax into the electricity bill, which magnified its amount. This convulsion of adverse conditions and inconsistent policies has raised severe financial problems for market participants and the TSO, which started to become more evident in 2011 and escalated over 2012.

In this challenging environment, RAE is assessing a restructuring of the market design, so as to reduce costs, enhance competition across the value chain, as well as compatibility with the European target model.

Within the context of the European Union's Directives and under the legislative framework of Law 4001/2011, the spin-off (legal and operational unbundling) of the transmission activity from the vertically-integrated PPC S.A. took place in 2011. The Independent Power Transmission Operator, ADMIE S.A., a 100% subsidiary of PPC, was registered as Société Anonyme in November 2011, by having transferred to it all relevant transmission assets, activities and personnel, and reported its first financial statements on 31.12.2011. Its official operation started on February 1st, 2012.

In November 2011, RAE issued Decision 1412 on the "Guidelines for the Certification of Transmission System Operators", which describes the evaluation criteria and the documentation required for certification. The Transmission System Operator (TSO) candidate must document its legal and operational unbundling from the vertically-integrated enterprise, established on the grounds of

- the independence of management

- the independence of financial resources, and
- the independence of operational activities.

The first phase (i.e. through the National Regulator) of the certification process for ADMIE SA was completed in July 2012, by the issuing of RAE's decision 672/2012, which was then forwarded to the European Commission for its further consideration and approval.

Referring to the Distribution Activity, the legal and operational unbundling took place in May 2012, with the establishment of DEDDIE S.A., as the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator, a 100% subsidiary of PPC, and the transfer of the entire distribution business unit to this new company. The network assets, however, still belong to PPC.

Recent investments and alliances that occurred in the energy market of Greece are the following:

1. The acquisition of an interest in the Heron II power plant by Qatar Petroleum International, in agreement with the Greek company GEK TERNA. The acquisition of 24% of the stake of ADMIE by China State Grid. The acquisition from a consortium of 3 TSOs based in Europe of 66% of DESFA.
2. Significant energy investments consist of placements from investment funds, concerning the Energy Oil & Gas. Investments on Renewables and investments in industrial energy from USA and Canadian Companies.
3. Strategic alliances/investments plans between international and local groups that are likely to occur in the following years.

Wind energy installed capacity, in the case of Greece, is expected to triple by 2030, which means that wind energy sub-sectors production is expected to increase to 15 GWh. This is also the case of PV output, which is also expected to triple, whereas the projections for hydropower energy show a significant increase of approximately 20%.

The interest in the Greek Energy Sector is traced in the energy projects concerning the transmission and distribution systems, new projects in power generation (RES and conventional), the increase of energy efficiency investments and the upcoming privatizations of major energy companies (DEPA). These developments along with the digital and operational transformation of the Greek banking system, the intense effort for the reduction of non-performing exposures by the banks and the banks' participation to the energy investments, due to low credit risk, create favourable opportunities. The National Energy Plan of Greece, which is scheduled by 2030 is also very promising and provides preferable modifications for investments. The greatest proportions of the investments which will be included in this plan refer to energy efficiency, RES electricity generation and infrastructure which are already the main targets for investments. The recent modifications of the RES market seem to be positive towards a mature and competitive environment for the interested parties. The new bidding procedure for the RES licenses has already created a new market operation for stakeholders, given that the RES projects remain a promising sector.

Greece is expected to create energy investment opportunities due to the availability of RES potential and the constant sizeable infrastructure project. Based on the Target Model, RES generators could sell electric energy directly in the market and would be subject to balancing responsibilities, unless no liquid Intra-day market exists. Based on the new framework,

participation in the market is translated to more opportunities for additional income, through market optimization techniques and provision of balancing services. Therefore, RES energy can outsource the new obligations to services provided by the RES aggregators, though this structure may show additional risks and costs. Moreover, Greece should simplify the procedure of production licensing, a fact that would directly allow the country to fully exploit its energy resources and develop a strong local supply chain supported by the international interconnections. According to RAE, the main risk that affected Greek RES sector was the country crisis. The risk seems nowadays significant low since the Greek economy shows stability and recovery. Finally, the total investments related to RES stand at 46,2% out of the total amount which projected to be invested in the Greek Energy Market by 2030 [43].

NORWAY

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Digital technologies play an important role in the operation of the power system, for management, control and monitoring purposes. Since January 2019 all Norwegian households are provided with advanced metering systems, delivering data on consumption, load and voltage to grid operators [110].

Customers owning smart meters will access to detailed information on electricity prices and, on the other hand, grid operators will be able to set grid tariffs based on customers' peak loads [110].

Stattnet is developing a data hub (Elhub) to store energy data and provide a monitoring platform to power suppliers.

Energy storage technologies also play an important role in the context of energy flexibility. The technical improvement of solar cells, batteries and hydrogen storage technologies could affect the flexible generation in Norway, based on hydropower [110].

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

As described above, Norway trades electricity in the Nord Pool. The Nord Pool is divided into zones, defined at national level by the respective TSOs. In Norway there are 4 bidding zones (see Figure 0-79). Those zones are however often adjusted by Stattnet.

Figure 0-79: Bidding zones in Norway [110]

The main physical volume consumed in Norway is traded in the Day-Ahead market. Intraday and balancing enable to adjust the portfolio close to the operational hour [62].

The financial forward market is regulated by the Financial Supervisory Authority of Norway and has the aim of assuring to market participants their positions months or years ahead of delivery [62].

Figure 0-80: Wholesale market in Norway [62]

As shown in Figure 0-80, the wholesale market in Norway is divided into [62]:

- The Day-Ahead Market (DAM) closes at 12:00 PM, e.g. 12-36 hours, before delivery. In the Nordic and Baltics the DAM is operated by Nord Pool. The trading is regulated by an implicit

auction where price and volume are calculated for every hour of the following day. Both consumers and producers can bid in the auction. The Day-Ahead price for each bidding zone considers the capacity of the transmission grid, provided daily at 10:00 AM by the TSO. The Nordic system price is based on the DAM calculations and is used as reference for price setting in the financial market and for bilateral/retail contracts.

- The **Intraday Market** opens three hours after closure of the Day-Ahead Market and is operated by Nord Pool. In the intraday market participants can trade until one hour before the production hour in order to correct eventual imbalances.
- The **balancing markets** are operated by the TSO Statnett and consists of
 - primary reserves (FCR), activated automatically, with the fastest response
 - secondary reserves (aFRR), activated automatically
 - tertiary reserves (mFRR), activated manually when needed, with the slowest response (15 minutes)
- The **imbalance settlement** takes place after the operational time and is currently regulated by the TSO.

Norway is part of the Nordic power system (together with Denmark, Finland and Sweden), where the balancing market consists of [111] (see Figure 0-81):

- **FCR (Frequency Containment Reserve)**
 - FCR-D, to balance the system in case of disturbances
 - FCR-N, to balance the system within normal frequency.
- **FRR (Frequency Restoration Reserve)**
 - aFRR, automatically activated. It was introduced in 2013. It is based on a merit order and has a faster response than mFRR.
 - mFRR, manually activated (15 minutes), used for power balancing and to react to congestions and disturbances.
- **RR (Replacement Reserve)**

Figure 0-81: Reserve products in the Nordic power system [111]

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

The power system operation in Norway has a high-flexibility grade, thanks to hydro capacity in reservoirs, and low carbon dioxide emissions in comparison to European countries. Norway has therefore no intention to build a national capacity mechanism.

The integration of renewable energy sources in Europe requires the increase of energy flexibility in the power system. Norway has the potential of providing seasonal storage and short-term flexibility, through its hydropower plants. Nord Pool plays an important role in this context, however a stricter collaboration between TSOs of the different countries would be needed to manage the power exchanges and increase flexibility [33].

The evolution of the power system in Norway is connected to the one of neighbouring countries, as for instance through decommissioning of nuclear plants in Sweden the regional capacity might be reduced. Norway will have thus to adapt to the changes in the European Union.

The main actions to be taken by the Norwegian government are [33]:

- Improve cooperation and move gate closure to 15 minutes ahead of real time, instead of 60 minutes
- Create an independent regulator

Decrease the electricity peak load by integrating energy efficiency strategies

FRANCE

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The development of smart grids is one of the main priorities in France. In 2013 the initiative Think Smart Grids was founded in France to support the development of smart grid solutions [112]. Innovation in the areas of power system flexibility include power-to-gas, demand response and storage technologies.

With an increased share of renewable energy sources (RES) and the reduction of nuclear power in the energy mix, new thermal power station would have to compensate the volatility of RES generation. Smart grids could however reduce the need for thermal power stations, by increasing monitoring and forecasting and enabling hence real-time adaptation of load and generation. Smart grid consists in the connection of several components in an integrated IT system [112].

A recent study performed by RTE analysed the combination of different flexibility solutions, including storage (batteries and hydroelectric power stations), demand response, both in the industrial and residential sector, and modulation of wind power (curtailment) [112].

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

One of the main objectives of the energy transition is to increase the flexibility of the power system. The balance responsible party system (see Figure 0-82) allows consumers, producers, suppliers and traders to carry out commercial transactions with different timeframes. There are around 180 balance responsible parties in France. Each party has the responsibility of creating an activity portfolio and keeping the balance within the portfolio [35].

The balance responsible party system consists mainly of [35]:

- The **Regulated Access to Historical Nuclear Electricity scheme**, the so-called *Accès Régulé à l'Électricité Nucléaire Historique (ARENH)*, which allows alternative suppliers to buy a portion of EDF's nuclear generation at a rate of € 42/MWh by requesting to exercise their ARENH rights to the Energy Regulatory Commission.
- The **balancing mechanism**, with the aim of keeping a balance between generation and demand.
- The **demand response mechanism**, which allows demand response operators or electricity supplier to send requests to consumers to reduce the electricity withdrawal. There are two kinds of demand response, industrial or distributed (residential or professional customers). Since 2011, RTE has been contracting mFRR (manual frequency restoration reserves), that can be activated on short notice. Since 2014 a new mechanism has been introduced in France, the NEBEF (Demand Response Block Exchange Notification), which allows participants to plan demand response the day before its activation.
- The **tariff-based demand response**, including the EJP (Effacement Jour de Pointe - demand response during peak days), where supply prices are increased during system peaks, and the Tempo signal, to allow suppliers to propose contracts for demand response.

- The **capacity mechanism**, launched in 2016 in France to ensure security of supply in medium term. Electricity suppliers are required to obtain capacity certificates to cover the demand of their customers during peak periods (several years in advance). RTE certifies the capacity of operators who are willing to make their capacity available during demand peaks. Capacity certificated are traded through auctions.

Figure 0-82: Balance responsible party system in France [35]

The French balancing market is defined through [2]:

- automatic services related to frequency restoration
 - FCR (Frequency Containment reserve - primary control), procured since July 2019 on daily basis, instead of weekly basis. The minimum bid size is 1 MW.
 - aFRR (Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve - secondary control), with a minimum bid size of 1 MW. Activation takes place on pro-rata basis. This reserve is not open to market players, only to large generators; the TSO can provide access to other market participants.
- manual services
 - mFRR (Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve - tertiary control), regulated by an annual tender. The minimum bid size is 10 MW. The activation time is 15 minutes.
 - RR (replacement reserve), adjustable in 30 minutes over a period running from 1 April to 31 March.

The access rules are proposed by RTE and approved by CRE [113]. Figure 0-83 provides further details related to the French balancing market.

Figure 0-83: Balancing market in France [113]

	Response time	Capacity procured	Energy (2016)	Participating entities	Procurement of capacity
FCR	< 30s	570 MW	↑236 GWh ↓232 GWh	Generators and consumers from FCR cooperation countries	FCR Cooperation weekly auction and secondary market
aFRR	< 15m	~700 MW	↑1,2 TWh ↓1,4 TWh	Generators and consumers in France	Compulsory participation, regulated price and secondary market
mFRR	< 13m	1000 MW	↑1,4 TWh ↓2,5 TWh	Generators and consumers in France	Call for tender
RR	< 30m	500 MW	↑1,2 TWh ↓1,5 TWh	Generators and consumers in France	Call for tender
	Other	~	~	Generators in France Other entities	Compulsory participation of available capacity Contracting

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

The Energy Transition for Green Growth Act requires the formulation of a new energy strategy, including the reduction of nuclear power in the electricity mix. In order to achieve a 40% share of renewable energy in the generation mix, energy flexibility plays a key role. Nuclear plants shall in fact adapt their operation to the volatile generation from renewable sources.

France is currently reinforcing the collaboration between research bodies and industry to boost the energy transition. The National Alliance for the Co-ordination of Research (ANCRE) was founded with the aim of contributing to the formulation of a national energy strategy [114].

The capacity mechanism developed by RTE encourages investments in generation and demand side management systems. RTE is involved in several European projects and large-scale initiatives together with ENTSO-E [115].

ITALY

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The following sections focus on the electrochemical storage systems, considering the key role they are expected to play in the coming years for the transition from the mostly current centralised electricity generation networks to distributed ones with increasing penetration of variable and not programmable renewable energy sources and more “intelligent” management of the energy flows, (with Smart Grids and “pro-users”, who are end-users with more active role in the electricity market).

They have the potential to support the national electrical system, being able to supply multiple network services and applications at different level of the electrical system, thanks to their characteristics of flexibility, versatility and modularity.

First of all, the electrochemical storages may find application in electricity generation plants from fuel or renewable sources. The storage devices can reduce the imbalances respect to the production forecast, and provide other network services such as voltage and frequency regulation. Finally, the production time shift can also be useful for accumulating energy in moments of congested network or when prices are low and feeding it into the grid at more favourable times in terms of network conditions or energy value. This can be a contribution to the fluidity of the energy market. In this sense, storage systems favour the aggregation of the electricity production from small and medium-sized plants into programmable large-scale production and storage systems.

With regard to the electricity transmission sector, the Italian network operators have identified electrochemical storage systems as an interesting strategy both for upgrading the electrical infrastructure and for managing the system in real time. In fact, the plants powered by renewable sources pertaining to the sub-transmission system, typically wind power plants, are often located in areas where the electricity grid is not very developed and may prove inadequate to accommodate the energy in some situations of high availability.

Also in the electricity distribution sector, the use of electrochemical storage systems may constitute a sustainable alternative to the traditional network enhancement, and provide those services useful for conducting it, helping DSOs in the path of growth towards the role of "Local dispatchers" of the network.

Furthermore, concerning the end users, the recent incentive measures assign an important role to the electrochemical storage systems installed at the plants. They allow not only a more flexible management of the user's system, but enable to actively participate in the management of the grid network [116].

In Italy, 37 electrochemical storage plants are installed or being installed for a total of 82 MW, of which mostly owned by Terna and Enel [42].

In particular, under the Defence Plan for the Security of the Italian Electricity System 2012-2015, Terna has identified a 75 MW storage-system installation programme, divides into Energy Intensive project and Power Intensive project, as can be seen in Figure 0-84.

- **The Large Scale Energy Storage Project**, launched in 2011, involves the installation of 35 MW of NaS batteries for energy intensive applications, to reduce grid congestions and to supply network services to ensure greater flexibility in the management of renewable energy plants, favouring their integration.

The total 35 MW capacity storage is divided among three NCSSs (Non-Conventional Storage System), located in the South of Italy (around Benevento city, Campania): two installations of 12 MW (Ginestra and Flumeri) and one of 10.8 MW (Scampitella).

- **The Storage Lab**, launched in 2012, envisages a two-stage installation of 40 MW of various storage technologies for power intensive applications, in order to increase the safety of the grid in the large islands (i.e. Sardinia and Sicily).

The first stage consists in the installation of 16 MW, divided into approximately 8 MW in Sicily and 8 MW in Sardinia. Nowadays, about 13 MW of multi-technological plants have been installed. The individual storage units, approximately 1 MW, are lithium-based (9,2 MW, 5 types) and of the ZEBRA type (3,4 MW, 2 types). Flow battery technologies are currently integrated in the project and to complement the existing technological programme, Terna also planned to install super-capacitor systems [16].

In the second stage, further 24 MW will be installed in Codrongianos (Sardinia) and Casuzze (Sicily) [66].

Figure 0-84: Terna's Storage Project [66]

In spite of many positive aspects related to electrochemical storage systems, there are still factors that limit their growth in the national market. The main barriers are:

- lack of familiarity with storage technology among utilities, regulators and financiers;
- lack of efficient long-term price signals capable of providing sufficient guarantees on the return of capital to lenders;
- technology is not yet mature in terms of storage capacity, energy density, power performance, lifetime, charging capabilities;
- high upfront costs, however they are expected to drop significantly within ten years or so.

The industry sector seems to have well understood the potential of the battery market and has seen the emergence of several players both for residential applications, particularly in combination with photovoltaic systems (ABB, SMA, Samsung, Tesla, Sonnenbatterie, BYD) and for applications on the grid (Siemens, Samsung, Toshiba, Fiamm, General Electric) [117].

Energy storage technologies are differentiated by the electrochemical species, type of electrolyte and construction characteristics as well as technical performances. They have different intrinsic properties that determine their technical suitability for certain applications or provide certain services to electricity system. Figure 0-85 shows different electrochemical storage systems and their key grid applications.

Figure 0-85: Grid electrochemical storage technologies and applications [118]

Application	Pb acid	Ni/MH	Na/S	Na/NiCl ₂	Redox Flow	Li/ion	Super capacitor
Time-shift	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Renewable integration	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Network investment deferral	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Primary Regulation	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Secondary Regulation	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Tertiary Regulation	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Power System start-up	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Voltage support	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Power quality	●	●	●	●	●	●	●

● Suitable ● Less suitable ● Unsuitable

The main electrochemical storage technologies are the following:

- **Lithium-ion batteries** are the most promising electrochemical storage technologies, characterized by long cycle life (up to 10.000 charge/discharge cycles at 80% DOD), high specific energy and specific power as well as high energy efficiency (higher than 90%). They appear to be those that are better suited for almost all applications, working well in energy intensive and power intensive services. The main obstacles are the following: high cost, higher environmental impact than other technologies, issues relating to the thermal stability and safety hazard when they are overloaded or subjected to too high temperatures.
- **High-temperature batteries (NaS and NaCl₂ batteries)** operates at high-temperature around 300°C in order to maintain the active salt materials and liquid and ensure sufficient conductivity of the electrolyte. They are characterized by high specific energy, high energy efficiency, good overcharge and discharge capabilities and good lifetime. They are particularly preferred for stationary storage applications.
- **Redox flow batteries** (of which the highest level of maturity was achieved by vanadium redox flow battery VRFB) are mainly featured by the total decoupling of power and energy. The power that the battery can supply or absorb depends on the quantity of electrolyte which takes part in the reaction instant by instant (compatibly with the speed of the reaction) and therefore by the membrane surface and pump speed. While, the storage capacity is linked to the total amount of electrolyte and therefore to the capacity of the tanks, therefore, for the same installed power, it is possible to increase the capacity of the battery by increasing the tank dimensions. These technologies are suitable for large scale applications (energy intensive), however their versatility makes it possible to use them even for power intensive

applications. The main disadvantages are the excessive complexity and low energy/volume ratio.

- **Lead-acid batteries** are the most widespread electrochemical storage technology. They have a good cost-performance ratio in a wide range of applications. However, they are very heavy and characterized by relatively low energy density, short lifetime, and toxicity [41] [42].

Economic impact of energy flexibility technologies

The costs related to electrochemical storage depend on the type of technology used Table 0.26 reports the installation costs and operation and maintenance costs for each electrochemical storage technology. For variable O&M costs calculation, it was assumed that the system performs at 80% DOD discharge/charge cycle for time-shift applications. Other applications may involve different values.

Table 0.26: Installation and O&M costs for each electrochemical storage technology [42]

Technology	Installation cost [€/kWh]	O&M fixed costs [€/kWh*y]	O&M variable costs [€/kWh*y]
Lead-acid	300	15	0,087
Nickel-cadmium	800	15	0,304
Nickel-metal hybrid	800	15	0,304
Sodium-nickel	560	10	0,304
Sodium-sulphur	500	10	0,031
Lithium-ions	500	10	0,023
VRFB	800	15	0,013

Lead-acid batteries are the most economic solutions because of their technological and market maturity, while the vanadium redox flow batteries are the most expensive ones, due mainly to their complexity.

Lithium-ions and sodium-based batteries actually have a similar positioning on the market, with a CAPEX cost around 500 €/kWh. They can be considered the main competitors on the future market of electrochemical storage. In fact, investment costs of these technologies are expected to drop significantly within ten years or so, in particular the cost of lithium-ions batteries for which a reduction by 40% is expected.

The O&M cost depends on periodic maintenance (topping up of electrolyte, periodic clamping of the terminals, energy cost for the supply of power air conditioning/ventilation, etc.), plus the replacing of the battery during the useful life of the plant. Lifetime of battery is different for each technology and also depends on the type of application.

The payback time (PBT) of electrochemical storage systems depends strongly on the type of application, but currently it is estimated to be 10 years for almost all applications to support the electricity system [42].

Environmental impact of energy flexibility technologies

The environmental impact associated with the electrochemical storage systems depends on the application and the type of technology used.

Lead-acid batteries and **nickel-cadmium batteries** are the most impacting ones due to the presence of toxic materials. For this reason, they require specified disposal management. The disposal of lead-acid batteries is managed by authorized and specialized companies, i.e. COBAT (Mandatory Consortium for exhausted lead batteries and lead waste), which ensures the collection and recycling of exhausted batteries; while the nickel-cadmium batteries are classified as hazardous waste and they must be collected by the producer and recycled in specialized facilities.

Lithium-ions batteries entail high environmental impacts because of they contain rare earths which have limited diffusion on the terrestrial crust as well as heavy metals, lithium and highly reactive alkali metals. Although recycling procedures have been developed for these, they are generally not applied and batteries are landfilling due to the high costs.

Instead, **high-temperature batteries** are the most ecological solutions and they are completely recyclable.

Also **vanadium redox flow batteries** are completely recyclable, being mainly composed of plastic materials (stack, pipes, tanks). While the electrolyte disposal, which contains a concentration of sulfuric acid slightly lower than the lead batteries, must follow the methods of special waste treatment. However, it can be completely recycled and reused.

Focusing on the carbon footprint, the electrochemical storage implementation could allow a significantly carbon saving. For example, approximately 100 g CO₂ eq./kWh are saved when using 50 kW photovoltaic system associated with lead battery, which entails 152 g CO₂ eq./kWh according to literature study [119], compared to the Italian electricity grid mix (457 g CO₂ eq./kWh) [42].

Social impact of energy flexibility technologies

The social acceptance of electrochemical storage technologies can be divided into three distinct dimensions: socio-political acceptance, community acceptance, market acceptance.

Regarding the first one, there is a high acceptability of technologies and policies which encourages the renewables sources diffusion.

Community acceptance depends mainly on the choose of the installation site. The citizens living in the immediate vicinity of the plants tends to oppose the installation of new technologies. However, the electrochemical storage systems would be installed near pre-existing plants, so they should not create strong dissents of the local community.

Regarding the market acceptance, these technologies could be accepted by operators and consumers, given the growing interest of the renewables source market and the promising advantages which they involve. Although there is still a lack of familiarity with storage technology among utilities, regulators and financiers.

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

The National Energy Strategy (SEN 2017) sets objectives to be achieved by 2030 in line with the Energy Union Plan:

- ✓ improve the country's competitiveness, continuing to reduce the price and energy cost gap with Europe, in a context of rising international prices;
- ✓ achieve and sustainably overcome the 2030 environmental and decarbonisation objectives defined at European level, in line with the future targets established in COP21;
- ✓ continue to improve security of supply and flexibility of energy systems and infrastructures in order to:
 - integrate growing quantities of electrical renewables, including distributed ones, and new players, enhancing and evolving networks and markets towards smart, flexible and resilient configurations;
 - manage the variability of flows and peaks demand;
 - increase the efficiency of energy expenditure through technological innovation.

National energy context sees an increasing complexity and demand for flexibility of the energy system, for which it is essential to guarantee reliability through:

- adequacy in the ability to satisfy energy needs;
- safety in dealing with changes in the operating status without violations of the system's operating limits;
- resilience to anticipate, absorb, adapt and/or quickly recover from an extreme event [86].

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

The National Energy Strategy (SEN 2017) aims to continue improving the security of supply and flexibility of energy systems and infrastructures, through the following interventions:

- start-up of the Capacity Market in 2018 to guarantee the power system adequacy, maintaining the availability of the gas power still needed, with priority for the flexible one, and integrating new resources in the new market (cross-border units, renewables, storage, active demand) and further enhance interconnections with foreign countries.

The Capacity Market represents one of the main solutions to guarantee that long-term price signals and adequacy conditions of the electricity system are consistent with decarbonisation objectives. The capacity market is a mechanism by which Terna procures capacity through long-term procurement contracts awarded through competitive bidding. It is not reserved only for thermoelectric capacity but open to a plurality of technological, national and cross-border options.

- interventions on networks to integrate renewable sources and increase resilience.
- increase of the storage capacity plants, investments in transmission and distribution networks, opening of the dispatching services market (MSD) to new resources and management of distribution networks in smart grid to increase flexibility [86].

The 55% growth target for non-programmable sources by 2030 requires the development of additional storage capacity. The role of storage systems is being discussed for several years in Italy, since they represent an important resource for the adequacy as well as for the safety and flexibility of the system. They are able to provide fundamental flexibility services:

- **Power-Intensive services**, characterized by short discharge times (in the order of seconds/minutes), able to contribute to the security of the system, such as fast and ultra-fast frequency regulation services;
- **Energy-Intensive services**, characterized by long discharge times (in the order of hours), such as load shifting (accumulation in the hours of overgeneration from RES and release in hours of low demand (usually nights or weekends when electricity is also lower-cost) and network congestion solving.

Among storage technologies, **pumped-hydro storage systems** are actually the most mature technology. They allow to modulate the electrical power supply throughout the day and to feed large amounts of energy into the grid quickly, at costs that are decidedly more advantageous than other storage systems.

For the next years, a strong development of **electrochemical storage systems** is expected both at distributed and centralized level. In particular, they have become fundamental to integrate RES (especially wind and solar energy), and because of the vital role they play in electric mobility [86] [41].

Other important intervention to increase the flexibility consists in **opening of the dispatching services market (MSD) to new resources** (non-programmable renewable sources, distributed generation, demand response, storage) [86]. With Resolution 300/2017/R/eel, Terna in agreement with ARERA has launched a process for progressive opening on the MSD to resources currently not enabled, through a series of pilot projects:

- **Virtually Aggregated Consumption Units (UVAC)**, characterized by the presence of only consumption units;
- **Virtually Aggregated Production Units (UVAP)**, characterized by the presence of only not relevant production units (whether they are programmable or not programmable), including storage systems;
- **Virtually Aggregated Mixed Units (UVAM)**, characterized by the presence of not relevant production units (either programmable or not programmable) including storage systems, and consumption units;
- **Relevant Production Units (UPR) not subject to mandatory participation**, characterized by the presence of relevant production units subject to voluntary enabling and/or not relevant (whether programmable or not programmable), and possibly also consumption units, subtended to the same node of the national transmission network.

The aim of these pilot projects is to immediately increase the amount of resources available to guarantee the adequacy and security of the electricity system at the lowest cost for the end user and, in addition, to diversify the types of resources that can be enabled to the services market.

These pilot projects allow Terna to test the performance of distributed resources whilst also allowing them to involve and incentivise operators, from within and outside the electricity sector, to research innovative solutions for the provision of ancillary services [66].

AUSTRIA

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The switch to renewable energies and increasing energy efficiency in order to achieve the EU climate protection targets poses a major challenge for the Austrian manufacturing and energy-intensive industry. At the same time, Austrian technology providers have the strong opportunity to expand their market leadership position worldwide and make a significant contribution to securing Austria as an industrial location. The current focus of research and development in Austria is the mitigation of emissions from industrial production. The aim is to reduce the use of raw materials and energy, to reduce emissions and to optimize and intensify processes, resulting in a low CO₂ footprint per product produced. However, in many industrial processes, the potential for energy efficiency has already been largely exhausted, and thermodynamic limits are partly reached. It is now increasingly necessary to integrate renewable energies into industrial processes and to synchronize the energy requirements of industrial plants with the availabilities of fluctuating renewables. Therefore, a central role of research and innovation is the advancing digitalisation, which creates new possibilities for making the energy system and industrial processes more flexible. Several strategies have already been implemented in the industrial sector, many are still in development. The following strategies are the most common ones [120, 121]:

- Digitalization (virtual processing, modelling, digital twin, ICT, etc.)
- Industry to grid
- Demand Side Management (DSM)
- Integration of renewables and application of storages (e.g. power-to-x, etc.)
- Exploitation of energy efficiency potentials and development of new processes (e.g. waste heat recovery, waste stream valorisation, etc.)
- Electrification: the shift from any non-electric source of energy to renewable electricity at the point of final consumption (e.g. new electro thermal processes, hydrogen as reducing agent in steel production, etc.)

A common way of on-site generation of electricity and heat is made with CHP plants or/and steam boilers or/and hot water boilers. Often used storage solutions are thermal storages, compressed air storages or gas storages [120, 121].

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

The access to the Austrian Power Grid (APG) control area is organized in two steps, namely the technical prequalification and the framework agreement. In a first step, the technical prequalification is analysed to examine if all required technical criteria are met. The applicant chooses for which type of control energy he wants to apply. Thus, it is not obliged for the applicant to prequalify for all types of control energy, but each type of control energy has to be prequalified separately. The relevant prequalification conditions are stated in the Operation Handbook of ENTSO-E, Policy 1. After three years, the prequalification must be renewed. In a second step, a framework agreement between the applicant and the control area manager is signed to gain an official accreditation. The accreditation does not oblige the partner to apply always for tenders,

but is only the necessary requirement for having the possibility to participate in all tenders. Tenders take place exclusively online at the APG's tendering system (TTS). Therefore, it is necessary to get the personal access details for the TSS system by the APG [122].

In 2016, € 90 million were used for the control energy market in Austria. Compared to 2014, this is a decrease of 37%. In 2018, the control energy costs were around € 68 million. Compared to 2017, again a decrease of 27% [45] [123]. The clearing fees are set by the E-Control, and have to be paid by the balance group representatives (BGRs) to the APCS Power Clearing and Settlement AG. The price for all chargeable physical energy consumption (total metered consumption on the demand side of a balance group's energy balance) is 0,0812 €/MWh, the price for all chargeable energy sales (total energy demand volume of a balance group less its physical energy consumption) is 0,0017 €/MWh [124].

Table 0.27 lists the participants of the control energy market in Austria. These participants are already prequalified and provide FCR, aFRR or mFRR as stated in Table 0.27.

Table 0.27: List of prequalified control energy participants in Austria [125]

Participants	FCR	aFRR	mFRR
A1 Telekom Austria AG		X	X
e2m-Energiehandel GmbH			X
Energie AG Oberösterreich Kraftwerke GmbH	X	X	
EVN AG	X	X	X
GEN-I Vienna GmbH			X
KELAG-Kärntner Elektrizitäts-Aktiengesellschaft	X	X	X
Lechwerke AG			X
Linz Strom GmbH			X
Next Kraftwerke GmbH		X	X
Norske Skog Bruck G.m.b.H. (no publication which control energy type is provided)	-	-	-
ÖBB-Infrastruktur AG		X	X
TIWAG-Tiroler Wasserkraft AG	X	X	
Salzburg AG für Energie, Verkehr und Telekommunikation	X	X	X
VERBUND Solutions GmbH		X	X
VERBUND Trading AG	X	X	X
Illwerke vkw AG			X
Wien Energy GmbH		X	X

FCR

The FCR is activated after a frequency deviation of 200 mHz and above. After 30 seconds of the occurrence, the maximum activation has to be reached and must be available for at least

30 minutes. FCR is activated automatically. The Austrian Power Grid AG must provide a primary control power volume of approximately +/-66 MW. Additionally, a primary control volume of +/-3000 MW is permanently available in the European grid. All Austrian power generators with an installed bottleneck capacity of more than 5 MW cover the costs for the primary energy control [125] [126].

The tendering period lasts for 24 hours (00:00-24:00). Within this period, an equal amount of negative and positive FCR has to be reserved and must be available without interruption. It is not possible to offer positive and negative FCR separately. The bidding period starts usually 14 days before the delivery day (at 11:00), and usually ends 2 working days before delivery day (D-2, 15:00). Since 2015, a cooperation for providing FCR between Austria, Swiss, Germany, Denmark and France exist. In the case that a tender is unsuccessful, suitable suppliers are instructed by law to provide the required FCR. Main parameters for FCR are as follows [127]:

- Primary control volume: +/-66 MW
- Minimum bid: +/-1 MW
- Increments: in full MW until pre-qualified power is met
- Maximum indivisible bids: +/-25 MW

aFRR

If the system is affected or it is assumed that it will be affected for longer than 30 seconds, the secondary control is activated. The secondary control volume depends on the volume of the largest power plant block in the control area, i.e. a failure of the largest power plant block has to be compensated through secondary control. Secondary control is activated automatically for relieving primary control so that it can resume its actual functions [125]. Since 2016, a cooperation between the German and Austrian DSOs for the provision of secondary control energy exists [123].

Secondary energy control is separated in positive and negative control energy. The positive as well as the negative control energy are temporal divided into six 4-hours blocks (00:00-04:00, 04:00-08:00, etc.). The tendering takes place daily and starts always one week before planned delivery (D-7, 10:00). End of the bidding period is one day before planned delivery (D-1, 08:00). Here too, in case of an unsuccessful tender, suitable suppliers are obligated to supply the required aFRR. The main parameters for aFRR are as follows [128]:

- Secondary control: +/-200 MW (daily tendering)
- Minimum bid: first bid per tender 1 MW, for each additional offer 5 MW
- Increments: in full MW until pre-qualified power is met

mFRR

The tertiary control is activated if the system is affected more than 15 minutes. Generally, tertiary control can be activated automatically or manually, whereby a manually activation is used in the Austrian control area. In Austria, the tertiary control is also used to support the secondary control for ensuring grid stability in case of a power plant failure [125].

Same as for the aFRR, the tendering takes place daily and starts one week before the planned delivery (D-7, 10:00) and ends one day before the planned delivery (D-1). However, positive and negative control energy are combined to one product time slot and therefore only six 4-hours

product slots exist (00:00-04:00, 04:00-08:00, etc.), where bids can be placed individually. The main parameters for mFFR are as follows [129]:

- Tertiary control: +280 MW, -195 MW
- Minimum bid: 1 MW
- Increments: in full MW until pre-qualified power is met
- Maximum bid: 25 MW

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

According to the Austrian Climate and Energy Strategy, the use of flexibility in the energy system must be boosted in order to maximize the use of renewable energies. At the same time, existing and new infrastructures have to be used efficiently. The main factors for using flexibility potentials are technical, economic and organizational issues. Flexibility parameters to consider are the quantity of energy, duration of storage, speed of use, chronological availability etc. Involved flexible energy options are as follows:

- Flexibility in the energy supply sector (sector coupling, targeted chronological use of non-volatile sources such as biomass, etc.)
- Flexibility in consumption (e.g. buffering of thermal energy for heating and cooling in building mass, adapting industrial and commercial processes)
- Flexibility through storage facilities (e.g. power storage, heat storage, gas storage.)
- Flexibility through smart network management (e.g. smart electricity networks, flexible heat networks)

The implementation of flexible energy systems requires new successful business models with appropriate regulatory frameworks. However, a secure and stable energy supply has to be maintained. More specific energy flexibility strategies are characterized in the following paragraphs [20].

380-kV ring in Austria

The Austrian Power Grid AG (APG) plans an expansion of its grid and foresees a 380-kV ring concept. The objective is to connect all large cities in Austria with the major generation units. This concept facilitates the sustainable integration of renewables into the grid. The overall aim is to create a high-performance grid infrastructure, where grid optimisation and reinforcement go before expansion and installing new power lines. A total grid investment volume of around € 2.5 billion is foreseen for the next ten years [130].

Sector coupling

Sector coupling is the linkage between hitherto separate systems like power, heat, mobility or industry. It allows all sectors of the economy to decarbonize and to be more flexible, which is the reason why it is seen as a key concept of the energy transition. The current used or at least tested coupling systems in Austria are power-to-gas, power-to-heat, power-to-chemicals and combined heat and power. Part of sector coupling are energy efficient technologies like heat pumps, which help to reduce the energy consumption. Additionally, fluctuations of renewable energies like wind or PV can be balanced without relying only on electricity storage systems. Moreover, through sector coupling, large and cheaper energy reservoirs outside the power sector can be used and

significantly increases flexibility on the power demand side. Biomass helps to increase the energy mix and makes also the supply more flexible. Furthermore, biomass can be used for demand-driven production of heat, electricity or biofuels. To sum up, sector coupling allows to generate many synergies between different energy carriers and is therefore an essential strategy to build a carbon-free and flexible energy system [131].

Electricity Market Design

New energy models for the market have to be developed. So far, enterprises have always been only consumers of energy. In the future, enterprises can either still be consumers, or also be producers of energy and thus turn into prosumers. In Austria, the objective is to provide 100% of electricity consumption through renewable energy sources by 2030. To redesign the electricity market, following actions were identified in Austria [131]:

- Adjust the network tariff structure: push smart meters and prosumer network tariffs for households and businesses
- Provide a stable framework and cut red tape for aggregators
- Raise awareness and strengthen consumer rights
- Divide infrastructure costs fairly
- Test blockchains
- Abolish tax on private electricity generation
- Develop alternative funding instruments and civil participation

Develop the balancing and control energy market and improve system stability

Aim of the control energy market is to keep a balance between supply and demand and thus maintain a secure and stable power grid system. The larger the market for control energy is, the more control power-capable power plants are available, and the easier it is to increase system stability. A stable legal framework at European and national level helps to attract new operators to join the control market. Key actions include [131]:

- Sending market operators the right price signals
- Making the control and balancing power market more attractive
- Improving the internal energy market and increasing flexibility
- Introducing annual flexibility reports
- Adjusting and balancing the tariff structure
- Ensuring network stability

Identified barriers for the implementation of flexibility options [132]:

- Complexity of production processes within a company (specific evaluation necessary)
- Investment required (e.g. storage etc.)
- Responsibility for failures due to flexibility options
- Interaction of ICT and grid operation (compatibility of technologies, suppliers etc.)
- Market barriers (spot market prices too low for economical usage, too many technical requirements for balancing market)
- Knowledge of load shifting and flexibility

- Organizational and systemic challenges for companies (adaption of working times, supply contracts, stock levels etc.)
- Risk of being economical
- Social acceptance (as of loss of flexibility in own enterprise)

To be flexible always implies a reaction to external signals. These can be prices or direct switching signals that are suggested to the plant manager or directly intervene in the process automation. This incorporation into a system in which one is no longer fully flexible and has to surrender some competencies can be an obstacle and lead to a negative attitude. Furthermore, it is also conceivable that competitiveness suffers under the consequently different production conditions [132].

BELGIUM

TECHNOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Industrial Flexibility valorisation is in majority via aggregators (third-parties), who use their own technical solutions to interact with their customers and with the markets where flexibility is valorised. The time delay mainly depends on how flexible the process is, and how quickly it can react to increase/reduce its power consumption/production.

The most common generation options are CHP (steam turbines, gas turbines, gas engines), wind power, solar power. Storage of intermediate product, if coupled with an overcapacity of a production asset, is a source of energy flexibility.

LEGAL AND ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

Flexibility valorisation through ancillary services provision (explicit)

Regarding possibilities for explicit balancing (provision of Ancillary Services), the characteristics of the Ancillary Services related to grid balancing in Belgium are summarized in Table 0.28 including whether or not it is open to Demand-Side Response (participation of industrial consumers).

Table 0.28: Characteristics of ancillary services types in Belgium [133]

Reserve type	Reserve name & direction	Capacity reservation	Reservation payment	Activation timing	Activation payment	Activation rule	Open to Demand-Side Response
FCR	R1, symmetric	Weekly auction, week-ahead	Pay-as-bid	15"	/	Automatic	Yes, in theory
	R1, up	Weekly auction, week-ahead	Pay-as-bid	15"	/	Automatic	Yes

	R1, down	Weekly auction, week-ahead	Pay-as-bid	15''	/	Automatic	Yes, in theory
aFRR	R2, up / down	Weekly auction, week-ahead	Pay-as-bid	7.5'	Pay-as-bid	Pro rata (parallel activation)	No
mFRR	R3, up / down	Month-ahead*	Pay-as-bid	15'	Pay-as-bid	DA bids, Merit order	Yes
	Free bids, up	/	/	15'	Pay-as-bid	ID bids, Merit order	Yes

Flexibility valorisation through market opportunities (implicit)

Regarding possibilities for implicit balancing (valorisation of flexibility on markets), three possibilities exist in Belgium: valorisation on the Day-Ahead market, on the Intraday market or via the Imbalance mechanism.

Day-Ahead market: this is a closed market, closing at 2pm on the previous day, with an hourly granularity. Big industrial consumers can sometimes have a direct access to the market. Otherwise, indirect valorisation of flexibility on the DA market can sometimes be done via energy supplier if its power price is indexed on the DA market. Flexibility activation decisions must be taken one day in advance and the flexibility must be activated for at least one hour.

Intraday market: this is an open market (OTC) where actors can exchange blocks of energy with one-hour granularity. This market size is small in Belgium compared to DA and imbalance. Flexibility activation decisions must be taken latest 15 minutes in advance and the flexibility must be activated for at least one hour.

Imbalance: power consumer must respect their power nominations as well as possible; however, when a consumer balancing error is in a direction that “helps” restoring the grid balance (long if the grid is short or opposite), the differential of energy can be sold at a higher price or purchases at a lower price. This allows a valorisation of flexibility from industrial with quick reactivity. Flexibility activation decisions must be taken for the next quarter-hour or in real-time and the flexibility must be activated for at least one quarter-hour.

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY FLEXIBILITY STRATEGIES

ENTSO-E Guidelines on Energy Balancing (at EU level) define the direction that all EU countries shall take related to balancing, and tend to facilitate the valorisation of industrial flexibility through demand-side response [134].

